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DOREM AND FERULA FLORAS OF KOPETDAG: BIORESOURCES, BIOCHEMISTRY, BIOMEDICINE, RATIONAL USE

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Abstract. *The article provides information on biological resources and phytochemical and pharmacological characteristics of some Dorem and Ferula floras of Kopetdag, which allows to identify the resource possibilities of their use in the pharmaceutical industry of Turkmenistan.*

Keywords: *dorema, ferula, bioresources, biological reserve, phytomass, essential oil, flavonoids, Kopetdag.*

A current task in modern pharmacy and biochemistry is to expand the nomenclature of medicinal plant raw materials, sourced from widely available medicinal plants of the local flora. Despite significant successes in the synthesis of chemical pharmaceuticals and their application, plants continue to be one of the promising sources for obtaining medicinal products. [2, 4, 5].

In recent years, medicinal and other resource plants of the Kopetdag Mountains have been intensively studied as sources of biologically active compounds and as objects for economic use. Despite the relatively small areas occupied by the mountainous ecosystems of Turkmenistan, the plant communities of this region are distinguished by the highest concentration of medicinal, food, fodder, and other groups of useful plants, which, in turn, are closely connected with the environment and household work of people.

We present information on the biological resources, biochemistry, biomedicine, or phytochemical-pharmacological features and bioeconomics of ephemeroïds from the Kopetdag.

Kopetdag *Dorema* (*Dorema kopetdaghense* M. Pimen.) is a perennial herbaceous plant from the celery family (Apiaceae Lindl.), reaching a height of 150–200 cm. It is a taproot monocarpic plant. The stem is cylindrical, tapering, round, branching in the middle into a pyramidal panicle, slightly downy. The leaves are grayish-downy, ternately divided, and their segments are further dissected twice pinnately into oblong-lanceolate parts. The umbels have 5–12 flowers, almost sessile. It blooms in May–June and bears fruit in June–July [2, 8].

It grows in the foothills and lower mountain ranges. It inhabits rocky and ravelly slopes, terraces, and dry riverbeds.

In the Central Kopetdag, it has been recorded in the following locations: Germab, Gokdere, Archabil Canyon, Vannovsky, Neftyanovsky, Yablonovsky, Kurtsuv, Babazav, Dushakerekdag, Kheyraabad, Karaagach, Mergenolen, Kurkulab Arvaz, Gaudan, and others [2, 6, 8].

The aerial parts of Kopetdag *Dorema* contain 0.09–0.12% essential oil, coumarins, and flavonoids. In the roots, the following have been found: resin (19%), terpenoids, and coumarins (umbelliferone).

An extract from the roots of *Dorema* has mild antitumor properties [5]. The resin can be used in the paint and varnish industry. However, the beneficial (including medicinal) properties of *Dorema* in Turkmenistan have not been sufficiently studied. The wide distribution of certain species of the genus, as well as the relatively large raw material reserves, make *Dorema* a promising object for further research and practical use. In the Central Kopetdag, dense thickets of the plant are rare despite its wide distribution. One such area was described by us in the Suncha area, where *Dorema* thickets occupy about 30 hectares. The plant density ranges from 5–6 to 30–35 plants per 100 m². The average weight of a fresh root is 2080.3 g. The above-ground plant mass is 929.6 g. The yield of air-dried raw material is 30% and 28%, respectively. Assuming the number of plants in the area is 36,000 (an average of 12 plants per 100 m²), we estimate that the total biological reserve of air-dried raw material in the area is 22.5 tons of underground and 9.4 tons of above ground phytomass [2].

For harvesting *Dorema* roots, perennial, well-developed vegetative individuals are used, while generative shoots are used for harvesting the grass. Roots are best dug up after the plant has finished its vegetative cycle. Grass is harvested when the leaf mass is at its maximum development, before it starts to dry out. Cut leaves and shoots are pre-chopped and dried in small stacks in the shade. After digging, roots are cleaned of soil remnants and immediately chopped into pieces no larger than 5–10 cm. The roots are dried in the shade or under the sun with active drying,

laid out in a thin layer, and constantly turned over. The dry raw material is stored in bales or bags in dry, well ventilated rooms, separate from other medicinal plant raw materials. Thus, based on accumulated experience, for harvesting raw materials, we recommend utilizing no more than 15–20% of the plants in a given area annually, ensuring the proper self-renewal of *Dorema* thickets and their stability in the plant community.

Ferula undulata (*Ferula undulata* M. Pimen. et J. Baranova) — this species was described in 1976 in the Central Kopetdag. It is a perennial monocarpic plant, 80–100 cm tall. The stem is reddish-brown, thick, branching from the middle into an oval panicle. The leaves wither quickly, are smooth on top, and more or less downy on the bottom; basal leaves have short petioles. Mature plants have 2–4 (5) leaves, 40–50 cm long and 50–60 cm wide. Stem leaves are much smaller. It blooms in May and bears fruit in June–July [7, 8]. *Ferula undulata* grows on fine-grained gravelly, often almost bare scree slopes in the mid-mountain region (shiblyak belt) up to the lower belt of juniper groves, among sparse xerophytic shrubs and highland xerophytes in sagebrush-grass communities.

In the Central Kopetdag, it has been recorded in: Germab, Kheyrabad, Sulyukli, Degirmenli (Prokhladnoye), Chaek, Gökdere, Archabil, Yablonovsky, Kurtusuv, Gaudan, Kurykhovdan, Sherlock, Babazav, Dashtoy, Chopandag. It is endemic to Turkmenistan [1, 3, 8]. The chemical composition is not studied. In folk medicine, the roots of *Ferula undulata* have long been used to treat various colds [2]. Economically significant thickets have been described by us in the area adjacent to the road from Gokdere to Chaek. *Ferula undulata* grows here in rather sparse groups in the sagebrush-grass shiblyak communities, covering an area of 150–160 hectares. On a transect of 100 m², an average of 11 *Ferula undulata* plants were counted. The productivity of its above-ground and underground mass was determined based on 112 randomly selected plants, excluding annual specimens. As a result, the average weight of one plant was 173.1 g of fresh above-ground and 192.2 g of underground phytomass. The largest roots reached a weight of 500 g. The yield of air-dried raw material for *Ferula undulata* was 31% for the roots and 28% for the above-ground mass. The exploitable reserve of raw material in the Gökdere-Chaek area is about 8 tons of above-ground and 10 tons of underground phytomass [2]. To ensure proper conditions for the development of the *Ferula undulata* population within its range, we suggest harvesting no more than 1/8 of its thickets annually, selecting the largest plants for root harvesting. Generative individuals should not be dug up, leaving them for seeding. The above ground mass (leaves) is harvested before it dries, without damaging the plant's root collar. Drying and storage of raw materials are similar to those described earlier.

Ferula gummosa (*Ferula gummosa* Boiss.) is a perennial herbaceous plant from the celery family, growing to a height of 150–120 cm. The stem is pale green,

cylindrical, branching at the top into a sparse panicle. Most of the branches are alternate, relatively thin. The leaves are gray-downy, soft, and wither quickly; basal leaves are multiply pinnately dissected into numerous small segments. The umbels vary: central ones are sessile, lateral ones are opposite. Each umbellet has 10–20 flowers. The petals are pale yellow. It blooms and bears fruit in May–June [7, 8]. The plant grows on fine-grained and gravelly slopes, in rocky mountain steppes, on subalpine meadows, and among juniper, rosehip, and tragacanth thickets, up to an altitude of 2300 m above sea level.

In the Central Kopetdag, it is found in: Robergovsky, Neftyanovsky, Dushakerekdag, Sulyukli, Asylma, Bolshoy Karanok, Misinev, Arvaz, Karayalchi, Kurtusuv, Gaudan [6, 8]. The above-ground mass of *Ferula gummosa* contains 1.64–2.1% essential oil, coumarins, and flavonoids (1.54–1.57%). The roots contain 0.58% essential oil, terpenoids, polyacetylene compounds, coumarins, and macrocyclic lactones. The fruits contain 0.48% coumarins, 46.9% fatty oil, resin, and 10–22% essential oil. In folk medicine, the resin is used as a pain reliever, expectorant, anti-spasmodic, and for treating bronchial asthma, chronic bronchitis, hysteria, paralysis, gastritis, skin diseases, and rheumatism. It has a mild hypotensive effect. *Ferula gummosa* in the Central Kopetdag usually forms sparse thickets or is limited by livestock grazing. The most accessible area for harvesting raw materials is in the Arvaz forestry area of the Bakharden forestry. Here, thickets are recorded in the localities of Gokgyadik, Gosharcha, Berkav, Akgaya, Yailak, Niyazym, and others. The total area covered by *Ferula* in this region reaches 240 hectares. The raw material reserves in the surveyed areas amounted to 20.8 tons of above-ground and 70.5 tons of underground phytomass. Harvesting and Storage Instructions. The aerial part (herb) and roots of *Ferula gummosa* are used as raw material. Over a period of 6–7 years, the plant forms only a basal rosette of leaves, after which it produces a flowering stalk and, following seed production, dies. Mature plants have 17–19 (up to 29) basal leaves. The herb is harvested manually in late May from half of the thickets, ensuring the root collar remains undamaged. The collected raw material is dried in small stacks in the shade for 5–6 days. The dried leaves are then packed in linen bags and stored separately from other medicinal raw materials.

The roots of *Ferula gummosa* are harvested manually, selecting the largest vegetative specimens and using no more than 1/10 of the individuals. The dug-up roots are cleaned of soil and immediately cut into pieces no thicker than 2–3 cm. The chopped raw material is dried using active drying methods either in the open sun or in the shade. The pieces are turned over two to three times during the day. The roots shrink by about three times during the drying process. For long-term storage, the dry raw material is packed in cellophane bags and stored separately from other materials, as it has a strong specific smell. The storage life of the raw material is 2 years.

Ferula ovina (Boiss.) Boiss.— *Ferula ovina* is a perennial herbaceous plant of the celery family, growing 40–60 (up to 80) cm tall. Its sturdy stem is slightly thickened at the nodes, rough from short stiff hairs, and usually one or two stems per plant. The leaves are long-lasting, stiff when dry, with basal leaves on petioles that have a triangular outline and are tripartite. The stem leaves have smaller blades, while the upper leaves are without blades, represented by sheaths, which are swollen and bent away from the stem. The umbels have 7–10 flowers, and the petals are yellow. It blooms and bears fruit in May–June [8]. *Ferula ovina* inhabits gravelly slopes, scree, rocks, shrub thickets, and mountain steppes, reaching altitudes of up to 3000 m.

In the Central Kopetdag, it is most commonly found in Robergovsky, Neftyanovsky, Gokdere, Chaek, Sulyukli, Degirmenli (Prokhladnoye), Desht, Nokhur, Sarymsakli, Asylma, Babazav, Bolshoy Karanok, Archabil, Chopandag, Misinev, Yablonovsky, Kurtusuv, Gaudan, and Karayalchi [6, 8]. The roots of *Ferula ovina* contain 0.29% essential oil, terpenoids, coumarins, and macrocyclic lactones. The aerial mass contains 0.06–0.8% essential oil. The seeds contain 15 components of essential oil, 0.1% coumarins, and 19.1% fatty oil. *Ferula ovina* has not been well studied as a medicinal plant. In folk medicine, decoctions of its stems and resin are used to treat scurvy and tuberculosis. Its milky sap is used to heal mouth diseases such as ulcers, wounds, stomatitis, and burns on the mucous membrane [5]. In the Central Kopetdag, *Ferula ovina* is widespread. The most promising areas for raw material harvesting are located between the points Heyrabat-Germab-Karayalchi Gorge. Here, it grows in sagebrush-grass communities, covering more than 200 hectares with extensive groups. To study the productivity of the plants, we measured the biometrics and determined the aerial and underground mass of 152 specimens of *Ferula ovina*. As a result, the average root weight was 171 g, with a maximum of 300 g of fresh mass. The aerial generative shoots of *Ferula ovina* exceed the roots in weight, while the vegetative ones are significantly smaller. Overall, with a high degree of certainty, it can be assumed that the ratio of above ground to underground mass in the plant is 1:1.

The moisture content in the roots is 68%, while in the above-ground shoots, it is 72%. Based on this data, the raw material reserve of *Ferula ovina* thickets in the Germab massif amounts to 35.6 tons of above-ground and 40.2 tons of underground mass in air-dried form. Given that the restoration of *Ferula ovina* thickets after root excavation takes 8–10 years, we recommend a sustainable harvesting regime, where no more than 1/10 of the plants are dug up, selecting only the largest (oldest) specimens for this purpose. Harvesting of the above-ground mass can begin in early May, using no more than 50% of the plants. Drying and storage of the raw material should follow the procedures described earlier. Thus, all species of *Ferula* and *Dorema* have medicinal value.

They are promising for the production of plant-based medicinal products. The biological resources and phytochemical characteristics of some ephemeral plants of Kopetdag reveal their potential for use in the pharmaceutical industry of Turkmenistan.

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PROPAGATION OF TURKMEN BARBERRY (BERBERIS TURCOMANICA) UNDER IN VITRO CONDITIONS

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Abstract. *Within the framework of scientific research on the cultivation of endemic and ancient (relict) species of medicinal flora of Turkmenistan and the identification of their significance for pharmaceutical purposes, the use of the method of microclonal propagation in biotechnology for growing medicinal plants is of great importance.*

Keywords: *berberis, in vitro, microclonal propagation, macrocomponent, Central Kopetdag.*

The method of microclonal propagation addresses the issues of conservation and reproduction of plant species that are difficult to propagate and are threatened with extinction, enrichment of their biodiversity, as well as the shortage of raw plant material. It makes it possible to obtain phytomass free from herbicides, pesticides, and heavy metals, and to produce biologically active substances from callus mass that are difficult and costly to synthesize and are widely used in pharmaceuticals, agriculture, and other industries, thereby reducing the cost of their production [2–4; 5; 7; 8].

In our country, in the production of hypoallergenic phytopharmaceuticals from medicinal plants, it is considered advisable to cultivate plants under in vitro conditions in order to comply with international standards.

Despite the fact that endemic species are used in folk medicine for the treatment of many diseases, their significance for pharmaceutical purposes has not yet been fully studied on a scientific basis [1]. Therefore, the propagation of endemic species under in vitro conditions and their use for pharmaceutical purposes is one of the important issues.

The research work was carried out from February to April 2025 in the biotechnology laboratory of the Institute of General and Applied Biology of the Oguzkhan Engineering and Technology University of Turkmenistan.

In the course of the research, a field expedition was organized to the Aydere Gorge (South-Western Kopetdag) in October 2024 and to Hyz-Dere (Central Kopetdag) in November 2024, where Turkmen barberry (*Berberis turcomanica* Kar.) grows naturally. The natural habitats of this species were studied, and data on the area it occupies and its productivity were collected (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Turkmen barberry. Hyz-Dere, Central Kopetdag.
(Photo by A. Akmuradov, 2024).

Objective of the study. Propagation of the medicinal plant Turkmen barberry under in vitro conditions, production of callus tissue, and determination of the conditions required for this process.

Plant material. Seeds were used to obtain shoots, with barberry cultivated under sterilized conditions.

Materials and methods. For in vitro plant propagation using the plant tissue culture method, various instruments and materials were employed, including a distiller, autoclave, biological safety cabinet, pH meter, electric heating oven, analytical balance, magnetic stirrer, climate chamber, alcohol burner, salts, phytohormones, vitamins, ethyl alcohol, 1N NaOH or KOH solution, beakers, flasks, graduated cylinders with volumes from 10 ml to 1.0 liter, test tubes, graduated pipettes (1–10 ml), electronic balances, tweezers, scissors, spatulas, thin aluminum foil, and parchment paper.

Sequence of operations for in vitro propagation of Turkmen barberry.

Preparation of containers and instruments. Containers were washed with hot water and detergent and rinsed 8–10 times with running water, followed by five rinses with distilled water containing a few drops of NaOCl. The cleaned containers were dried in a drying oven at 130 °C for 1 hour. Washing was carried out in a clean, dust-free washing room. Subsequently, the dried glassware and instruments were sterilized in an autoclave for 25–30 minutes at a pressure of 1 atm.

Preparation of the nutrient medium. In the experiments, a nutrient medium prepared according to the Murasige–Skoog (MS) method was used [10]. The composition of this medium includes macro- and micronutrients, vitamins, a specially

prepared iron solution (Fe chelate, Fe-EDTA), agar-agar (8 g/l), and sucrose (30 g/l).

To prepare 1 liter of the nutrient medium, the required volume of each stock solution was added with a pipette into a 1-liter container. The resulting liquid medium was transferred into a graduated cylinder and the volume was adjusted to 950 ml with distilled water. The pH of the medium was adjusted to the required level, within the range of 5.7–5.8. Agar in the flask was heated in an oven with constant stirring until complete dissolution and gelation of the medium. The prepared medium was poured into test tubes to one-quarter of their volume, and the tubes were placed on metal racks. For sterilization, they were autoclaved at 121 °C for 15 minutes at a pressure of 0.7–1.0 atm. After sterilization, the test tubes containing the nutrient medium were stored in a refrigerator at 4 °C.

Aseptic technique. Disinfection of the plant material was carried out in a laminar airflow cabinet. Before starting work, the surface of the workbench was disinfected with a 96% ethyl alcohol solution. The necessary instruments and containers with nutrient medium were then placed on the bench and sterilized under ultraviolet light for 15–20 minutes using a mercury–quartz lamp. Prior to work, hands were disinfected with a 70% ethyl alcohol solution.

Sterilization. One of the main conditions for successful *in vitro* cultivation of plant cells and tissues is sterility, since under artificial conditions not only the cultivated plants but also various bacteria and fungi can proliferate. These microorganisms consume nutrients from the medium that are essential for plant growth and inhibit development. Therefore, selecting the most appropriate conditions for each species is a complex but important task.

Sodium hypochlorite, hydrogen peroxide, and ethanol solution were selected as disinfectants. Their effectiveness was determined during the course of the study.

Seed disinfection methods. Seed disinfection prior to sowing was carried out using the following methods:

In the first method, prepared seeds were washed under running water for 5 minutes, sterilized in 70% ethyl alcohol for 3 minutes, in 3% hydrogen peroxide for 5 minutes, and in 15% sodium hypochlorite for 10 minutes, followed by three rinses with distilled water.

In the second method, seeds were sterilized in 6% hydrogen peroxide for 3 minutes, in 70% ethanol for 1–2 minutes, and in 10% sodium hypochlorite for 15 minutes, then rinsed with distilled water.

In the third method, seeds were treated with 0.5% sodium hypochlorite for 20 minutes and rinsed three times with distilled water. The sterilized seeds were placed on Murasige — Skoog nutrient medium prepared with different macrocomponent concentrations (Table).

Table
Composition of the Murasige — Skoog nutrient medium (mg/l)

Components	Amount (mg/l)	Components	Amount (mg/l)
NH ₄ NO ₃	1650	CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.025
KNO ₃	1900	CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.025
KH ₂ PO ₄	170	Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.25
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	370	KI	0.83
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	440	Thiamine-HCl	1.0
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	27.8	Pyridoxine-HCl	0.5
Na ₂ EDTA·2H ₂ O	37.3	Nicotinic acid	0.5
H ₃ BO ₃	6.2	Ascorbic acid	1.0
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	8.67	Sucrose	20,000

The Murasige — Skoog nutrient medium, most commonly used for the cultivation of isolated plant tissues under *in vitro* conditions, contains a well-balanced composition of nutrients and differs from other media in the ratio of ammonium and nitrate ions. It also supports organogenesis and somatic embryogenesis. To prevent damage to shoots caused by toxic compounds (phenols, terpenes, and other secondary metabolites) released by primary explants, an antioxidant was added to the nutrient medium at a concentration of 1 mg/l. Ascorbic acid was used as the antioxidant.

The first seedlings of the sown barberry seeds emerged 10–12 days after sowing. After 10 days, the germination rate reached 70%. The seeds showed good germination, and no contamination was detected. During the experiment, the timing of germination, growth activity, and the onset of root system formation were recorded (Figs. 2 and 3).

Fig. 2. Seedling of Turkmen barberry obtained from seed

Fig. 3. Turkmen barberry seedlings obtained under *in vitro* conditions

Ty-two days after sowing, the callus induction method was applied to Turkmen barberry. Small explants measuring 1.5–2.0 mm were excised from young shoots, specifically from the region closest to the central vein, and placed into Petri dishes containing Murasige — Skoog (MS) nutrient medium supplemented with phytohormones for callus tissue induction.

Phytohormones are regulators of plant growth and development. Under the influence of phytohormones, cells lose their specialization (dedifferentiate) and begin to divide [3; 6; 9]. Using phytohormones, it is possible to induce callus formation in plant tissues that do not normally respond to injury.

Callus tissue formation occurred within 4–5 weeks, depending on the activation of growth. During this period, test tubes containing the explants were monitored every 5 days, with close attention paid to their growth characteristics. Thus, callus formation on stem explants of barberry was observed over 26–30 days on MS medium supplemented with IAA (1 mg/l), gibberellin (1 mg/l), and Kalanchoe juice (200 mg/l) (Figs. 4 and 5).

Fig. 4. Stem and leaf explants obtained from Turkmen barberry

Fig. 5. Callus tissue obtained from Turkmen barberry

The obtained callus tissue was then divided into fragments measuring 2–3 mm, transferred into test tubes containing fresh nutrient medium, and subcultured.

The experimental results demonstrated that callus tissue can be obtained from barberry stem explants using phytohormones at different concentrations.

Thus, *in vitro* cultivation of cells and tissues of medicinal plants makes it possible to obtain environmentally clean raw material throughout the year. This method is convenient for producing the required plant material and ensuring good plant growth regardless of environmental influences. With the correct selection of conditions for cell propagation, as well as an optimal combination of phytohormones, it allows the production of large amounts of tissue biomass synthesizing biologically active substances.

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SELECTION AND PROPAGATION OF PAEONIA SUFFRUTICOSA ANDREWS IN RUSSIA

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Abstract. *Breeding work aimed at developing domestic cultivars of tree peony is currently ongoing at the MSU Botanical Garden. In the breeding process, seed material from the cultivars “P. suffruticosa,” yellow peony (P. lutea), and Delavay’s peony (P. delavayi). Morphogenetic analysis revealed that most hybrids possess traits characteristic of semi-shrub species: numerous flowers, presence of underground shoots facilitating rapid vegetative propagation; however, unlike wild species, seeds of interspecific cultivars are sterile. To date, we have registered 50 domestic cultivars of tree peonies, which have been included in the cultivar catalogue and recommended for cultivation. A methodology for conducting evaluation tests of tree peony has been developed. Research on microclonal propagation of cultivars is progressing successfully.*

Keywords: *morphogenesis in vivo and in vitro; microclonal propagation; ontogenesis and selection of Paeonia suffruticosa Andrews; formation of introduction populations*

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Introduction

To expand the range of ornamental plants in the central zone of Russia, the introduction of newly cultivated plants, which are not yet of industrial importance but are currently being tested in collections of scientific institutions, is highly important. In nature, tree peonies grow in mountains up to 4000 m above sea level

within the temperate subtropical climatic zone of Southwest China. F. C. Stern (Stern, 1946), in his monograph, divided the section *Moutan* DC. into two subsections: *Vaginatae* and *Delavayanae*. The subsection *Vaginatae* includes a group of shrub species (taxon "*P. suffruticosa* Andrews") characterized by complete lignification of shoots and differentiation of the apex into a single terminal flower on the shoot, where, at the bud stage, the staminodial disc completely covers the pistils. The subsection *Delavayana* comprises a group of semi-shrub species: *P. lutea* Franch., *P. delavayi* Franch., *P. potaninii* Komarov. They are characterized by partial lignification of shoots, the presence of xylo-podias (underground shoots), and the formation of 3–4 flowers in the axils of the upper leaves of the shoot, with the staminodial disc at the bud stage forming fleshy lobes at the base of the pistils.

The history of introduction and collection of tree peonies in the Botanical Gardens of Russia dates back to 1824 and is divided into three stages, each with clearly defined specific tasks, content, and outcomes. In the Imperial Botanical Garden, tree peonies were included in the collection of subtropical herbaceous plants and were maintained outdoors only during the summer season.

During the years of the Great Patriotic War, a group of these plants was left outdoors under snow cover for the first time, where they successfully overwintered. The establishment of a new collection at the Botanical Garden of Moscow State University named after M. V. Lomonosov required the selection of the most promising and resilient forms, the development of cultivation techniques, and the issuance of recommendations for practical application (Uspenskaya, 2001).

Statement of the Problem

To date, tree peonies have not yet achieved widespread use in Russian landscaping; for many gardeners, they remain an expensive exotic plant. There are two main reasons for this. The first is the difficulty of propagating tree peonies. The second is the near absence of domestic planting material. Currently, the Russian market is flooded with Polish and Chinese seedlings which, unfortunately, lack sufficient winter hardiness and frost resistance.

Therefore, at present, the Moscow State University Botanical Garden continues breeding efforts to develop domestic cultivars of this species. For breeding purposes, we used seeds of cultivars of *P. suffruticosa*, yellow peony (*P. lutea*), and Delavay's peony (*P. delavayi*), collected from plants growing in the garden's branch on Prospekt Mira (Moscow, Apothecary Garden).

Results

The work was carried out in several directions: 1) obtaining the maximum number of seeds of *P. suffruticosa* cultivars through open and cross-pollination; 2) selecting the resulting seedlings for winter hardiness, frost resistance, drought

tolerance, ornamental qualities, and others; 3) subsequently assigning cultivar status to the most ornamental forms; 4) interspecific hybridization: using *P. lutea* Franch. and *P. delavayi* as maternal forms, pollinated with a mixture of pollen from tree peony cultivars; 5) identifying dominant traits in the obtained hybrids.

At present, we have registered 50 cultivars of tree peonies, which are listed in the catalog and recommended for use in production. Some new cultivars of Russian breeding are presented in Figures 1–14 and 15.

Figure 1 ‘Cinderella’

Figure 2 ‘Brigantina’

Figure 3 ‘Albert Vlasov’

Figure 4 ‘Rimma Barykina’

Figure 5 ‘Acad. Atabekov’

Figure 6 ‘M.V. Lomonosov’

Figure 7 'Yulia Drunina'

Figure 8 'Olga Turdzhanova'

Figure 9 'Vorobyevsky'

Figure 10 'Peter the Great'

Figure 11 'Lyubov'

Figure 12 'Tatyana'

Figure 13 'Stefan'

Figure 14 'Smolin'

A methodology for conducting DUS testing on tree peony was developed for work with this crop (Procedural documents, 2006).

Meanwhile, the introduction process is inseparably linked to seed propagation. Varieties and promising seedlings obtained through intervarietal crossings produce a large number of viable seeds. As a result, the required seed stock has been established. Peony seeds are characterized by prolonged germination, as they possess an underdeveloped embryo that differentiates during maturation. A method for accelerated seed germination has been developed, along with the timing and conditions for their long-term storage. The tree peony is a slow-growing and labor-intensive plant to propagate, which complicates the rapid introduction of new cultivars into cultivation. For more than 30 years, techniques of agronomy, as well as seed and vegetative propagation, have been developed — mainly by grafting cuttings onto roots of herbaceous peonies (Uspenskaya, 2007).

Most of the hybrids obtained retained traits of semi-shrub species: prolific flowering shoots and the presence of underground shoots, which facilitated their rapid vegetative propagation; however, unlike wild species, the seeds of interspecific cultivars proved to be sterile (Uspenskaya, 2009).

Currently, microclonal propagation protocols for tree peony cultivars of European and Chinese origin have been developed. However, for each new cultivar of this species, it is necessary to determine and select the optimal propagation conditions under sterile conditions. At the Laboratory of Plant Developmental Biology of the Faculty of Biology at MSU, the most widespread microclonal propagation method for this species has been the activation of axillary meristem activity. For this species, apical and lateral buds from lignified 4–5-year-old shoots proved to be the optimal explant (Krinitsyna et al., 2008). The study demonstrated that the optimal material for the micropropagation of tree peonies in *in vitro* culture is large (25 mm or longer) and medium-sized (10–20 mm long) apical and lateral

buds. Furthermore, for cultivars derived from *P. suffruticosa* ('Nikolai Vavilov' and 'Vladimir Novikov') exhibiting acrosympodial shoot growth, the highest regeneration rates were observed in apical buds or those closest to them. For the cultivars 'Kuindzhi' and 'Coral', in the breeding of which *P. lutea* with a mesosympodial type of shoot growth was used, the best explants were buds of the specified sizes taken from the middle part of the shoot.

In addition to the physiological age of the initial explant, which undoubtedly plays a significant role in the expression of morphogenetic capacity, the timing (season) of its isolation from the mother plant is an equally important factor. According to our observations under the conditions of the central region of Russia, it is optimal to detach the buds of the cultivars we propagate from the mother plant at the very beginning of the vegetation period — in late March to early April. Tissues and organs isolated during the vegetative phase exhibit a higher sensitivity to the nutrient medium composition and an enhanced ability to form adventitious buds, develop shoots, and root than those isolated during deep and forced dormancy.

For normal regeneration of the cultivars 'Vladimir Novikov' and 'Kuindzhi', the presence of IAA (0.2 mg/l) and BAP (1 mg/l) in the medium was necessary and sufficient, whereas cultivars 'Nikolai Vavilov' and 'Korall' require a medium supplemented with IBA (0.2 mg/l) and BAP (1 mg/l). For the propagation of Chinese tree peony cultivars, IMC [10] and β -naphthylacetic acid (NAA) are also used.

The induction and subsequent development of roots, as well as their number in the regenerant, depend on specific concentrations of auxins in the medium. For the induction of root formation and subsequent rooting of regenerants of Chinese breeding cultivars, IMC is used at a concentration of 15 mg/L. Reducing the concentration of IMC to 2 mg/L during the propagation of domestic breeding cultivars resulted in the same yield of rooted plants (about 60%). Using a lower auxin concentration during root induction does not produce the desired effect. Doubling the concentration of IMC does not lead to an increase in the yield of rooted plants for any of the cultivars studied (Krinitzyna et al., 2011).

Conclusions

Based on the conducted research, the obtained cultivars of domestic breeding can be recommended for introduction into cultivation for the purpose of landscaping settlements, as well as for use as medicinal raw materials. In traditional medicine of China, Korea, and Japan, the roots of tree peonies, which are included in all Tibetan medicine formulations, are widely used. To investigate the medicinal significance of tree peonies, researchers from the Laboratory of Blood Protective Properties at the Faculty of Biology, Lomonosov Moscow State University, conducted physiological and biochemical studies of the root system of tree peonies and discovered that extracts from them slow blood clotting and even dissolve

thrombi; that is, heparin was found in the roots, which promotes blood thinning. It has been established that preparations obtained from these plants also help to reduce blood sugar levels (Ulyanov et al., 1997; Lyapina et al., 1998). However, to obtain a sufficient amount of raw material, it is necessary to establish industrial plantations of this crop in Russia.

Successful evaluation of numerous peony cultivars from the MSU Botanical Garden collection has already been conducted in many regions of Russia. In particular, the study of their adaptive response characteristics under the monsoon climate conditions of Southern Primorye has been conducted for many years by researchers from the Far Eastern Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences: A. S. Proshina, N. V. Makedonskaya, and L. N. Mironova (Mironova L. N., Dudkin R. V., 2007).

Figure 15. Curator of the tree peony collection at the Botanical Garden of the Biology Faculty of Moscow State University, Marianna Sergeevna Uspenskaya, and the cultivar ‘Irina’ developed by her

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TOPICAL METHODS OF ROOT CANAL PREPARATION IN VETERINARY ENDODONTICS

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Abstract. *The aim of this study was to analyze and systematize clinical approaches in order to formulate standardized practical recommendations. A detailed comparison of the principal canal preparation methods was performed, including the classical Step-back technique, as well as the modern coronal-apical techniques Step-down and Double-flare; more than 65 scientific sources by Russian and international researchers published between 2015 and 2025 were examined. The comparative evaluation was conducted based on five key criteria — preservation of natural anatomy in curved canals, irrigation efficiency, processing speed, ease of mastering, and versatility of application in various clinical situations. Particular attention was given to the instrumental component. A comparative analysis of the operational characteristics of stainless steel and nickel-titanium instruments was performed. Parameters such as flexibility, cutting efficiency, control during operation in curved canals, risk of cyclic fatigue, and cost-effectiveness were examined. The evolution of file geometry has been traced, from classical manual K- and H-files to modern rotary Ni-Ti systems with complex cross-sectional designs. Based on comparative data, the superiority of rotary Ni-Ti instruments for managing the complex anatomy typical of animals has been concluded. Protocols for pharmacological canal treatment have been systematized, with a central emphasis on combining irrigation with sodium hypochlorite and EDTA. Typical clinical errors during the mechanical preparation phase are described, including loss of working length, ledge formation, canal transportation, and perforation, along with measures for their prevention. The outcome of this work was the development of a set of six practical recommendations aimed at implementing a safe and predictable approach in routine clinical practice and formulating the primary conclusion — modern veterinary endodontics should be*

based on the integrated use of corono-apical preparation techniques, specialized nickel-titanium instruments, and strict irrigation protocols, which together minimize risks and enhance treatment success.

Keywords: *veterinary endodontics, root canal preparation, nickel-titanium endodontic instruments, ProTaper system, Step-back technique, Step-down technique, Double-flare technique, dental diseases in animals.*

Introduction

Oral diseases in companion animals, especially cats and dogs, consistently dominate veterinary consultation statistics [1]. This high frequency of clinical cases confirms that veterinary dentistry has long ceased to be a niche specialty and has become a critically important discipline. The increasing demand from animal owners naturally motivates veterinarians to improve their qualifications and standardize treatment protocols; however, the field still encounters significant systemic barriers. Development is primarily hindered by the lack of specialized university programs and the ambiguity of the regulatory framework, including inadequate technical equipment of veterinary treatment facilities [2].

Endodontics plays a crucial role in addressing these issues, enabling the preservation of each tooth, which is of fundamental importance for small animals. The success of therapy entirely depends on the quality of mechanical and medicinal treatment, since the primary objective of the veterinary practitioner remains the complete eradication of infection within the dental root canal system for subsequent hermetic obturation [3]. Contemporary diagnostic methods, including cone-beam computed tomography, facilitate detailed investigation of complex anatomy and pathological features, transforming treatment from an intuitive pursuit into a precise and predictable procedure [4].

This review outlines current mechanical preparation strategies, Step-down and Double-flare, emphasizing their advantages and potential limitations in clinical practice [5, 6, 7, 8]. Considerable attention is devoted to the systematic analysis of instruments, comparing the properties of nickel-titanium alloys with traditional steel and evaluating standards for their safe use [9, 10, 11, 12, 13]. Furthermore, the review addresses key ancillary stages, including irrigation protocols and the analysis of common clinical errors [14, 15, 16]. Consequently, a set of recommendations has been developed to support a comprehensive and deliberate approach in the routine practice of the veterinary dental clinician.

Current methods of root canal preparation

The foundational principle of successful endodontic treatment is the cleaning and shaping of the root canal, referred to as Cleaning and Shaping [17]. Modern veterinary practice aims to accomplish these tasks as comprehensively and safely

as possible, while considering the complex anatomy of animal teeth. Obsolete approaches involving movement from the root apex toward the crown have been replaced by more physiological coronal-apical techniques, with the Step-down and Double-flare methods occupying a prominent position among them [8, 18].

The rationale of the Step-down method, often termed the ‘from the crown down’ technique, prescribes beginning preparation with the coronal and middle thirds of the canal, followed by instrumentation of the apical portion. This algorithm takes effect immediately after the formation of adequate endodontic access. The first step involves determining the preliminary canal patency using a thin instrument, for example, a size fifteen file. Subsequently, the coronal third is enlarged up to the beginning of the curvature, for which Gates-Glidden drills or specialized nickel-titanium shaping instruments, such as SX files of the ProTaper system, are ideal. This preparation provides direct access to the apical zone, eliminates narrowing at the orifice, and significantly facilitates subsequent canal irrigation with antiseptics [8, 18, 19].

Only after this preliminary preparation does the clinician determine the working length using an apex locator and radiographic control [4]. The procedure is completed by stepwise instrumentation of the apical third with manual or rotary files, during which the specialist progresses from smaller diameter instruments to larger ones. It is critically important to continuously perform recapitulation — the repeated passage of the canal with an instrument of the previous size, which prevents lumen blockage by dentinal debris [5, 15].

The widespread recognition of the Step-down technique is attributed to several undeniable advantages, the primary one being the reduction of the risk of apex infection. Early removal of infected masses from the coronal portion prevents pathogens from penetrating into the tissues surrounding the root apex [20]. Furthermore, the space created at the initial stage serves as a reservoir, allowing the irrigation needle to penetrate deeper, thereby significantly enhancing the effectiveness of antiseptic treatment [14]. From a technical perspective, the clinician achieves superior tactile control, as after the orifice is opened, it becomes considerably easier to perceive the direction and curvature of the canal when working at depth [21]. This approach minimizes the risk of iatrogenic errors, including the creation of false passages, ledges, or perforations in the apical third [15]. It is also noteworthy that, compared to ascending preparation techniques, patients treated with the Step-down method experience significantly fewer postoperative pains [22].

A logical development and refinement of the described approaches is the Double-flare technique, or the double enlargement method. It is a type of hybrid that combines the advantages of both descending and ascending preparation, rendering it indispensable when dealing with complex anatomy, especially when the clinician encounters curved or narrow canals [8]. Technically, the process is organized into three consecutive stages, each addressing a specific task.

The procedure begins with the coronal phase, known as reverse enlargement, which fully replicates the principles of the Step-down technique. The specialist employs large-diameter instruments, such as size forty-five, and progressively transitions to thinner files, each time advancing deeper into the canal. Thus, having established direct access, he proceeds to the apical phase, shaping the apical portion up to the pre-determined size of the master file, for example, #30 or #35, to create a reliable apical stop. The final step involves creating taper, employing the Step-back technique. In this technique, each subsequent instrument with a larger diameter is inserted one millimeter shorter than the previous one, resulting in a smoothly funnel-shaped canal that gradually widens from the apex to the crown [8, 18].

This multi-stage strategy enables the achievement of an optimal cavity architecture, creating ideal conditions for subsequent three-dimensional obturation not only with gutta-percha but also with modern bioceramic sealers based on calcium silicate [23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28]. Stepwise mechanics allow the clinician to precisely follow the natural curvature of the canal, minimizing the risk of straightening or transportation [29]. Furthermore, the combination of different vectors of instrument movement ensures effective evacuation of dentin debris and infected tissues, preventing their blockage of the apical area [20]. It is noteworthy that the method is universal and easily adaptable for both manual operation and the use of modern mechanical systems [6, 7].

Comparative studies convincingly demonstrate that modern corono-apical strategies significantly outperform outdated linear methods, allowing preservation of the natural tooth anatomy and minimizing intraoperative risks [1, 3, 29].

The Step-down and Double-flare methods, based on the corono-apical principle, allow controlled removal of infected tissues from the orifice to the apex, minimizing extrusion of debris beyond the root [20, 30] and creating space for effective irrigation [14]. In contrast, the classical Step-back method, proceeding ‘bottom-up’, inevitably leads to the accumulation of dentin debris and microorganisms in the apical third, which predictably increases the likelihood of canal blockage, ledge formation, and other iatrogenic complications [3, 15]. Simultaneously, the choice of a specific clinical algorithm cannot be standardized, as the clinician must rely not only on the initial diameter of the canals but also consider their degree of curvature [1, 21], as well as not only anatomical parameters but also a comparative analysis of various other characteristics of the examined methods, which are reflected in Table 1 [3, 5, 6, 8, 14, 15, 20, 22, 29].

Specifically, the Step-down and Double-flare techniques minimize the risk of operator errors and establish an optimal foundation for hermetic obturation, ensuring the longevity of the outcome [3, 8, 15, 21, 23, 26, 29]. Essentially, modern mechanical preparation ceases to be a mere sequence of mechanical manipulations, evolving into a deliberate strategy where every movement of the practitioner is guided by anatomical understanding and a commitment to safety.

Instruments for the implementation of modern methodologies

The history of advances in root canal preparation methods is essentially a chronicle of the continuous evolution of the instruments themselves, with each technological breakthrough unveiling new horizons for the clinician. It is impossible to dissociate the technique employed from the instruments the specialist uses; thus, the gradual shift from labor-intensive manual preparation to mechanized technologies marked a genuine revolution [13, 31]. The replacement of rigid, inflexible stainless steel with flexible nickel-titanium shape memory alloys has enabled the resolution of clinical challenges previously deemed unfeasible [9, 32, 33]. In veterinary endodontics, where we continuously contend with complex anatomy, these advancements have been pivotal, allowing the quality of cleaning, procedural safety, and treatment predictability to attain a fundamentally new, previously unreachable level [1, 34, 35].

Even the most advanced theoretical concept of preparation inevitably encounters strict physical limitations of the material in practice. The efficiency of the clinician's work ultimately depends on the operational characteristics of the specific file, particularly its modulus of elasticity and resistance to cyclic fatigue, including its ability to precisely follow the complex canal trajectory [9, 10, 11, 36, 37]. To objectively assess this technological gap, a detailed comparison of the properties of classical steel files, such as K- and H-files, and modern rotary nickel-titanium systems is required [5, 6, 7, 31, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42].

The physico-mechanical properties of materials determine not only the tactics of work but also the limits of safe application of instruments. The rigidity of stainless steel, which provides high cutting efficiency on straight sections, results in elastic deformation with a restoring force in a curved canal. It is precisely this tendency of the instrument to return to its original shape that is the primary cause of canal transportation and ledge formation [15, 29]; meanwhile, the crystalline structure of the steel undergoes accelerated accumulation of fatigue damage under cyclic bending, thus limiting the lifespan even of hand files [43].

Unlike steel, the superelasticity of nickel-titanium is caused by a martensitic phase transformation, which enables the alloy to undergo significant deformation without irreversible changes [6, 9, 29, 33, 44]. However, this very property predisposes the material to adverse phenomena, since when the elastic limit is exceeded, plastic deformation ensues, which is not detectable by visual inspection but critically undermines fatigue strength [36, 37]. Therefore, file deformation should be regarded as a direct indication for its immediate disposal [43, 45]. While traditional manual files, each with its unique cross-sectional shape, dictated a rather narrow range of movements and imposed strict safety limitations, modern rotary Ni-Ti systems, by contrast, thanks to their complex, optimized geometry, have become integral to predictable rotary protocols [13, 46, 47, 48, 49].

Outdated reamers and highly specialized H-files have been replaced by universal and safe Ni-Ti systems, whose geometry is originally designed to enable the Step-down and Double-flare techniques [6, 7, 13, 31, 51]. Thus, knowledge of the evolution of shapes and their associated limitations enables the clinician not only to consciously select an instrument for a specific task but also to gain a deeper understanding of the biomechanical principles underlying successful root canal preparation. This understanding serves as a logical bridge to the next critically important aspect — the standardization and safety protocols for handling instruments.

To navigate the vast diversity of endodontic instruments and communicate effectively with colleagues around the world, clinicians rely on the rigorous framework of standards, particularly ISO 3630–1:2019. These international standards serve as a universal coordinate system, where each parameter has a clear physical rationale. For example, regardless of the total length of the instrument shaft, its active working part always remains constant at 16 millimeters; moreover, the file numbering is not arbitrary but corresponds precisely to metric values, where the number on the handle directly indicates the diameter of the instrument tip in hundredths of a millimeter [53].

An equally important characteristic is the taper, which determines the degree to which the instrument thickens with each millimeter of its length. While the classical standard implies a smooth expansion of 0.02 millimeters, modern engineering has progressed further, offering files with increased or variable taper [53, 54]. This innovation enables much faster shaping of the canal space, creating an optimal funnel-shaped form [26]. Furthermore, to prevent the specialist from wasting precious seconds scrutinizing microscopic markings during the procedure, an intuitive color-coding system was introduced. This system, employing a sequence from white to black through various spectral colors, supplemented with rings of corresponding colors to indicate a transition to another size decade, creates a repeating cycle that enables instantaneous identification of the file size even by peripheral vision.

However, even precise knowledge of the instrument's geometry does not guarantee successful performance, as the safety of the clinician's manipulations directly depends on understanding the physical limits of the metal. In the tooth canal, the clinician encounters two main influencing factors: torsional load and cyclic fatigue. While the first factor, which occurs during tip binding, is effectively managed by modern endomotors with an autoreverse function, cyclic fatigue exhibits a subtle characteristic. It accumulates inconspicuously as the file rotates within a curved canal and can be aggravated by increased surface roughness of the instrument [55], frequently resulting in sudden instrument fracture despite the instrument appearing externally intact [10, 12, 36, 37, 39, 43].

It is precisely this hidden risk that dictates the primary safety standard in modern endodontics, which for rotary systems is formulated as the '1 to 1' principle,

meaning the use of a single set of files for only one canal [43, 45]. This approach, despite its apparent extravagance, is the only guarantee that the metal fatigue limit will not be exceeded at the most critical moment [37]. Simultaneously, when working with manual instruments, the main evaluation criterion becomes solely visual inspection. Before each insertion into the canal, the file must undergo a thorough inspection; any indication of unwinding of the coils or deformation, including changes in surface gloss, should be treated as a signal for the immediate disposal of the instrument [12, 15].

Auxiliary aspects of preparation. It would be a dangerous misconception to believe that the success of endodontic treatment depends solely on masterful handling of the file. In fact, high-quality instrumental preparation should be considered only the first half of success. The second, no less significant aspect of success lies in the chemistry of the process, namely in proper medicinal treatment and strict adherence to protocols that prevent iatrogenic errors [14, 56, 57, 58].

Even the most thorough mechanical preparation cannot completely eliminate the biofilm and remnants of vital pulp [59], nor completely clean infected dentin from deep microcanals. The file inevitably leaves behind the so-called smear layer, sealing bacteria within [16, 60]. This problem is resolved by irrigation, during which the canal contents are actively flushed out using various antiseptic solutions that function as an indispensable chemical complement to mechanical cleaning [14, 20, 61, 62].

According to some researchers, sodium hypochlorite unquestionably remains the leader among irrigants. Its status as the ‘gold standard’ is fully justified, as it possesses the unique property of dissolving organic matter, whether pulp remnants or collagen, thereby inflicting a powerful impact on the bacterial flora [16, 56, 57, 58, 60]. In veterinary practice, it is generally necessary to balance efficacy and safety, favoring concentrations in the range of 2.5 to 3%. Undoubtedly, a more concentrated solution at 5.25% acts more aggressively, but its application requires utmost caution, as accidental extrusion beyond the root apex may cause severe chemical burns to the surrounding tissues [14, 58].

To combat inorganic contaminants, it is most appropriate to use EDTA — ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid — in solution form at concentrations ranging from 15 to 17%. This substance functions as a chelating agent, gently dissolving the mineral component of the smear layer and reopening the dentinal tubules [14, 16, 61]. EDTA is typically applied after completion of instrumentation, preparing the substrate for the final antiseptic action against the biota.

The contemporary clinical approach relies on the synergy of these solutions. The most effective protocol entails continuous irrigation with sodium hypochlorite throughout the entire canal enlargement phase. Then, to remove mineral debris, the canal is filled with EDTA for one to two minutes, and the procedure is completed with a final application of hypochlorite, which simultaneously neutralizes

the previously introduced acid and ensures deep disinfection [14, 20, 56, 57]. To enhance the cleaning quality, especially in the hard-to-reach apical third, solution activation methods using ultrasound or negative pressure are applied [20].

Special attention must be paid to the anatomy of small animals, such as cats or miniature dog breeds [14]. When working with their thin canals, it is critically important to use special irrigation needles with lateral perforations and stoppers. This design directs the fluid flow toward the canal walls rather than inward, minimizing the risk of the aggressive solution extruding beyond the root. If the clinician encounters active exudate or bleeding, it is advisable to preliminarily treat the canal with 2% chlorhexidine, thereby creating an additional antiseptic barrier prior to introducing sodium hypochlorite [56, 57].

At the same time, it must be noted separately that even the most advanced technical equipment does not protect the practitioner from complications if errors occur during canal preparation and any biomechanical laws are violated. One of the most common problems is the sudden loss of working length, when the instrument ceases to advance along the canal to the apical foramen. Usually, this is caused by the so-called dentin plug, formed from debris that the practitioner inadvertently packed into the apical area by omitting the phase of regular irrigation [14, 20]. In other cases, the pathway is obstructed by an iatrogenic ledge formed as a result of deviation from the main canal course [15]. The only way to avoid such scenarios is through strict adherence to the protocol, which involves constant return to small files for patency control and copious irrigation; simultaneously, it is necessary to cross-check the apex locator readings with radiographs to entirely exclude cases of forced instrument advancement [4, 5, 15].

If the specialist attempts to forcibly penetrate a curved canal using rigid stainless steel files or by skipping sizes, there is a risk of creating a ledge. This local indentation in the wall alters the natural trajectory of the canal and becomes a trap for subsequent instruments. Failure to adequately address the situation may lead to a more serious complication known as the zip effect or transportation, whereby the canal is unnaturally straightened and its wall thins to the point of perforation or false passage formation [4, 5, 15]. Effective preventive measures against such errors include either the use of safe and non-aggressive flexible nickel-titanium files [6, 7, 29] or the preliminary shaping of the instrument's curvature to match the canal's form during manual preparation.

In veterinary practice, these risks are significantly increased due to the specific anatomy of the patients. Special caution should be exercised by specialists with feline teeth exhibiting cervical resorption [63, 64], complex cases of destructive periodontitis combined with root resorption [65], as well as the mandibular incisors of miniature breed dogs, where the root walls are physiologically so thin that any careless movement risks perforation [34, 66]. Therefore, in complex cases, especially when working

with teeth exhibiting cervical resorption (cats) or physiologically thin walls (miniature dog breeds), intraoperative radiographic control or CT becomes an essential instrument for verifying both the working length and the position of the instrument, as well as for excluding perforation [4]. Only strict adherence to established standards and protocols, from creating adequate access to the sequential use of instruments from smaller to larger sizes, ensures safe treatment [1, 35].

Practical Recommendations. Based on the analysis and synthesis of all the information presented above, we have formulated a number of recommendations for implementation in the routine clinical practice of veterinary endodontics:

1. For mechanical preparation of root canals, particularly in small companion animals, preference should be given to corono-apical preparation techniques such as Step-down or Double-flare, especially when working with curved and narrow canals [3, 8, 18, 29].

2. When working in canals with complex anatomy, the choice of instruments should favor machine-operated Ni-Ti systems, which provide better conformity to the natural canal curvature and reduce the risk of transportation compared to rigid stainless steel files [6, 7, 9, 29, 42].

3. It is essential to strictly adhere to the instrument safety protocol by using a separate set of machine-operated Ni-Ti files for each canal and performing a visual inspection of manual instruments before each use, with mandatory disposal at the first signs of deformation [12, 36, 37, 45, 43]. Furthermore, it must be understood that performing revision endodontic treatment requires increased precision and control [67].

4. Effective medicinal treatment is achieved through combined irrigation, which includes continuous rinsing with sodium hypochlorite during the preparation stage and the use of EDTA to remove the smear layer, followed by final activation of the antiseptic solution [14, 15, 16, 20, 56, 57].

5. In cases of complex anatomy, such as when treating teeth with resorption or in miniature dog breeds, intraoperative radiological control is required to prevent iatrogenic errors, allowing verification of the working length and instrument position [4, 34, 63, 64, 66].

6. The creation of adequate endodontic access, providing a straight-line entry to the canal orifices while maximizing the preservation of pericervical dentin, is a critically important initial stage on which the long-term strength of the tooth depends [18, 66].

Conclusions and findings. An analysis of the current state of the field allows us to assert that modern veterinary endodontics has definitively established itself as a rigorous clinical discipline grounded in solid biomechanical laws. A fundamental shift has been the change of paradigm, characterized by the transition from apical-coronal methods to coronal-apical preparation techniques, which, combined with the use of flexible Ni-Ti instruments, has enabled confident control over the complex anatomy of canals in animals, minimizing the risk of intraoperative complications.

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THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN *HELICOBACTER PYLORI* INFECTION AND THYROID FUNCTION IN CHILDREN WITH CHRONIC GASTRODUODENAL PATHOLOGY DURING PUBERTY

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Abstract. *This article explores the relationship between Helicobacter pylori infection and thyroid functional status in children during a critical developmental phase — early puberty (Tanner stages I–III). Objective: to evaluate the changes in thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), triiodothyronine (T3), and thyroxine (T4) levels in children with chronic gastroduodenitis combined with gastroesophageal reflux disease, contingent upon H. pylori infection status. Methodology: a comprehensive evaluation of 77 children aged 8–15 years was conducted using endoscopic, morphological, molecular-genetic (PCR), and serological diagnostic methods; The hormonal profile was assessed by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. Results: it was demonstrated that the presence of H. pylori statistically significantly correlates with a predominance of erosive forms of mucosal lesions (58.6% of cases). In infected patients, a significant decrease in total T3 levels ($p=0.014$) and a relative increase in TSH were observed in seropositive children, indicating the development of euthyroid pathology syndrome. Conclusions: H. pylori infection during puberty functions not only as a local etiological factor but also as a trigger for hormonal imbalance, which impairs the regenerative capacity of the mucous membrane. The necessity of including eradication therapy as a factor for mediated correction of endocrine regulation has been substantiated.*

Keywords: *Helicobacter pylori*, children, pubertal period, stages of sexual development, thyroid gland, thyroid hormones, chronic gastroduodenitis, gastroesophageal reflux disease, erosive lesions.

Introduction. In contemporary pediatrics, there is an observed increase in the proportion of destructive and atrophic alterations of the mucous membrane (MM) of the upper digestive tract (UDT) in children. A distinctive role in the pathogenesis of these conditions is assigned to infection with *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*), which is currently regarded not only as a local etiological factor but also as a trigger for systemic metabolic and neuroendocrine alterations [1, 5].

The period of puberty (Tanner stages I–III) represents a critical phase of ontogenesis, characterized by heightened activity of adaptive mechanisms and instability of endocrine regulation [2, 4, 6]. In recent years, the ‘stomach–thyroid axis’ has been actively studied, as thyroid hormones play a key role in the proliferation and regeneration of the gastrointestinal epithelium [3, 7]. Clarifying the mechanisms underlying the development of chronic inflammation in *H. pylori*-associated gastroduodenitis, considering hormonal status and *Helicobacter pylori* infection, is essential for optimizing therapeutic strategies during puberty.

Objective of the study: to evaluate the dynamics of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), triiodothyronine (T3), and thyroxine (T4) levels in children at stages I–III of pubertal development (PD) with chronic gastroduodenitis (CGD) and gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), depending on the presence of *H. pylori* infection.

Materials and Methods. The main group (MG) comprised 77 patients aged 8–15 years (Tanner stages I–III according to J. M. Tanner) with confirmed chronic esophagogastrroduodenal pathology in the phase of exacerbation. The control group (CG) included 28 practically healthy peers (health groups I–II), matched for sex and pubertal stage.

Diagnostics included:

1. Endoscopic confirmation: EGD (Olympus P-20) with targeted biopsy.
2. Detection of *H. pylori*: comprehensive application of PCR diagnostics on biopsy specimens, rapid urease test, and ELISA for antibody detection in blood serum.
3. Hormonal profile: assessment of TSH, T3, and T4 levels by ELISA in blood serum.

Statistical analysis was conducted using nonparametric methods (Mann-Whitney U test, χ^2) with Statistica 6.1 software; differences were considered significant at $p \leq 0.05$. Data are presented as median (Me) and interquartile range [25%–75%].

Results and Discussion. Infection with *H. pylori* was detected in 37.7% of patients (n=29). It was found that the presence of the pathogen correlates with the severity of mucosal damage: erosive forms of gastroduodenitis (EGD) occurred

significantly more frequently in *H. pylori*-positive children than in those with a superficial process (48.57% versus 28.57%, respectively; $p=0.05$). The combination of EGD and GERD also predominated in the infected group (58.6% versus 37.5% in the uninfected group; $p=0.04$).

Within the group of *H. pylori*-positive patients, subgroups of seropositive (presence of antibodies in the blood — 16.9% of the total sample) and seronegative individuals were identified. In seropositive children, combined erosive lesions were diagnosed in 76.9% of cases, highlighting the role of the severity of the systemic immune response in the progression of mucosal destruction.

Analysis of thyroid status revealed a statistically significant decrease in total T3 levels in *H. pylori*-positive patients compared to negative patients ($p=0.014$, Table 1).

Table 1. Thyroid system parameters according to *H. pylori* infection status

Parameters	<i>H. pylori</i> -negative (N=48) Me [25%-75%]	<i>H. pylori</i> -positive (N=29) Me [25%-75%]	Control (N=28) Me [25%-75%]
TSH (μ IU/mL)	1,65 [1,20–2,25]	1,80 [1,60–2,20]	1,80 [1,30–2,20]
T3 (nmol/L)	2,10 [1,90–2,30]	1,90 [1,80–2,10]*	1,95 [1,70–2,20]
T4 (nmol/L)	113,5 [103–126]	114,0 [103–125]	113,5 [99,5–126]

* $p < 0.05$ compared to *H. pylori*-negative.

Of particular interest are the data showing elevated TSH levels in seropositive patients (1st subgroup) compared to seronegative patients ($p=0.04$) and controls ($p=0.05$). Since TSH can suppress the synthesis of protective mucopolysaccharides, its relative increase in the context of decreased T3 indicates the development of ‘low T3 syndrome’ (euthyroid sick syndrome) [4, 10]. This results in a reduced regenerative capacity of the mucosa and promotes the chronicity of erosive lesions.

Conclusion *H. pylori* infection in adolescents during early puberty is associated with a more severe course of acid-dependent diseases and is correlated with thyroid dysfunction. The observed decrease in T3 and increase in TSH in infected patients act as factors exacerbating trophic disorders of the mucous membrane. Timely eradication therapy is a mandatory component of treatment, as it not only eradicates the infectious agent but also promotes normalization of neuroendocrine regulation, thereby improving the healing efficacy of gastrointestinal mucosal defects.

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FROM FIBROSIS TO NEOPLASIA: MOLECULAR AND CELLULAR MECHANISMS OF MALIGNANT TRANSFORMATION IN MINERS WITH OCCUPATIONAL PNEUMOCONIOSIS

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Abstract: *The study addresses the persistent epidemiological challenge of increased cancer incidence among coal miners in the Kuzbass region. Moving beyond the traditional view of occupational pneumoconiosis (PC) as a condition leading solely to localized pulmonary fibrosis and respiratory failure, this research investigates its role as a systemic process that establishes a pre-tumor microenvironment. The aim was a comprehensive pathomorphological and immunohistochemical analysis to identify features linking chronic dust-induced damage to oncogenic risk. A retrospective analysis included 20 cases of malignant neoplasms in miners with verified PC (2015–2020). Histological, histochemical (Van Gieson, Weigert, Kason stains), and immunohistochemical (IHC) examinations of lung tissue were performed, targeting markers of proliferation (Ki-67), epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT: E-cadherin, N-cadherin, vimentin), activated myofibroblasts (α -SMA, desmin), and endothelium (CD31, CD34). Morphometry was conducted using ImageJ software. Results confirmed extensive diffuse sclerosis and revealed critical additional findings: profound disorganization of basement membranes with “tunnel-like” defects, concentric perivascular/peribronchial fibrosis, and a high density of α -SMA+ myofibroblasts. IHC analysis demonstrated a clear EMT phenotypic shift (loss of E-cadherin, gain of N-cadherin/vimentin) and elevated Ki-67 index in stromal compartments. The discussion posits that PC represents an active, biologically controlled state of chronic tissue remodeling, not a passive scar. The identified EMT and the population of activated myofibroblasts — functionally analogous to cancer-associated fibroblasts (CAFs)—transform the fibrotic stroma into a pro-tumor niche conducive to carcinogenesis. This model provides a pathogenetic basis for the elevated cancer risk. The conclusion advocates for a paradigm shift in occupational health monitoring, recommending*

the integration of fibrogenesis activity and EMT biomarkers as predictive tools for individualized oncological risk assessment in high-risk groups.

Keywords: *occupational pneumoconiosis, pulmonary fibrosis, epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), myofibroblasts, cancer-associated fibroblasts (CAFs), oncogenesis, miners, Kuzbass, immunohistochemistry.*

Occupational lung diseases, particularly pneumoconioses (PC), remain a significant medical and social burden in coal mining regions like Kuzbass. Despite extensive study, a concerning epidemiological discrepancy persists: miners exhibit elevated rates of cancer incidence not fully explained by the classical paradigm of PC as a disease culminating primarily in restrictive respiratory failure due to localized pulmonary scarring [1, 2, 3, 4]. This observation necessitates a reevaluation of the pathogenetic continuum linking chronic inhalational injury to long-term systemic consequences, with malignant transformation being of paramount interest. Contemporary pathophysiology reframes fibrosis not as a static, inert endpoint but as a dynamic, biologically active process of dysregulated tissue repair and remodeling [5, 6]. Within this framework, the phenomenon of epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) emerges as a pivotal mechanism bridging chronic inflammation, fibrogenesis, and carcinogenesis. EMT involves the transdifferentiation of epithelial cells, which lose polarity and cell-cell adhesion, acquiring a mesenchymal phenotype characterized by motility, invasiveness, and heightened resistance to apoptosis [7, 8]. We hypothesize that in occupational PC, sustained dust and inflammatory stress drives EMT, fundamentally altering the nature of the resulting fibrotic tissue. This study proposes that the fibrotic stroma in PC is not merely a scar but an active “pre-tumor” niche. Consequently, the primary objective was to perform a detailed pathomorphological and immunohistochemical investigation of fibrogenesis in PC among Kuzbass miners to identify and characterize molecular and cellular signatures that support the link between dust-induced damage and elevated oncogenic risk.

The research was based on a retrospective analysis of 20 documented cases of malignant neoplasms diagnosed between 2015 and 2020 in coal industry workers with a verified diagnosis of pneumoconiosis. For in-depth morphological evaluation, archival samples of lung tissue obtained via autopsy (n=15) and diagnostic biopsy (n=5) were selected. Tissue had been routinely fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin and embedded in paraffin. The methodological approach encompassed several tiers of analysis. Standard light microscopy with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining provided an overview of histoarchitecture. Special histochemical techniques were employed for connective tissue component evaluation: Van Gieson’s stain for collagen fibers, Weigert’s resorcin-fuchsin stain for elastic fibers, and Kason’s trichrome stain for differential visualization. Immunohistochemical (IHC) analysis was conducted on paraffin sections using a streptavidin-biotin-peroxidase

method following antigen retrieval. A comprehensive antibody panel targeted key biological processes: cellular proliferation (Ki-67), epithelial-mesenchymal transition (E-cadherin, N-cadherin, vimentin), activated myofibroblasts (α -smooth muscle actin (α -SMA), desmin), and vascular endothelium (CD31, CD34). Visualization was achieved with a DAB chromogen system. Finally, morphometric analysis was performed using an Olympus CX31 microscope coupled with digital imaging and ImageJ software. Measured parameters included thickness of bronchial walls and small/medium-caliber vessel walls, alveolar septal width, and quantitative assessments such as the Ki-67 proliferation index (percentage of positive nuclei) and the area density of α -SMA-positive stromal cells.

The investigation revealed a complex pathological landscape extending beyond classic fibrotic descriptions. While expected patterns of diffuse parenchymal sclerosis and hyalinized collagen deposition were confirmed, more profound alterations were consistently observed. A key morphological signature was the significant disorganization of the basement membranes underlying the respiratory epithelium. Findings included focal thickening, homogenization, splitting, and the formation of discrete micro-defects or “tunnels,” interpreted as structural facilitators for cellular migration. Pronounced concentric perivascular and peribronchial fibrosis was ubiquitous, often forming characteristic “bulbous” structures encasing dust-laden macrophages. The most compelling data emerged from immunohistochemistry. Sclerotic foci demonstrated a high stromal density of cells strongly positive for α -smooth muscle actin (α -SMA), confirming a prominent population of activated myofibroblasts. Concurrently, a definitive phenotypic shift indicative of active EMT was documented: a marked reduction in the expression of the adhesion molecule E-cadherin in bronchial epithelial cells was paired with a substantial increase in the expression of the mesenchymal markers N-cadherin and vimentin within the stromal compartment. Furthermore, the Ki-67 proliferation index was significantly elevated not only within epithelial but also, notably, within stromal fibroblastic cell populations. Vascular remodeling was evidenced by endothelial hyperplasia (CD31+) and medial thickening in the microcirculatory bed.

The integrated results compel a revised understanding of occupational pneumoconiosis pathogenesis. The identified triad — systemic fibrotic remodeling, basement membrane disruption, and immunohistochemical evidence of EMT coupled with myofibroblast activation — indicates that PC is not a passive consequence of dust accumulation but an active, dysregulated biological process of chronic tissue injury and response [5, 6, 9, 10]. The central role of epithelial-mesenchymal transition, as validated by the E-cadherin to N-cadherin/vimentin switch, is critical [7, 8]. Under the persistent duress of particulate and inflammatory stimuli, airway epithelial cells undergo dedifferentiation, acquiring a mesenchymal progenitor-like state. These transformed cells contribute directly to fibrotic matrix overproduction

and, importantly, themselves exhibit pro-oncogenic traits such as enhanced survival, motility, and pro-inflammatory signaling. This radically transforms the character of the fibrotic stroma. The infiltrating α -SMA-positive myofibroblasts are functionally homologous to cancer-associated fibroblasts (CAFs), which are established master regulators of the tumor microenvironment in oncology [6, 11]. CAFs are potent modulators, fostering angiogenesis, suppressing anti-tumor immunity, and secreting paracrine factors that directly stimulate the proliferation and survival of potentially neoplastic cells. Therefore, the fibrotic tissue in PC evolves from a static lesion into a dynamic, biologically “primed” environment that orchestrates a permissive milieu for carcinogenic initiation and progression. This model offers a coherent pathogenetic explanation for the high prevalence of lung cancer in this cohort and suggests a mechanism for increased risk of extrapulmonary malignancies via the induction of a sustained systemic inflammatory and fibrogenic response [12, 13, 14]. The consistent late-stage (IV) diagnosis of cancers in the study group underscores a critical flaw in current surveillance, which relies on imaging to detect advanced structural changes rather than molecular precursors of risk.

In conclusion, this study provides evidence that occupational pneumoconiosis in miners represents a model of chronic, activated fibrogenesis intrinsically linked to the EMT process, transcending its classical definition as a localized sclerotic disorder. The fibrotic stroma, populated by activated myofibroblasts (putative CAFs) and cells undergoing EMT, constitutes the morphological substrate of an active pro-tumor niche, thereby establishing a plausible biological basis for the observed increase in systemic cancer risk. These findings justify a fundamental shift in occupational health strategy. The integration of biomarkers indicative of active fibrogenesis and EMT — potentially via IHC on biopsy material or assays for circulating factors — into enhanced medical surveillance protocols for high-risk workers is a promising avenue. This approach enables a transition from reactive diagnosis of advanced disease to predictive, personalized risk assessment and truly preventative oncology in this vital industrial population.

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VALVED AND NON-VALVED STRUCTURES OF THE LEFT RENAL VEIN AND THEIR SIGNIFICANCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PATHOLOGICAL PROCESSES

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Abstract. *In a morpho-hemodynamic study of 60 cadaveric specimens, it was demonstrated that the trunk of the left renal vein (LRV) and the left adrenal vein are valveless in 100% of cases, forming a basis for pathological reflux. A high frequency of valve incompetence was identified in the tributaries: gonadal (55%) and diaphragmatic (23.3%). Mathematical modeling demonstrated that the anatomical position of the LRV in the aorto-mesenteric 'pinch' predisposes to chronic venous hypertension and increased turbulence of blood flow. The synthesis of data allowed the formulation of a vicious cycle concept linking congenital anatomical features, acquired valvular insufficiency, and specific hemodynamics in the pathogenesis of left-sided varicocele, pelvic venous congestion syndrome, and pathologies of the left kidney and adrenal gland.*

Keywords: *left renal vein, valvular insufficiency, venous reflux, aorto-mesenteric compression, varicocele, pelvic venous congestion syndrome, hemodynamics, morphology, venous hypertension.*

Introduction

The territory of the left renal vein (LRV) is a high-risk area for the development of pathologies associated with venous hypertension and reflux, including Nutcracker syndrome, varicocele, pelvic varicose veins (PVV), as well as lesions affecting the left kidney and adrenal gland [1, 2, 3, 6]. Despite the recognized association, the comprehensive morphofunctional status of the valvular apparatus of the LRV tributaries remains insufficiently studied, complicating the understanding of its pathogenesis.

Structural characteristics of the region play a pivotal role. In 100% of cases, the left renal and adrenal veins are valveless, creating an anatomical basis for horizontal and vertical reflux, thereby rendering the left kidney and adrenal gland susceptible to retrograde pressure [4]. Simultaneously, a high frequency of tributary valve insufficiency is observed: gonadal valve insufficiency was detected in 55% of cases (a predisposing factor for varicocele and pelvic venous congestion syndrome), while relative insufficiency of the diaphragmatic valve was found in 23.3% [4, 5] (Fig. 1).

Hemodynamic analysis further elucidates the condition: a longer and wider course of the LRV in the presence of aorto-mesenteric compression predisposes to specific pressure losses, and the continual pulsatile impact of the arteries chronically sustains phlebogenic hypertension [5, 11].

Objective — integration of contemporary morphological and hemodynamic data to develop a comprehensive understanding of how valved and valveless features of the LRV basin influence the development of clinically significant pathological processes.

Methods and Principles of Investigation

This study involved an analysis of the valved structures within the left renal vein system using 60 cadaveric specimens from individuals aged 16 to 70 years. For each case, personal data, sex, age, cause and date of death, and time of autopsy were recorded. The postmortem interval did not exceed 20 hours. For anthropometric characterization, the trunk index was calculated (based on measurements of trunk length and height), and the somatotype was determined (brachy-, meso-, or dolichomorphic).

The study methodology included isolation of the organ complex using Shor's method, which comprised the left kidney with its renal vessels and ureter, the left adrenal gland with the central adrenal and diaphragmatic veins, the pancreas, the spleen, and the complete portal vein system. Preparation of the specimen for contrast involved placing the organ complex in a tray with water at room temperature for 2 hours to wash the vessels free of blood. Subsequently, the tributaries of the inferior vena cava, renal veins, portal vein, as well as the inferior and superior

mesenteric veins were ligated, and the vascular bed was filled with a radiopaque agent — an aqueous suspension of barium sulfate — followed by angiography.

Angiographic examination was conducted using RM-1 X-ray film with an exposure time of 0.2 seconds. The obtained images, after standard processing, were examined on a negatoscope with an evaluation of the venous structures. To preserve anatomical integrity and prevent deformation of the organs, the organ complex was placed on a gauze pad in a container with a 5% formalin solution following the examination.

Results

The primary causes of death in this patient group were trauma, poisoning, acute cardiovascular insufficiency, and diseases of the abdominal cavity and thoracic organs. The qualitative and quantitative characterization of valvular anomalies in the left renal vein (LRV) territory, obtained through a comprehensive morphological study of 60 cadaveric specimens using angiography, revealed a systemic and progressive pattern of disruptions that constitute the anatomical basis for chronic venous dysfunction. The key and most consistent finding was the complete absence of valvular structures in the main outflow pathways — the trunk of the left renal vein and the left adrenal vein, observed in 100% of cases (60/60) (Fig. 1) [2].

Fig. 1 — Specimens illustrating the normal state of the valvular structures of the left renal vein.

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This fact is not a random variation but represents a consistent anatomical feature that underlies fundamental hemodynamic disturbances in the region. The absence of a valvular barrier in the trunk of the LRV creates conditions conducive to the development of pathological horizontal reflux, whereby blood, under the influence of retrograde pressure, can freely flow back into the kidney's venous network. Similarly, the valveless structure of the left adrenal vein predisposes the formation of vertical ascending reflux flowing from the renal vein directly into the venous sinusoids of the adrenal gland. According to the pathogenetic hypothesis proposed by the authors, these persistent retrograde flows exert chronic mechanical and hemodynamic effects on the organ parenchyma and constitute a direct morphological basis for the development of a wide spectrum of pathological processes. In the left kidney, this may contribute to juxtaglomerular hypertension, interstitial fibrosis, and cyst formation, while in the left adrenal gland, it may create conditions for hemorrhages (hematomas), hyperplastic transformation (adenomatosis), as well as initiate or sustain tumor growth, including pheochromocytoma and incidentalomas. Thus, the initial 'vulnerability' of the main venous collectors transforms into a persistent risk factor for organ pathology [5].

Fig. 2 — Specimens illustrating gonadal valve insufficiency and isolated diaphragmatic valve insufficiency.

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Moreover, the study revealed a high prevalence of acquired or congenital defects of the valvular apparatus in the major tributaries of the LRV. The most frequent anomaly was gonadal valve insufficiency, diagnosed in 55% of cases (33/60) (Fig. 2).

This valve, which normally prevents the backflow of blood from the renal vein into the gonadal vein, loses its valvular function when insufficient. As a result, a distinctly directed descending vertical reflux occurs, wherein blood under elevated venous pressure from the LRV territory flows retrogradely into the gonadal vein and subsequently into the pampiniform venous plexus of the testis or the pelvic venous plexuses in women [2, 4]. This mechanism constitutes a direct anatomical and physiological basis for the development of clinically significant conditions: left-sided varicocele in men and pelvic venous congestion (PVC) in women [1, 2, 10, 12]. The correlation between the observed high incidence of valve insufficiency (55%) and the epidemiology of these conditions confirms the pivotal role of this defect in their pathogenesis [4, 5, 8, 9].

Another significant, though less frequent, anomaly is dysfunction of the diaphragmatic vein valve. Relative insufficiency of this valve was documented in 23.3% of cases (14/60) [2]. Relative insufficiency denotes that the valve is morphologically intact but unable to fully perform its function under conditions of chronically elevated pressure within the LRV system. Moreover, in 11.1% (3/27) of cases with an otherwise normal condition of the remaining valves, isolated insufficiency of the diaphragmatic valve was identified, indicating the possibility of its primary weakness. Since the diaphragmatic vein drains into the adrenal vein (or directly into the renal vein) at an acute angle, and the adrenal vein itself lacks valves, insufficiency of the diaphragmatic valve potentiates and exacerbates ascending reflux into the adrenal vein system. This combined reflux effect generates a strong pathological pressure gradient directed specifically at the cortical and medullary regions of the adrenal gland, potentially acting as an additional cofactor in the cascade of pathological changes in the organ [5].

Pathophysiological Mechanism and Hemodynamic Modeling. The identified morphological anomalies of the valvular apparatus are comprehensively explained and quantitatively substantiated through analysis of the unique hemodynamic conditions arising from the anatomical position and geometry of the left renal vein (LRV). A key external pathogenetic factor is the constant pulsatile mechanical compression of the LRV, which it undergoes in the so-called aorto-mesenteric ‘clamp’—an anatomical space bounded anteriorly by the trunk of the superior mesenteric artery (SMA) and posteriorly by the abdominal aorta [1, 4, 6]. Although the magnitude of this compressive effect may be minor at any given moment, its principal characteristic is its chronic, lifelong nature. For decades, the pulsations of two large arteries have been transmitted to the wall of a thin-walled

vein, causing not only periodic obstruction of the lumen but also continuous microvibration and mechanical stress on the endothelium. This factor is a direct driver of chronic venous hypertension in the proximal segment of the LRV [1, 5]. Increased retrograde pressure, in turn, acts as the principal force that reveals initially incompetent valves or provokes relative insufficiency of existing valves in the tributaries, thereby enhancing and stabilizing pathological reflux through the gonadal, diaphragmatic, and adrenal veins [4].

For the quantitative assessment of differences in blood flow conditions, the researchers performed comparative mathematical modeling of hemodynamics in the right (RRV) and left (LRV) renal veins, based on fundamental hydrodynamic principles — the Hagen-Poiseuille equation for laminar flow and the Darcy-Weisbach formula for calculating pressure losses [1]. The initial anatomical parameters incorporated into the model were: the length of the veins ($L(\text{LRV}) = 0.0058$ m versus $L(\text{RRV}) = 0.0024$ m) and their diameters ($d(\text{LRV}) = 0.0018$ m versus $d(\text{RRV}) = 0.0012$ m). Incorporation of these data along with blood viscosity constants and pressure gradients enabled the derivation of several critically important calculated parameters. The analysis confirmed that, despite similar final values of hydraulic pressure losses ($h_{\text{LRV}} = h_{\text{RRV}} = 0.00303$ m), the fluid flow conditions in the two veins differ fundamentally. The calculation of the Reynolds number (Re)—a dimensionless parameter determining the flow regime (laminar or turbulent)—was the most indicative. The Reynolds number (Re) for the LRV (≈ 92723.2) was significantly higher than that for the right renal vein (RRV) (≈ 66394.4). Although both values correspond to a turbulent regime, such a pronounced increase for the LRV unequivocally indicates a qualitatively greater degree of turbulence, instability, and chaotic blood flow within its lumen compared to the RRV [1]. This flow pattern has direct pathophysiological consequences: turbulent flow exerts increased damaging shear stress on the endothelium, contributing to its dysfunction and the activation of pro-inflammatory and prothrombotic mechanisms [7]. Furthermore, persistent turbulence and vortex formation impose additional hemodynamic stress on the orifices of the tributaries and the remaining valvular structures, potentiating their secondary trauma and progressive degeneration, thereby perpetuating the vicious cycle of valvular insufficiency and reflux [4].

The synthesis of morphological, hemodynamic, and mathematical data obtained enables the conceptualization of the left renal vein (LRV) basin not as a mere assembly of disparate vessels, but as an integral and highly integrated functional system wherein the condition of each element critically depends on the others. In this system, primary anatomical anomalies of key components (complete absence of valves in the main trunks — LRV and the left adrenal vein) synergistically interact with acquired or constitutional defects of peripheral elements (valvular insufficiency of the gonadal and diaphragmatic veins). This interaction

generates a self-sustaining pathophysiological vicious cycle characterized by three interrelated processes [1, 2, 4, 5].

Firstly, the basis of the pathology is chronic venous hypertension in the LRV territory. It arises as a result of the combination of external compression (the 'aorto-mesenteric clamp') and intrinsic hemodynamic insufficiency caused by valve incompetence in the trunks and the turbulent nature of blood flow [1, 4, 5]. This elevated venous pressure is not a passive consequence but an active pathogenetic factor that persistently stretches the venous walls and opens the orifices of tributaries.

Secondly, against the background of this hypertension, a system of pathological refluxes of three clearly defined types develops, each with its own direction and clinical target: 1) Horizontal reflux occurs directly in the trunk of the LRV due to the absence of valves; its vector is directed retrogradely from the renal vein toward the kidney, creating conditions for overload and damage to its venous bed. 2) Descending vertical reflux occurs through the gonadal vein due to valve insufficiency; the blood flow moves downward into the pampiniform plexus of the testis or the pelvic venous plexuses [2, 4, 10]. 3) Ascending vertical reflux arises through the adrenal and diaphragmatic vein systems due to their valveless condition and relative insufficiency of the diaphragmatic vein valve; this flow is directed upward into the adrenal gland parenchyma [2, 4, 5]. This triad of refluxes results in not a local but a total dysfunction of the entire venous basin.

Thirdly, the persistent presence of this complex — hypertension combined with multidirectional reflux — consistently manifests as a spectrum of specific clinical nosologies. Descending reflux through the gonadal vein is the direct cause of left-sided varicocele in men and pelvic venous congestion syndrome (PVCS) in women, corresponding to the identified high prevalence (55%) of gonadal valve incompetence [1, 2, 8, 9, 12, 13]. Horizontal and ascending refluxes create a unique, continuously active pathological environment for the parenchyma of the left kidney and left adrenal gland [2, 4, 5]. In the kidney, chronic retrograde venous congestion may potentiate the development of interstitial fibrosis, cyst formation, and also affect the function of the juxtaglomerular apparatus, potentially contributing to renovascular arterial hypertension. In the adrenal gland, a constant inflow of venous blood under elevated pressure may act as a factor provoking microhemorrhages, hyperplasia of the cortical and medullary tissue, and may also promote tumor processes such as adenomas and pheochromocytomas [2, 4]. Thus, the identified anatomical and hemodynamic abnormalities evolve from a theoretical model into a framework explaining the etiology of a group of diseases characterized by common venous dysfunction of the left renal-adrenal region [4, 5, 6].

Conclusion

This comprehensive study convincingly demonstrates that the valveless structure of the primary trunks within the LRV basin is not a normal variant, but a key predisposing anatomical factor which, together with acquired valve insufficiency in the gonadal and diaphragmatic veins, creates a unique hemodynamic environment conducive to the development of chronic regional venous pathology. The obtained results warrant further research to quantitatively assess the contribution of these mechanisms to the development of specific diseases of the adrenal glands and kidneys.

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**PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF PATHOLOGICAL CHANGES
IN THE MUCOUS MEMBRANE OF THE DENTURE BED DURING
THE PERIOD OF ADAPTATION TO REMOVABLE DENTURES IN
ELDERLY AND SENILE PATIENTS**

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Abstract. *In Russia, the proportion of elderly and senile individuals ranges from 15 to 35% of the total population across various regions. Factors contributing to the development of inflammatory processes in the mucous membrane of the oral cavity during the use of removable dental prostheses have been identified. These include mechanical trauma, poor oral hygiene, as well as a decrease in systemic and local immunity. Clinical observations indicate that after 3–7 days of using removable dental prostheses, hyperemia appears on the mucous membrane of the denture bed. Fourteen days after the insertion of removable dentures, this*

*phenomenon diminishes, and after one month approaches normal values. There is a correlation between the severity of inflammation, immunological parameters of mixed saliva, and the microflora of the oral cavity. In elderly and senile patients, following the insertion of removable dentures, there is a noted increase in fungi of the genus *Candida albicans*. When fitting removable plate dentures during the adaptation period, it is necessary to combine therapeutic and prophylactic effects, including anti-inflammatory, antifungal, and immunological agents.*

Keywords: *adaptation, removable dentures, elderly and senile patients, local immunity of the oral cavity.*

There is a significant increase in the elderly population both in Russia and worldwide. In Russia, the proportion of elderly individuals ranges from 15 to 35% of the total population across various regions. Furthermore, the number of people over 60 years of age is steadily increasing [4]. Elderly individuals often encounter additional challenges due to oral cavity health issues. Dental diseases can cause pain, impair chewing and swallowing, cause discomfort, disrupt speech, and hinder communication, ultimately impacting quality of life and potentially leading to social isolation. Research indicates that dental problems in elderly individuals are frequently advanced and require substantial intervention. This is due to limited access to timely and quality dental care, as well as a shortage of affordable options for treating teeth and periodontium, and for fabricating high-quality dentures. It is recommended to develop specialized dental care programs for elderly individuals at the pre-retirement stage, when their health permits them to independently attend dental clinics. Primary attention should be given to tooth restoration and rational prosthetics to prevent potential issues with the dentoalveolar system in the future. Sanitation of the oral cavity, periodontal treatment, and therapeutic maintenance should be provided through dental care programs, including prosthetics tailored to the patient's age and condition. Special attention should be given to the prevention of diseases of the oral cavity, adherence to hygiene, correction of hygienic skills, and the use of appropriate dental care products. Removable dentures remain the most accessible means of restoring masticatory function in elderly patients who often lack the financial means to utilize modern high-tech treatment methods. A removable denture made of acrylic resin contains various components such as plasticizers, inhibitors, and dyes, which may provoke inflammatory and allergic reactions upon contact with the mucous membrane of the oral cavity. Chemical components released from the acrylic base may act as toxins and allergens, complicating the determination of the onset of allergic reactions. During the use of a removable prosthesis in the oral cavity, substances are produced that can adversely affect various resistance factors, both specific and nonspecific. This can lead to suppression of local immunity. Clinicians have identified factors contributing to

the development of inflammatory processes in the mucous membrane of the oral cavity during the use of removable dental prostheses: mechanical trauma, poor oral hygiene, and reduced immunity of the patient's oral cavity. These factors are more frequently observed in elderly and senile patients [10].

Clinical observations by researchers confirmed that after 3 days of wearing removable plate dentures, hyperemia develops on the mucous membrane of the denture bed. This marks the onset of an inflammatory reaction of the mucous membrane of the denture bed. However, after 14 days the inflammation diminishes, and after 1 month it is no longer present. The mechanical impact of removable dental prostheses affects the trophism of the oral cavity tissues, resulting from insufficient oxygen supply to these tissues. Impairment of microcirculation is observed. This dystrophic phenomenon leads to an inflammatory process. There is a correlation between the severity of inflammation in the soft tissues of the oral cavity, the immunological parameters of the oral fluid, and the microflora of the oral cavity [7].

The qualitative and quantitative composition of the oral cavity microflora must remain constant. The biological equilibrium between the patient's organism and the microbial flora is maintained by the patient's physiological processes. It also directly influences the normal function of the salivary glands and the mucous membrane of the oral cavity. The normal microbial flora serves as a biological barrier and a constant stimulator of local immunity in the oral cavity. It exerts a positive effect on the patient's organism as a whole. Changes in the balance of microorganisms lead to a reduction in the protective properties of the microflora, subsequently resulting in infection. The placement of removable plate dentures introduces a traumatic factor. This factor affects the proliferation of pathogenic microbial flora and the development of diseases in the oral mucous membrane. In elderly and senile patients, following the placement of removable dental prostheses, an increase in *Candida albicans* is observed, resulting in an inflammatory process. Additionally, denture plaque may contain *Str. milleri*, *Str. salivarius*, *Str. faecialis*, *D. pneumoniae*, *Neisseria*, *Klebsiella*, and *Fusospirochetes*. Microorganisms become activated, releasing toxins that induce inflammation and other pathological reactions in the organism. Microorganism activity on denture surfaces alters immunological reactivity and induces sensitization, resulting in the formation of antigen-antibody complexes. Activation of the complement system and the release of biologically active mediators lead to enhanced phagocytosis, immune adhesion, and chemotaxis of neutrophils. Resistance of the tissue structures of the denture bed to mechanical stress decreases due to the prolonged presence of bacterial antigens. The solution to this problem lies in improving the effectiveness of prevention and treatment of candidiasis by targeting the local immunity of the patient's oral cavity. [2]

Removable acrylic dentures are essentially composite irritants that exert a complex of negative effects on the mucous membrane; the longer they are used, the more

pronounced the pathological processes become, particularly within the microcirculatory system. Their hygienic condition deteriorates, and microbial contamination increases, which subsequently leads to chronic inflammation, causes destructive changes in the denture bed tissues, and may adversely affect the entire organism. During the adaptation period to removable dental prostheses, it is necessary to combine therapeutic and preventive measures, including anti-inflammatory, immunological agents, as well as antifungal and antibacterial drugs [1, 9]. The primary factor of specific antimicrobial defense is immunoglobulins: s-IgA, IgA, and Ig G. Their specific reactivity decreases under the influence of removable dental prostheses [5].

Saliva is a highly complex medium, the composition of which directly affects the tissues of the oral cavity and the body as a whole. Following the placement of removable dental prostheses, local immunity levels in the oral fluid undergo changes. The pH of the oral cavity is altered. This impacts the activity of lysozyme. Immunity indicators in the oral fluid influence the adaptation to removable dental prostheses in patients following their placement. The progression of inflammation reflects a diminished specific immune response. In patients with a prolonged inflammatory process, reduced specific immunity is observed. It is necessary to influence the inflammatory process and perform correction of the immune system. Different changes in the quantitative content of immunoglobulins are observed depending on the dental materials used for the fabrication of removable dentures. The greater the proliferation of pathogenic microflora on the surface of removable dentures, the more pronounced the quantitative content of secretory immunoglobulins [3, 6].

In this regard, it can be concluded that during the adaptation period to removable dentures, one of the relevant approaches to the prevention and treatment of pathological changes in the mucous membrane of the denture bed in patients is maintaining it in a functionally active state. For this purpose, implementing measures that promote the improvement of trophism, metabolism, and blood circulation in the mucous membrane is highly relevant. During the stages of adaptation to removable dental prostheses, the significant role of local immunity status in the oral cavity and changes in the quantitative composition of immunoglobulins in mixed saliva have been established. For analyzing adaptation to removable dentures in elderly and senile patients, it is necessary, following an assessment of local immunity, to include the use of immunomodulatory agents that facilitate its acceleration. The study of cellular components of innate immunity may serve as a key criterion for evaluating successful adaptation to removable dentures. The time required to adapt to the use of a removable denture depends on several factors, including the type of denture, the condition of the oral cavity, the method of fixation, and individual psychosomatic characteristics. Compliance with all stages of the fabrication and application technology of the prosthesis can significantly accelerate the adaptation process to orthopedic devices.

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**DEVELOPMENT OF A PROGRAM FOR THE INDIVIDUAL
PREVENTION OF DENTAL DISEASES IN CHILDREN
WITH DOWN SYNDROME**

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Abstract. *It is known that Down syndrome is not a rare pathology, with an average incidence of one case per 700 births worldwide. The study of the dental status of children with Down syndrome, the identification of risk factors for dental diseases such as periodontitis and caries, and the development of an individualized dental disease prevention program are essential. A total of 102 children aged between 8 and 12 years were examined to analyze dental status and investigate the risk factors for the development of primary dental diseases. To obtain more detailed information about the socio-economic living conditions of families with children, a questionnaire survey was conducted. The clinical examination of the patient's oral cavity included: external examination of the child, inspection of the oral mucous membrane, frenula, bands, hard dental tissues, as well as assessment of occlusal status. The effectiveness of oral hygiene was assessed using PHP. An individualized prevention program was developed for children with genetic pathology. It has been established that factors reducing the effectiveness of the prevention program include: impaired mental development of the child, specific somatic characteristics of children with Down syndrome, socio-economic factors, and parents' attitudes towards their own health and that of their children.*

Keywords: *dental disease prevention, Down syndrome, prevention program, educational activities.*

Relevance of the problem

In recent years, congenital malformations have ranked first in the assessment of morbidity and mortality among the pediatric population. It is known that Down syndrome is not a rare pathology, with an average incidence of one case per 700 births worldwide. However, in Russia, many issues concerning the practical rehabilitation of children with Down syndrome remain unresolved [1]. The dental status of children with Down syndrome residing in Russia is insufficiently studied; however, these children particularly require dental sanitation due to unsatisfactory oral hygiene [3,7]. Oral hygiene management in such children is highly challenging and causes numerous difficulties for parents due to malocclusion or non-cooperative behavior of the children [2,4]. There is a high prevalence of periodontitis, caries, and an increased occurrence of dentoalveolar anomalies. The development of individualized prevention programs for children with genetic pathologies remains insufficiently explored [5,6].

Therefore, it is essential to study the dental status of children with Down syndrome, identify risk factors for periodontitis and caries development, and develop an individualized prevention program for dental diseases.

Objective of the study: to develop an individualized prevention program for caries and periodontal diseases and to identify factors reducing its effectiveness.

Materials and methods of the study

A total of 102 children aged between 8 and 12 years were examined to analyze dental status and investigate the risk factors for the development of primary dental diseases. All examined children were divided into two main groups: the first group included 38 children with Down syndrome; the second group included 64 practically healthy children without hereditary diseases.

Children with Down syndrome were examined at the rehabilitation center ‘Sail of Hope,’ where they had been monitored since their initial visit. Clinical examinations of the children were performed by specialist physicians from the rehabilitation center ‘Parus Nadezhdy’ department, following standard methodologies. Examinations of clinically healthy children were conducted at the dental clinic of N. N. Burdenko VGMU. The number of decayed, missing, and filled teeth and surfaces (DMF+dmf), the PMA index, and oral hygiene effectiveness (PHP) were assessed before and one year after the implementation of the prevention program. To obtain more detailed information on the socio-economic living conditions of families with children, a questionnaire survey was conducted. The clinical examination of the patient’s oral cavity included: external examination of the child, inspection of

the oral mucous membrane, frenula, bands, hard dental tissues, as well as assessment of occlusal status. The effectiveness of oral hygiene was assessed using PHP.

Research Results

The number of teeth affected by carious lesions in patients with Down syndrome was higher than in children from the comparison group (5.2 ± 1.48 in group 1, 4.1 ± 2.4 in group 2) ($p < 0.05$). The mean value of the DMF surface index was 7.9 ± 2.85 in group 1 and 5.7 ± 4.71 in group 2 ($p < 0.05$). In children with Down syndrome, the PMA index values were significantly higher, at $26.8 \pm 10.4\%$, compared to $8.9 \pm 4.57\%$ in the control group ($p < 0.005$). The mean PHP index in children with Down syndrome was 3.4 ± 0.87 points, while in the control group it was 1.6 ± 0.59 . The differences are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Poor oral hygiene in children with Down syndrome is attributed to the peculiarities of their general somatic condition. When examining the frequency of tooth brushing, it was found that only 2 children (6%) with Down syndrome brush their teeth twice a day, 18 children (47%) brush irregularly, and 18 children (47%) brush once a day.

All children with Down syndrome use incorrect tooth brushing techniques; among them, only 25 (66%) perform this procedure independently. The remaining 13 (34%) patients have their teeth brushed by their parents. In the comparison group, only 10 children (16%) brush their teeth irregularly, 12 children (19%) brush twice a day, and 42 children (65%) brush once a day. Three indicators of sugar consumption frequency were identified: consumption of sweets at every meal; once a day; and once a week. After each meal, cariogenic foods were consumed by 16 children (42%) with Down syndrome and 34 children (53%) in the comparison group. Approximately 20 children (53%) with the genetic pathology consumed sweets once a day, compared to 26 children (41%) in the comparison group. Sweets were consumed once a week by 2 (5%) children with Down syndrome. To obtain more detailed information about the socio-economic living conditions of families with children, a questionnaire survey was conducted. A total of 102 questionnaires were analyzed.

The study results demonstrated that 29 children (76%) with Down syndrome reside in families with low and very low living standards, while in the comparison group only 33 children (52%) do. An average living standard was characteristic of families of 9 children with genetic pathology (24%) and 20 children (31%) without this pathology. A high living standard was characteristic only of 11 families in the comparison group (17%). The social status of parents of children with Down syndrome is represented by the following categories: workers — 21 individuals (55%), office employees — 12 individuals (32%), unemployed — 5 individuals (13%). In the comparison group, office employees predominated — 41 individuals (64%), with unemployed and workers accounting for 5 (8%) and 18 (28%) individuals, respectively. Comparison of the compliance parameter between the two

groups indicates somewhat lower adherence to the physician's recommendations in the group of children with Down syndrome. Only 5 children (13%) and their parents complied with all medical prescriptions, compared to 21 children (33%) in the control group.

Undoubtedly, the adverse oral conditions in children with Down syndrome, along with general risk factors, contributed to the high prevalence of caries and periodontal diseases. We developed and implemented a prevention program for dental diseases (caries and periodontal diseases), targeting the elimination of local risk factors and the improvement of oral health among the children. The prevention program includes the following stages: 1 — preparatory stage; 2 — preventive and educational work; 3 — implementation stage.

The preparatory stage of the prevention program involves adapting the child to the dental office environment and to specialist physicians. Examination, consultation, preparation of medical documentation, and conducting a sanitary-educational discussion with the parents. Simultaneously, general risk factors for the development of major dental diseases were identified. A plan of dental interventions is developed and coordinated with the child's parents.

The second stage involved training the child and parents in proper oral hygiene. A discussion was held with teachers (educators), medical personnel of the children's institution, and psychologists, during which the aims and objectives of dental prevention were explained, emphasizing that the success and efficacy of the preventive measures largely depend on their engagement and rigor. We responded to all the questions posed by the teaching staff, aiming to enlist teachers and educators as allies in promoting the dental health of children. The main content of the sessions aimed at preventing dental diseases included training on proper oral hygiene; recommendations on rational nutrition (limiting carbohydrate consumption); prevention of harmful habits; rationales for the necessity of periodic examinations and fostering a conscious attitude towards the prevention and treatment of dental diseases; Understanding the importance of healthy teeth and overall health. For children, dental disease prevention activities were conducted in the form of plays titled "The Tooth Fairy and Neznaika Visiting Children," with the distribution of gifts.

For children in the second group without genetic pathology, lessons on dental disease prevention were organized. In grades 1 and 2, "Health Lessons" were conducted on the topic: "The Role of Proper Nutrition in the Prevention of Caries." In grades 3–4, 'Health Lessons' were conducted on the topic: "Prevention of caries and its complications." In grades 5–6, on the topic: "Oral hygiene." Hygiene lessons, including training in hygienic oral care skills, were conducted at least twice a year with monitoring of compliance.

All children received training in effective oral hygiene using jaw models, toothbrushes, and toothpaste.

The third stage is the implementation stage. Monitoring the accuracy of hygienic procedures. Formulation of a treatment plan and informing the child's parents. Professional hygiene and oral cavity sanitation. Implementation of measures from the prevention program.

One year after the preventive interventions, the average CPITN and carious teeth indices were 5.3 ± 0.31 in the first group and 4.1 ± 0.23 in the second group. The increase in caries was higher in the group of children with Down syndrome-0.2-compared to the comparison group-0.1. The mean PMA index decreased from $26.8 \pm 10.4\%$ to $21.4 \pm 1.41\%$ ($p < 0.05$), while in children from the control group, it decreased from $8.9 \pm 10.42\%$ to $6.8 \pm 0.43\%$ ($p < 0.05$). An improvement in oral hygiene effectiveness was noted. Following the preventive measures implemented, an improvement in oral hygiene effectiveness was also observed. If the initial PHP index in group 1 was -3.3 ± 0.98 , after one year it was -2.4 ± 0.14 ($p < 0.05$). However, the effectiveness of oral hygiene remained unsatisfactory. In the comparison group, the mean PHP index was 1.7 ± 0.63 before the preventive procedures and 1.3 ± 0.11 after ($p < 0.05$). Following the implemented preventive measures, an improvement in the effectiveness of oral hygiene was observed in children without genetic pathology.

Conclusion

Based on the above analysis, it can be concluded that the proposed individualized prevention program was most effective in children without genetic pathology. Unfortunately, the influence of uncontrolled risk factors on the effectiveness of preventive measures in children with Down syndrome was significant. Factors diminishing the effectiveness of the prevention program include the child's mental developmental disorders, somatic characteristics of children with Down syndrome, the socio-economic factor, and the parents' attitudes toward their own health and that of their children. The family's social status and low economic level of living are common factors statistically associated with an increased risk of caries. The health status of a child with Down syndrome is strongly influenced by environmental factors. Thus, a low family economic level increases the likelihood of inadequate nutrition, overcrowded living conditions, and is often associated with excessive maternal employment, lack of awareness, and consequently, insufficient care for the child. It should be noted that the effectiveness of the proposed dental disease prevention program could have been significantly higher if 87% of parents of children with genetic pathology had demonstrated greater awareness and responsibility for their children's dental health. Preventive measures consist of simple procedures, most of which can be performed by patients themselves and their parents. The most challenging part is convincing them of its necessity. Creating conditions for the harmonious growth and development of the child, particularly of the dentoalveolar system, can only be ensured through the combined efforts of parents, dental practitioners, and hygienists.

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**MULTI-STAGE AND MULTIDISCIPLINARY APPROACH
TO THE TREATMENT OF PALLIATIVE PATIENTS
OF YOUNGER AGE GROUP**

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Abstract. *Over the past decade, Russia has experienced a significant decline in infant and childhood mortality, increased survival of extremely premature infants, as well as of patients with oncological, hereditary, and severe, prognostically unfavorable diseases. However, concurrently with this positive trend, the number of children with disabilities due to conditions limiting life expectancy is increasing. In 1998, The World Health Organization has defined the provision of palliative care to children as a distinct and critically important issue of medico-social assistance. Palliative care — is a clinical specialty developed for the prognosis, prevention, and treatment of physical, psychological, social, and spiritual suffering, applying a consistent approach across all age groups, from the prenatal period to old age [1]. This refers to active and comprehensive care for the body, mind, and spirit of a child suffering from a life-threatening disease or condition, as well as support for family members (caregivers) during the child's illness and following their death. The objective is to enhance the child's quality of life by alleviating physical, psychological, social, and spiritual suffering of both the child and their family members or caregivers through psychosocial support before and*

after the death of a terminally ill loved one [2]. According to some estimates, the number of children requiring palliative care worldwide reaches 21 million [3,4]. The demand for palliative care services in neonatal intensive care units is increasing. Infants who previously died at an early age in neonatal intensive care units can now undergo prolonged hospitalization prior to death. [5,6]. Thus, in the United Kingdom, the prevalence of life-threatening or life-limiting conditions among children aged 0 to 19 years is 30–45 cases per 10,000 population and continues to increase [7]. The spectrum of diseases requiring palliative care and leading to death in childhood and adolescence includes malignant neoplasms (8%) and non-oncological pathology (92%), of which severe congenital malformations (CM) account for 44%, cardiovascular system lesions — 23%, diseases of the neonatal period — 12%, diseases of the nervous system — 12%, and others — 9%. Annually, in Russia, palliative care is provided to more than 34,000 children with congenital malformations and over 9,000 infants with diseases of the neonatal period [8,9]. The number of such patients is increasing year by year, causing serious concern among neonatologists, anesthesiologist-resuscitators, pediatric surgeons, pediatricians, and healthcare administrators. Thus, the development of treatment and care algorithms for newborns and infants with palliative status currently represents one of the primary priorities of healthcare.

The aim of our study was to identify the disease structure, optimal diagnostic algorithm, and the conservative and surgical treatment approaches for palliative patients in the younger age group.

Keywords: *palliative patients, infants, children.*

Materials and Methods of the Study

A retrospective cohort analysis of clinical cases of palliative care provided to infants was conducted at the Regional State Autonomous Healthcare Institution ‘City Ivano-Matreninskaya Children’s Clinical Hospital’, Department of Anesthesiology, Resuscitation, and Intensive Care No. 2, from June 2020 to August 2025. A total of 1830 medical records were analyzed. The study included 70 children aged from 1 month to 1 year, of whom 38 were boys, 32 girls, and 51 were premature infants. Medical records of 43 patients, assigned palliative status based on a single primary disease, and 27 records of patients with a combined primary diagnosis were analyzed.

The decision to assign palliative status to a patient was made in accordance with the Order of the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Russian Federation dated May 31, 2019 No. 345n/372n ‘On the Approval of the Regulation on the Organization of Palliative Medical Care, including the Procedure for Interaction among Medical Organizations, Social Service Organizations, Public Associations, and Other Non-Profit Organizations Operating

in the Healthcare Sector,' by a commission consisting of the deputy chief physician for therapeutic work, a specialist physician in palliative care, a neonatologist, an intensivist, a neurologist, a pulmonologist, a cardiologist, a pediatric surgeon, a neurosurgeon, an ophthalmologist, and a rehabilitation specialist. As an additional criterion for assessing the indications for assigning palliative status, the PaPaS scale (Paediatric Palliative Screening Scale) [10] was utilized. The commission meeting was conducted with the participation of the child's legal representatives.

An evaluation of concomitant pathology of the central nervous system, respiratory, cardiovascular systems, and gastrointestinal organs, as well as their impact on the outcome of the primary disease, was performed. The extent of clinical-laboratory and instrumental examinations, conservative treatment strategies, indications and timing for surgical interventions, and disease outcomes were established.

Results

From June 2020 to August 2025, 70 children were admitted to ICU No. 2 of OGAUZ GIMDKB, all assigned palliative status due to incurable diseases.

According to the primary pathology, the patients were distributed as follows (Tables 1 and 2).

Table 1. *Distribution of patients by single primary diagnosis*

Diagnosis	Number
Diseases of the CNS	16
Multiple congenital malformations	12
Bronchopulmonary dysplasia	8
Intestinal diseases	4
Chromosomal disorder	3
Total	43

Table 2. *Distribution of patients with combined primary diagnoses*

Diagnosis	Number
Bronchopulmonary dysplasia Perinatal CNS injury	12
Intestinal disease Perinatal CNS injury	6
Multiple congenital malformations Perinatal CNS injury	3
Multiple congenital malformations Intestinal disease	2

Diagnosis	Number
Multiple congenital malformations Bronchopulmonary dysplasia	1
Mitochondrial disorder Perinatal CNS injury	1
Mitochondrial disorder Cardiomyopathy	1
Bronchopulmonary dysplasia Intestinal disease	1
Total	27

Comorbid pathology is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. *Comorbid pathology*

Comorbid disease	Number
Diseases of the nervous system	164
Hematological disorders	116
Metabolic disorders	104
Respiratory diseases	79
Gastrointestinal diseases	77
Prematurity	50
Cardiovascular diseases	34
Ophthalmic diseases	27
Musculoskeletal diseases	15
Diseases of the urinary system	14
Infectious diseases	13
Perinatal exposure to infectious diseases	8
Cytomegalovirus infection	7
Diseases of the maxillofacial region	2

The extent of clinical, laboratory, and instrumental examinations was determined by the nature of the primary and concomitant pathology and was adjusted according to the clinical situation. In addition to the standard general clinical minimum, rigorous bacteriological monitoring was performed.

All children were observed by a neurologist, neonatologist, ophthalmologist, pulmonologist, and cardiologist; in cases of intracranial hemorrhagic syndrome and/or hydrocephalus, a neurosurgeon was also involved. In cases of surgical pathology, pediatric surgeons were engaged in the examination. The additional instrumental examination included regular neurosonography and echocardiography. Radiological diagnostic methods were applied as indicated.

Conservative treatment included a comprehensive set of patient care measures, respiratory support, and pharmacological therapy. Sixty-two (88.6%) patients had respiratory failure requiring various types of respiratory support, selected according to the severity of respiratory insufficiency:

- supplemental oxygen delivery via nasal cannula — 13 (21%) patients;
- non-invasive assisted lung ventilation (NIV) — 20 (32.2%) patients;
- invasive artificial lung ventilation (ILV) — 29 (46.8%) infants.

The extent of pharmacological therapy was determined by the characteristics of the primary and concomitant pathologies. In the absence of contraindications to treatment and weaning, physiotherapy specialists were actively engaged to conduct courses of massage and therapeutic physical exercises. The procedure of peritoneal dialysis was performed in five patients (7.1%).

Following the assignment of palliative status to 37 patients in the study group, 51 surgical procedures were performed (Table No. 4).

Table 4. *List of surgical interventions*

Name of the surgical procedure	Number
Antireflux surgery + gastrostomy + tracheostomy	10
Gastrostomy + Nissen antireflux surgery	5
Tracheostomy	4
Tracheostomy + gastrostomy	4
Panretinal laser coagulation of avascular zones of the retina with elements of demarcation coagulation	3
Reconstruction of the intestinal tube lumen	3
Ventriculosubgaleal shunting	2
Ventriculoperitoneal shunting	2
Suturing of intestinal perforation	2
Gastrostomy	1
Relaparotomy with abdominal cavity organs revision	1
Abdominal cavity revision with intestinal biopsy	1
Ileostomy reconstruction	1
Nissen anti-reflux procedure	1
Drainage of the pleural cavity	1
Chemical pleurodesis	1
Inguinal herniorrhaphy with gastrostomy and tracheostomy	1
Percutaneous cholecystostomy	1
Suturing of fundoplication cuff perforation	1
Ventriculo-subgaleal shunting combined with Nissen anti-reflux procedure and gastrostomy	1
Triventriculocysternostomy	1

Ventriculo-subgaleal shunting combined with laparotomy and bowel resection	1
Anoplasty	1
Lung biopsy	1
Ileostomy	1
Total	51

The duration of stay of palliative patients in the ICU depended on the severity of the child’s condition, the dynamics of clinical and laboratory parameters, and the need for replacement respiratory or renal therapy (Table No. 5).

Table 5. Duration of patient stay in the ICU

year	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
number of children	10	15	7	15	18	7
minimum number of days	3	1	3	3	4	1
maximum number of days	72	100	136	82	215	60
median	14	13	47	38	24	29

After stabilization of their condition, children were transferred from the ICU to other hospital departments or to regional medical institutions equipped with palliative care beds for further treatment and convalescence. Three children were transferred to a hospice. The overall mortality rate among palliative patients was 22.9% (Table 6).

Table 6 Mortality

Year	Total number of patients	Number of fatal outcomes
2020	10	1
2021	14	7
2022	7	1
2023	15	2
2024	17	5
2025	7	1
Total	70	16

Discussion

Among 1830 patients treated in ICU No. 2 from June 2020 to August 2025, 70 children were assigned palliative status (3.8%). The predominant cause for assigning palliative status to infants was diseases of the nervous system, both as the sole primary condition and as part of a combined diagnosis. This was followed by BLD and MVRP.

When discussing the structure of diseases, it should be noted that in 27 (28.7%) cases the primary diagnosis was combined, consisting of two diseases, as both conditions contributed equally to the pathogenesis and determined the severity of the patients' state, or had equal importance in thanatogenesis.

Comorbid pathology significantly influenced the severity of the patients' condition and the disease outcomes. Respiratory failure was diagnosed in more than 85% of palliative patients and was generally due to a combination of etiological factors: severe irreversible CNS damage, presence of bulbar and pseudobulbar disorders, development of pneumonia including aspiration pneumonia on the background of gastroesophageal reflux (GER), and formation of bronchopulmonary dysplasia as a result of prolonged oxygen therapy and mechanical ventilation.

It should be noted that there were limitations to performing non-invasive lung ventilation due to craniofacial malformations and the presence of gastroesophageal reflux. Thus, in the presence of GER, the continuous flow of the respiratory mixture generated by the device during NIV led to aerophagia, which aggravated the aspiration syndrome.

Diseases of the nervous system, as comorbid pathology, were present in the vast majority of children and significantly complicated the prospects of successful therapy for palliative patients.

A critical problem in neonatal and pediatric intensive care units is anemia. Despite our efforts to minimize hematological testing, anemia requiring hemotransfusions occurred in 54 (77%) children. It is well known that the greater the number of hemotransfusions, the higher the risk of transfusion-related complications [11]. A total of 215 erythrocyte suspension transfusions were administered based on clinical indications, averaging 3 hemotransfusions per patient.

In more than 50% of cases, the assignment of palliative status was due to diseases associated with prematurity. These conditions include bronchopulmonary dysplasia, necrotizing enterocolitis and its sequelae, and perinatal damage to the central nervous system. Among all palliative patients, there were 51 (72.9%) premature infants, of whom 24 had a gestational age between 22 and 27 weeks, 15 between 28 and 32 weeks, and 12 between 33 and 37 weeks.

In the examination and treatment of palliative patients, we adhered to the principle of *minimal sufficiency*; however, we paid particular attention to certain studies, such as bacteriological monitoring. Given the duration and continuity of patients' hospital stays and the near-universal acquisition of nosocomial flora with the development of infectious processes, bacteriological testing was performed on all patients without exception. All available potentially sterile biological media underwent bacteriological examination. The results of bacteriological monitoring were always considered when prescribing or adjusting antibacterial therapy.

It should be emphasized that we carefully minimized laboratory investigations involving blood sampling in infants. Frequent and varied hematological tests inevitably contribute to the development of iatrogenic anemia, which is particularly pertinent in critically ill patients with compromised hematopoiesis. Consequently, there is a need for multiple hemotransfusions, which is accompanied by a high risk of complications related to blood component transfusions, prolonged hospital or intensive care stays, and increased treatment costs [11].

The restriction of radiological diagnostic methods in intensive care is due to the high cumulative radiation exposure in children. Specifically, routine chest radiography was not performed and was replaced by ultrasound examination whenever possible.

Pharmacotherapy generally included an extensive list of agents, such as anti-bacterial, anticonvulsant, antiviral, vasoactive, neurometabolic drugs, glucocorticosteroids, components of parenteral nutrition and infusion therapy, diuretics, and others. taking into account the severe comorbidity of palliative patients.

An important issue is the feeding of palliative infants, as it is indisputable that a 'non-fed' patient has significantly lower chances of a favorable outcome compared to a patient receiving adequate enteral nutrition. The primary causes of the 'inability' to provide adequate enteral nutrition were GER and severe intestinal insufficiency developing in patients repeatedly operated on gastrointestinal organs. In several cases, feeding difficulties led to the development of conditions such as protein-energy malnutrition, TPN (total parenteral nutrition)-associated liver injury, osteopenia (complicated by fractures of tubular bones in 4 cases), metabolic disorders, translocation syndrome, and bloodstream infection in the context of prolonged central venous catheterization.

In cases of diagnosed GER, the treatment protocol included dietary correction, positional therapy, and transpyloric administration of milk formula. If conservative measures proved ineffective, surgical treatment was performed.

Following the assignment of palliative status, surgical treatment was performed in 37 (53%) children. In addition to surgeries related to the multistage correction of surgical diseases, operative interventions aimed at facilitating the treatment and care of palliative patients, such as gastrostomy and tracheostomy, were performed.

Among 70 children with palliative status, 48 (68.5%) infants exhibited severe irreversible central nervous system damage, accompanied by bulbar and pseudobulbar dysfunctions, gastroesophageal reflux, and respiratory failure, including that of central origin. Aspiration of milk formula and oropharyngeal contents is a cause of prolonged pneumonia refractory to conservative treatment. The presence of an endotracheal tube does not fully isolate the airways; moreover, it constitutes a risk factor for the development of nosocomial pneumonia [12]. Prolonged presence of a feeding tube in the esophagus combined with gastroesophageal reflux may cause

erosive lesions of the esophageal mucosa [13]. In 10 cases, surgeons performed simultaneous surgical interventions comprising the ‘neurological triad’: tracheostomy, endoscopic Nissen antireflux procedure, and gastrostomy.

The indication for performing simultaneous surgical treatment was a combination of the following factors:

- bulbar and pseudobulbar disorders;
- gastroesophageal reflux and lack of response to conservative therapy;
- previous and anticipated prolonged invasive respiratory therapy.

Conclusions

Advances in life-saving technologies have resulted in an increase in the number of palliative patients. Improved care methods for extremely premature infants have made a significant contribution to the increase in this patient population. The overwhelming majority of palliative infants present with multisystemic involvement. The provision of medical palliative care is a team-based, methodical, and exhausting process. The treatment of a palliative child in intensive care is only the first step on a path of challenging daily, often many years of, labor. The further development of diagnostic and treatment algorithms for this patient group is currently one of the priority tasks in healthcare.

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**COMBINED TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH DIAGNOSED
EUSTACHIAN TUBE DYSFUNCTION ASSOCIATED
WITH ADENOID HYPERTROPHY**

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Abstract. *Hypertrophy of the pharyngeal tonsil (adenoids) is one of the leading causes of persistent nasal obstruction in children and a frequent trigger of latent Eustachian (auditory) tube dysfunction. This combination often masquerades as “routine” adenoiditis: the child becomes accustomed to chronic nasal congestion, while a conductive component of hearing loss develops gradually — without prominent complaints — yet with an increased risk of delayed speech development and learning difficulties. This article presents the experience of observing 336 children aged 3–18 years with adenoids complicated by latent Eustachian tube dysfunction. The features of comprehensive management in this patient group were studied using an original patented combined treatment protocol. Analysis of the obtained data showed that the combined approach provides more effective nasopharyngeal sanitation, restoration of olfaction, and improvement of auditory function according to objective monitoring methods; the techniques are feasible in outpatient settings.*

Keywords: *adenoids; latent Eustachian tube dysfunction; laser therapy; ultraphonophoresis with Fermencol.*

References: *12 sources.*

Introduction Despite advances in diagnostic methods and treatment, the incidence of ENT diseases in children continues to increase. A substantial clinical risk is associated with delayed recognition of Eustachian (auditory) tube dysfunction, which may result in persistent hearing impairment and subsequently lead to speech development disorders and learning difficulties [3].

According to epidemiological data, hypertrophy of the Waldeyer–Pirogov lymphoid ring in children aged 3–7 years is observed in 6–12% of cases (up to 15% in some reports), most commonly due to enlargement of the pharyngeal tonsil, and it occupies an important place in the structure of acute and chronic pediatric ENT pathology [1,2]. Adenoid hypertrophy also remains clinically relevant in adults: in a subset of patients it causes persistent nasal obstruction, more often in men [5,6]. Acute conditions (sinusitis, otitis, adenoiditis) frequently become chronic and are accompanied by hearing loss; without timely diagnosis, this sustains Eustachian tube dysfunction and may progress to persistent hearing loss, potentially resulting in disability [4,7,9].

Hearing loss is classified as sensorineural or conductive; in pediatric practice, the conductive component predominates and is typically associated with middle-ear pathology in the setting of ENT infections [8,10]. Even moderate hearing loss can “steal” up to half of educational information, negatively affecting speech acquisition, behavior, and a child’s self-esteem. Therefore, children require regular follow-up with assessment of ENT status and hearing, and, when indicated, timely speech therapy intervention [11,12].

Aim of the study. To evaluate the effectiveness of comprehensive therapy — including pharmacotherapy, laser therapy, and low-frequency ultrasound — in children with adenoid hypertrophy complicated by latent Eustachian tube dysfunction.

Materials and Methods

A total of 336 children aged 3–18 years were observed (median age 7 years [Q1 5; Q3 10]) with grade I–III adenoid vegetations; the cohort included 168 boys and 168 girls. Treatment was provided at LLC “Medin” and LLC “DNK-Clinic” (Yaroslavl, Russia).

Study group allocation

Using simple randomization, children with adenoid vegetations were assigned to three groups according to the treatment regimen:

- Group 1 (control, n=100): standard pharmacotherapy in accordance with Russian Ministry of Health clinical guidelines (19.11.2021 No. 1968, as amended). The treatment algorithm included antibacterial therapy, anti-inflammatory agents, topical nasal decongestants and antiallergic medications, intranasal corticosteroids, antiviral drugs, immunomodulators, and analgesics for pronounced pain.

- Group 2 (comparative, n=118): pharmacotherapy combined with laser therapy according to the conventional protocol applied to the projection of the palatine tonsils and adenoid vegetations (1–2.5 min per field), pulse repetition rate

300–600 Hz, wavelength 0.85 μm , 2–5 W in pulsed mode (age-adjusted). The course comprised 10 daily sessions [Belova E. V., 2008].

- Group 3 (main, n=118): pharmacotherapy combined with a physiotherapy complex including laser therapy and endonasal ultraphonophoresis with Fermencol using an original patented method (Patent RU2798699C1, 23.06.2023). After nasal cavity sanitation, the patient was positioned supine; laser irradiation was performed according to the above protocol, followed by placement of a moistened turunda with Fermencol into the nasal cavity and endonasal low-frequency ultrasound exposure using the “Tonzillor-MM” device with the appropriate applicator in the minimal mode (40 μm). The turunda was then left in place for 20–30 min. The course comprised 10 daily sessions.

Diagnostic criteria and clinical assessment

Adenoid vegetations were considered the main cause of impaired nasal breathing in children and a trigger for Eustachian tube dysfunction in complicated adenoiditis. Medical history focused on the pattern of nasal obstruction, symptoms suggestive of obstructive sleep apnea, and associated clinical manifestations (predominantly nocturnal cough, hyponasal speech, articulation disorders, reduced olfaction, and dysphagia).

Objective examinations

Objective assessment included pharyngoscopy, anterior rhinoscopy, and nasopharyngeal endoscopy to determine the degree of hypertrophy and to evaluate the mucosal condition.

Tympanometry and instrumental assessment

Tympanometry assessment included changes in tympanometric pressure (daPa) and the proportion of patients with resolution of the conductive component after treatment.

Mucociliary transport function

Under normal conditions, the indicator dye appears in the nasopharynx within 15–18 min.

Additional diagnostic methods

Lateral-view nasopharyngeal radiography was performed from the age of 3 years. To monitor treatment effectiveness, noninvasive methods were preferred. The following were used for objective follow-up: assessment of olfactory function, evaluation of nasal mucociliary transport, tympanometry (before and after the treatment course), microbiological examination of nasal discharge with antibiotic susceptibility testing, immunological testing (before and after treatment), and rhinocytogram.

Statistical analysis

Quantitative variables are presented as median and interquartile range, Me [Q1; Q3]. For each patient, treatment effectiveness was assessed by calculating

individual changes: absolute change ($\Delta = \text{Post} - \text{Pre}$) and/or relative change ($\Delta\% = (\text{Post} - \text{Pre})/\text{Pre} \times 100\%$). Between-group comparisons of effect magnitude ($\Delta/\Delta\%$) across the three independent groups were performed using the Kruskal–Wallis test (H); differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. For categorical outcomes (e.g., “improvement/no improvement”), the Pearson χ^2 test was used to compare proportions between groups. When the “no improvement” category was absent in all groups (zero cells and no variability), χ^2 was not calculated because frequency comparisons under these conditions are non-informative and methodologically inappropriate.

Results

At the initial visit, the most frequent symptoms were hyponasal speech/voice timbre changes in 184 patients (54.8%), reduced olfaction in 157 (46.3%), predominantly nocturnal cough in 129 (38.4%), dysphagia in 78 (23.2%), and mucopurulent discharge in 74 (22.0%).

The distribution of children by adenoid hypertrophy grade was as follows: grade I-150 (44.6%), grade II-146 (43.4%), and grade III-40 (11.9%).

After treatment, improvement was observed in all groups, with the highest symptom resolution rates recorded in the combined-treatment group.

Restoration of auditory function

Before treatment, all patients demonstrated a conductive component of hearing loss. After the treatment course, hearing recovered in 89 (89.0%) children in the control group, 111 (94.1%) in the comparative group, and 114 (96.6%) in the main group. In the follow-up period (6 months), the outcomes remained at comparable levels: 89 (89.0%), 110 (93.2%), and 114 (96.6%), respectively.

Tympanometry

Assessment included changes in tympanometric pressure (daPa) and the proportion of patients with resolution of the conductive component after treatment. Resolution of the conductive component was documented in 88 (88.0%) patients in Group 1 (control), 111 (94.1%) in Group 2 (comparative), and 115 (97.4%) in Group 3 (main) (Table 1). Tympanometric pressure (daPa) was interpreted relative to the reference range (target value close to 0 daPa; acceptable deviations within ± 50 daPa). At 6-month follow-up, the most pronounced normalization of Eustachian tube ventilation function was observed in Group 3: a type A tympanogram was recorded in 116 (98.3%) children.

Two analytical approaches were used: (1) the Pearson χ^2 test for comparing proportions of “improvement/no improvement”; χ^2 was not calculated for this block because the “no improvement” category was absent in all groups (zero cells). (2) Between-group comparison of the magnitude of change in tympanometric pressure was performed using the Kruskal–Wallis test based on ranked values ($\Delta/\Delta\%$); the differences between groups were statistically

significant ($H=143.94$; $p<0.001$), with the maximal effect in the combined-treatment group.

Table 1. Changes in tympanometric pressure (daPa) and resolution of the conductive component

Parameter	Group 1 (control), n=100	Group 2 (comparative), n=118	Group 3 (main), n=118	Kruskal–Wallis H; p
Tympanometric pressure after treatment, daPa, Me [Q1; Q3]	-76 [-83; -70]	-40 [-48; -32]	-34 [-38; -24]	$H=143.94$; $p<0.001$

Mucociliary transport function

At baseline, children with adenoid pathology demonstrated slowed mucociliary clearance: the median transport time was 22 [20; 23] min. After treatment, mucociliary transport accelerated in all groups — to 18 [17; 19] min in Group 1, 17 [16; 18] min in Group 2, and 16 [16; 17] min in Group 3-indicating the most pronounced normalization with combined treatment.

When comparing the distribution of outcomes between groups using the Pearson χ^2 test for the “improvement/no improvement” proportions, statistically significant intergroup differences were found ($\chi^2=8.02$; $p=0.0181$). Comparison of effect magnitude between groups also showed significant differences by the Kruskal–Wallis test ($H=27.22$; $p<0.0001$).

Laboratory parameters

Complete blood count assessment revealed statistically significant reductions in leukocyte count and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), reflecting a decrease in the severity of latent inflammation (Table 2).

Table 2. Changes in blood laboratory parameters (leukocytes, ESR) before and after treatment in children with adenoid hypertrophy and latent Eustachian tube dysfunction

Parameter	Before treatment, Me [Q1; Q3]	Group 1 (after), Me [Q1; Q3]	Group 2 (after), Me [Q1; Q3]	Group 3 (after), Me [Q1; Q3]	Pearson χ^2 ; p	Kruskal–Wallis H; p
Leukocytes, $\times 10^9/L$	11.3 [10.3; 12.8]	9.7 [8.6; 10.6]	7.7 [6.9; 8.5]	6.0 [5.9; 6.1]	$\chi^2=57.84$; $p<0.0001$	$H=216.54$; $p<0.0001$
ESR, mm/h	14.3 [11.2; 17.0]	9.0 [8.4; 9.7]	7.2 [6.7; 7.9]	6.9 [6.4; 7.6]	$\chi^2=9.55$; $p=0.0084$	$H=158.19$; $p<0.0001$

Bacteriological findings

Bacteriological testing demonstrated not only a diverse pathogen spectrum in the nasal cavity of the examined children, but also a high prevalence of high-titer conditionally pathogenic flora (Table 3).

Table 3. Bacteriological examination (detection rate, %) before and after treatment and intergroup differences

Indicator	Before treatment, %	Group 1 (after), %	Group 2 (after), %	Group 3 (after), %	Kruskal–Wallis H; p
Staphylococcus aureus	35	7	5	5	H=211.02; p<0.0001
Staphylococcus haemolyticus	18	6	4	3	H=294.34; p<0.0001
<i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	12	10	7	7	H=210.96; p<0.0001
<i>Candida</i> spp.	4	3	1	1	H=210.35; p<0.0001
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	6	1	0	0	H=208.86; p<0.0001
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	7	4	3	3	H=204.22; p<0.0001
Conditionally pathogenic flora	$\geq 10^4$ — 18	$\geq 10^3$ — 69	$\geq 10^2$ — 80	$\geq 10^2$ — 81	H=281.88; p<0.0001

A

B

Figure 1. Rhinocytogram of Patient A., 6 years old, before (A) and after (B) treatment (Group 3, main group).

Rhinocytogram

At baseline, children with latent Eustachian tube dysfunction demonstrated marked leukocytosis on rhinocytogram-32 [28; 34] leukocytes per high-power field (HPF). After treatment, the parameter decreased in all groups: to 14 [12; 15] per HPF in the control group, 7 [6; 8] per HPF in the comparative group, and 3 [2; 4] per HPF in the main group, indicating the most pronounced anti-inflammatory response with the combined treatment using the original protocol (Fig. 1). The Pearson χ^2 test was not applied because no patients without improvement were observed (all cases were classified as “improvement”); therefore, comparison of frequencies was not applicable. Between-group differences in effect magnitude were statistically significant according to the Kruskal–Wallis test ($H=294.19$; $p<0.0001$).

During therapy, positive changes in resonatory function were also noted: resolution of hyponasality was recorded in 84% of children in Group 1, 93.2% in Group 2, and 95.7% in Group 3. In addition, 6 (5%) patients in Group 3 demonstrated restoration of voice timbre characteristics, consistent with improved nasal breathing and resonatory function.

Discussion

The present findings confirm that in children with adenoid hypertrophy, Eustachian tube dysfunction often follows a latent course and requires additional diagnostic assessment for detection (tympanometry, evaluation of mucociliary clearance, and rhinocytogram). In all groups, treatment was associated with regression of inflammatory manifestations and improvement of Eustachian tube ventilation–drainage function; however, the most pronounced and stable improvement was observed with the combined approach (pharmacotherapy plus a comprehensive physiotherapy protocol). This is consistent with superior reductions in tympanometric pressure, faster mucociliary clearance, and improved inflammatory marker profiles.

The advantage of the combined regimen is presumably related to a synergistic anti-inflammatory effect and an impact on tissue changes within the rhinosinotubar region: improvement of secretion rheology, normalization of mucociliary transport, and reduction of inflammatory infiltration. An important clinical outcome was a lower recurrence rate of Eustachian tube dysfunction during follow-up, suggesting that an organ-preserving strategy may be considered an alternative to early surgical intervention in selected patients, provided that strict dynamic monitoring is ensured.

Conclusions

1. Comprehensive treatment of children with adenoid hypertrophy complicated by Eustachian tube dysfunction provides greater clinical and functional effectiveness than standard pharmacotherapy, as confirmed by objective measures (tympanometry, mucociliary clearance, rhinocytogram, and laboratory inflammatory markers).

2. The most pronounced normalization of Eustachian tube ventilation and sustained resolution of the conductive component of hearing loss are achieved when pharmacotherapy is combined with a physiotherapy complex (laser therapy plus ultraphonophoresis with Fermencol), with persistence of the effect at follow-up and minimal recurrence.

3. Therapy is accompanied by decreased inflammatory activity (reduction in leukocytosis and ESR) and attenuation of inflammatory changes on rhinocytogram, reflecting regression of local inflammation in the rhinosinotubar zone.

4. Treatment accelerates ciliary transport and restores mucociliary clearance, which is important for nasopharyngeal sanitation and prevention of chronic disease.

5. The protocol is feasible in outpatient settings, well tolerated by children, and can be used both during exacerbations and in the inter-recurrence period, provided that objective efficacy monitoring is available.

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ULTRASOUND DIAGNOSTICS AND ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT FOR STRESS URINARY INCONTINENCE IN WOMEN

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Introduction

Changes in pelvic floor structures may contribute to the development of its dysfunction. Clinical manifestations of pelvic floor dysfunction may include stress urinary incontinence, chronic pelvic pain syndrome, sexual dysfunction, formation of cubital ulcers, infectious complications, and others [1]. Although not resulting in fatal outcomes or disabling complications, all of them significantly reduce a woman's quality of life, leading to the development of psycho-emotional disorders, social isolation, and so forth.[6]

The cause of stress urinary incontinence in women is dysfunction of the closure mechanism and innervation of the urethra and bladder neck, resulting from decreased pelvic floor muscle tone, prolapse of the anterior vaginal wall, and impaired tone of the bladder and urethral sphincters [2,3,7]. In most cases, the treatment of functional urinary incontinence involves surgical methods aimed at restoring the geometry of the urethrovesical segment [6]. One reason for the ineffectiveness of surgical treatment is the absence of a unified examination standard and standardized diagnostic algorithms for stress urinary incontinence in women. Consequently, following prolapse correction, patients often develop stress urinary incontinence, which diminishes quality of life and satisfaction with treatment outcomes.

Therefore, a detailed study of the morphological features of the female urethra and bladder neck that predispose to the development of functional urinary incontinence will enable the selection of the most appropriate treatment method for this condition and exclude cases of urinary incontinence associated with detrusor overactivity [6,7,8].

A known method for assessing the functional competence of the urethral sphincter in women is based on three-dimensional ultrasound examination of the urethra, during which the ratio of the cross-sectional area of the urethra in the proximal segment to the width of the urethral sphincter is determined [3]. It is emphasized that 3D/4D imaging modes allow volumetric reconstruction of all pelvic structures [5,6]. However, these methods require expensive equipment and trained personnel, which limits their widespread use and precludes their application as routine diagnostic techniques for pelvic organ dysfunction [5,8].

Materials and Methods

To investigate the potential of additional diagnostic methods for stress urinary incontinence, ultrasound examination (US) was performed on women without clinical symptoms of stress urinary incontinence and pelvic organ prolapse (control group) and on 23 patients with stress urinary incontinence (main group) before treatment and three months postoperatively. The clinical manifestations of stress urinary incontinence in patients were confirmed by data from comprehensive urodynamic investigations.

The ultrasound probe was placed in the vaginal vestibule at the level of the external urethral orifice with minimal pressure on the surrounding tissues to avoid voluntary deformation of the urethrovesical segment using an 11 MHz linear probe. The length of the urethra from the internal to the external orifice, as well as the length and width of the pseudoprostate, were measured, with determination of its area and calculation of the ultrasonographic index of the female urethra, defined as the ratio of the pseudoprostate area to the urethral length.

Results.

In women without stress urinary incontinence, the ultrasonographic index of the female urethra exceeded 9.0, with a mean value of 9.7. In all women with confirmed stress urinary incontinence, the ultrasonographic index of the female urethra was below 8.0, with a mean value of 7.1.

After surgical treatment for stress urinary incontinence, in 17 patients (73.9%), the ultrasonographic index of the female urethra increased to above 9.0, while in 6 patients (26.1%), it ranged from 8.0 to 9.0.

Thus, the effectiveness of surgical treatment for stress urinary incontinence in women can be considered proven when the ultrasonographic index of the female

urethra exceeds 9.0 postoperatively. When the ultrasonographic index of the female urethra ranges from 8.0 to 9.0, surgical treatment is deemed insufficiently effective, and these patients should be classified as at risk for recurrence of stress urinary incontinence.

Conclusions

Measurement of the ultrasonographic index of the female urethra is a highly informative diagnostic method for stress urinary incontinence in women. The advantages of the proposed method are its simplicity, associated with the accessibility and promptness of measurement tools, allowing its use for the diagnosis of stress urinary incontinence in women, assessment of the effectiveness of surgical treatment, and determination of the likelihood of recurrence of stress urinary incontinence after treatment.

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A MODERN VIEW ON THE ISSUES OF ETIOLOGY AND PATHOGENESIS OF CHRONIC GINGIVITIS

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Abstract. *Periodontal tissue diseases constitute one of the most serious issues in contemporary dentistry. A correlation exists between the quantity of dental deposits, individual oral hygiene, and the condition of periodontal tissues. Hygienic and therapeutic dental procedures will not be effective without cultivating patient responsibility for the health of oral tissues and organs. According to WHO data, approximately 45–50% of patients with chronic periodontal diseases do not adhere to medical recommendations, leading to serious medical and social consequences. The issue of compliance has intensified as periodontologists increasingly focus not only on symptom elimination but also on the prevention of periodontal disease exacerbations. Patient interest in ongoing dental treatment and adherence to the*

attending physician's recommendations improves the quality of care. Lack of or insufficient motivation and awareness, coupled with low compliance, exacerbate these outcomes and contribute to an increased prevalence of periodontal tissue diseases, leading to tooth loss and a decline in the patient's quality of life. A significant role in the pathogenetic mechanism of infectious processes in the oral cavity is attributed to the symbiosis of aerobic microorganisms, both among themselves and with anaerobic microorganisms. The patient's resistance to the pathological process of infectious origin is determined by the characteristics of their organs and tissues, circulatory system, lymphatic system, and regenerative capacity. Endotoxins increase the secretion of interleukins and gamma-interferon, activate platelets, and promote the release of neutrophils from bone marrow cells. A significant etiological factor in the development of chronic catarrhal gingivitis is the imbalance between the patient's defense mechanisms and the pathogenic bacteria originating from the oral cavity.

Keywords: *periodontal diseases, chronic catarrhal gingivitis, etiology, pathogenesis, compliance.*

Periodontal diseases represent one of the most serious challenges in modern dentistry, as there is an observed increase in prevalence among young individuals. A correlation exists between the quantity of dental deposits, individual oral hygiene, and the condition of periodontal tissues. Chronic diseases of internal organs and body systems, such as cardiovascular pathology, gastrointestinal disorders, and diabetes mellitus, undoubtedly exert a pathological effect on periodontal tissues [4].

The high prevalence of periodontal tissue diseases among patients engaged in harmful industries such as the production of non-ferrous and rare metals, the manufacture of powders from these metals, their processing under pressure, the production of abrasives, chemical power sources, and similar activities undoubtedly exerts a negative impact on periodontal tissues and overall health. Hygienic and therapeutic dental procedures will not be effective without cultivating patient responsibility for the health of oral tissues and organs. Simultaneously, the importance of patient compliance with the physician's prescriptions increases, as the prevention and treatment of periodontal diseases require extended durations, and interruption of such regimens results in exacerbation and increased severity [9].

According to WHO data, approximately 45–50% of patients with chronic periodontal diseases do not adhere to medical recommendations, leading to serious medical and social consequences. The patient's behavior concerning the correct intake of prescribed medications, accurate execution of prescribed non-pharmacological procedures, adherence to the prescribed diet, limitation of harmful habits, and the establishment of a healthy lifestyle is described by the term compliance, which literally means compliance, submissiveness, agreement, or approval. The issue of compliance has intensified as periodontologists increasingly focus not only

on symptom elimination but also on the prevention of periodontal disease exacerbations. Considerable importance is attributed to patients' adherence to medication regimens and dental recommendations [7].

Foreign literature assigns particular significance to positive compliance in periodontal practice. The effectiveness of therapeutic measures depends on several factors, foremost among them being patient compliance. A relationship has been observed between compliance and tooth loss due to periodontal pathology, tooth extractions for this reason, and disease remission. The formation of therapeutic cooperation is influenced by various factors: psychological characteristics of the patient; the internal disease representation (harmonious type of internal disease representation; hypognosia, anosognosia, hypernosognosia); personality traits of the patient (anxious and suspicious individuals; perseverative personalities; hypertimic patients; hypotimic character traits; schizoid personality traits) [5].

It has been established that, in young individuals, the main factors contributing to low compliance among dental patients are limited time availability, the high cost of dental procedures, fear, and distrust toward the physician. The primary reasons for visiting a dental prosthodontist are acute tooth pain beneath a fixed prosthesis or problems with previously fabricated removable dentures. It is considered that patients mainly postpone visits to the dental physician due to insufficient motivation to undergo dental treatment. The delayed presentation of patients with periodontal disease for dental treatment is primarily due to fear of procedures (57.9%), the high cost of services (33.5%), and lack of time (7.2%) [8].

To improve patient adherence to dental treatment, it is essential to motivate them, provide more detailed information on treatment methods and modalities, appropriately select specific medications, and align the physician's prescriptions with the patient's usual daily routine. The necessity of substantiating the prescription of a specific procedure or medicinal product is also essential [1].

Thus, patient interest in the dental treatment provided and adherence to the attending physician's prescriptions enhance the quality of care. Lack of or insufficient motivation and awareness, coupled with low compliance, exacerbate these outcomes and contribute to an increased prevalence of periodontal tissue diseases, leading to tooth loss and a decline in the patient's quality of life.

Gingivitis is a pathology directly associated with an imbalance between bacterial symbiosis and the tissues of the oral cavity. Among the etiological factors of periodontal tissue diseases, significant attention is given to dental plaque and calculus; to microorganisms and their metabolic products; the regulation of metabolic processes in the tissues of the oral cavity. Based on the analysis of the reviewed literature, it was established that researchers distinguish between non-mineralized and mineralized dental deposits. Non-mineralized dental deposits encompass dental plaque and soft dental biofilm. The formation of dental calculus occurs due to

mineral components such as calcium, phosphorus, carbonates, magnesium, and trace elements present in the oral fluid. The surface of dental calculus in contact with saliva is covered by bacterial plaque [2].

Experimental and clinical studies conducted by researchers have concluded that the causative agents of inflammatory processes in the oral cavity are aerobes and anaerobes. The proportion of aerobic microorganisms ranges from 91.7% to 94.8%. In chronic catarrhal gingivitis, the most frequently encountered microorganisms are *St. albus*, *St. aureus*, *Candida albicans*, and anaerobes. The majority is comprised of *Escherichia coli* — the intestinal bacillus. Aerobic microorganisms, consuming oxygen from the tissues, produce substances with strong reducing properties that stimulate growth. A significant role in the pathogenetic mechanism of infectious processes in the oral cavity is attributed to the symbiosis of aerobic microorganisms, both among themselves and with anaerobic microorganisms. Clinical research data indicate that the mechanism of such symbiosis is based on four components: the elimination of free oxygen, which is absorbed by aerobic microorganisms; the release by aerobic microorganisms of superoxide dismutase and catalase, which influences the survival of anaerobes; Secretion by aerobic microorganisms of biologically active substances that stimulate the growth of anaerobes; Provision by aerobic microorganisms of protective and oral factors that enhance the process of anaerobiosis [3].

An important aspect in the development of periodontal diseases is represented by factors such as: microbial adhesion to host epithelial cells; the adaptation factor; The penetrating factor, i.e., the ability of microorganisms to invade the cell (invasion); the ability to exert a damaging effect on target cells; the ability to diminish the immune defenses of the macroorganism; the ability to stimulate cytokine production; toxic substances produced by microorganisms of a specific nature; enzymes and metabolic products; non-specific products formed during the degradation of microorganisms. The patient's resistance to the pathological process of infectious origin is determined by the characteristics of their organs and tissues, circulatory system, lymphatic system, and regenerative capacity. Gram-positive microorganisms exhibit a mechanism of adhesion to the protein structures of the patient's organism, resulting in the formation of an extracellular glycocalyx that provides protection against antibiotics and biologically active substances of a specific nature. The binding of patient proteins with microorganisms influences receptors located on the surface of neutrophils, resulting in their activation. Microorganisms such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus albus* adversely affect the body by producing specific enzymes, including hyaluronidase, coagulase, and fibrinolysin, as well as toxins such as leukotoxin and dermonecrotic toxin. Chronic catarrhal gingivitis may be caused by streptococci. Their detrimental effect is associated with a broad spectrum of damaging factors. Following the binding of lipopolysaccharides from gram-negative microorganisms to host proteins, a lipid A-associated complex

is formed, serving as a mediator for the activation of leukocytes and macrophages. Moreover, endotoxins contribute to the increased secretion of interleukins and gamma-interferon, activate platelets, and facilitate the release of neutrophils from bone marrow cells [1].

An analysis of the literature review indicates that a significant etiological factor in the development of chronic catarrhal gingivitis is the imbalance between the patient's defensive mechanisms and the pathogenic bacteria originating from the oral cavity.

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EPIDEMIOLOGY OF EPILEPSY: GLOBAL TRENDS AND REGIONAL DATA FROM AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract.

Background: Epilepsy is a common chronic neurological disorder affecting over 50 million people worldwide. The prevalence and incidence of epilepsy vary significantly across regions, reflecting differences in risk factors, diagnostic capabilities, healthcare access, and social stigma.

Aim: To review global epidemiological trends of epilepsy and analyze regional data from Azerbaijan, including population-based data from the Mashtaga settlement in Baku.

Methods: A narrative review of international and national literature was performed. Regional epidemiological data were extracted from published studies conducted in Azerbaijan between 1984 and 2021, including population-based surveys and clinical-epidemiological investigations.

Results: Global epilepsy prevalence ranges from 4 to 10 per 1000, with higher rates in low- and middle-income countries. Incidence varies from 20 to 70 per 100,000 per year. In Azerbaijan, prevalence estimates range from 3.8 to 8 per 1000 and incidence from 24.5 to 83 per 100,000. A population-based study in Mashtaga (2016–2019) reported prevalence of 4.2 per 1000. Overall incidence ranged from 413.3 to 421.1 per 100,000, while primary incidence varied from 4.4 to 6.4 per 100,000. Prevalence was higher in males (4.9/1000) than in females (3.4/1000). Peak prevalence occurred in males aged 15–19 years (14.8/1000) and in females aged 40–49 years (5.7/1000).

Conclusion: Epidemiological data from Azerbaijan show a significant burden of epilepsy, influenced by social and medical factors such as consanguinity,

underreporting, and limited diagnostic resources. Improved registry systems, enhanced diagnostic capacity, and comprehensive public health strategies are essential to reduce the burden of epilepsy in Azerbaijan.

Keywords: *epilepsy, epidemiology, prevalence, incidence, Azerbaijan, Mashtaga, population-based study*

Introduction

Epilepsy is a chronic neurological disorder characterized by recurrent unprovoked seizures and affects people of all ages worldwide. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that more than 50 million people live with epilepsy globally, with a significant proportion residing in low- and middle-income countries where diagnostic and treatment resources are limited. Epidemiological studies of epilepsy are essential to inform healthcare planning, allocate resources, and develop effective preventive and therapeutic strategies. [1, 2, 3]

Global prevalence estimates of epilepsy range from 4 to 10 per 1000 population, while incidence varies from 20 to 70 per 100,000 per year. These variations are influenced by multiple factors including genetics, perinatal complications, infections, head trauma, cerebrovascular diseases, and social determinants such as access to healthcare and stigma. Studies from Europe and North America generally report lower prevalence and incidence rates compared to low-income regions, where higher rates are associated with infectious diseases, traumatic injuries, and limited medical care. [2, 8]

In Azerbaijan, the epidemiology of epilepsy has been investigated through several population-based and clinical studies. The prevalence of epilepsy in Azerbaijan has been reported to range between 3.8 and 8 per 1000, and incidence from 24.5 to 83 per 100,000. The country's epidemiological data are affected by regional differences in healthcare access, diagnostic practices, and social factors, including the prevalence of consanguineous marriages and stigma, which may lead to underreporting and misclassification of epilepsy cases. [10, 17]

This article provides a comprehensive review of global epidemiological trends in epilepsy and presents regional data from Azerbaijan, with special emphasis on population-based studies conducted in the Mashtaga settlement of Baku. These findings reflect both the burden of epilepsy and the challenges in accurate case identification and management in the region.

Methods

This study is a narrative review of published literature on the epidemiology of epilepsy globally and in Azerbaijan. Data were extracted from peer-reviewed journals, national reports, and academic publications. Regional data from Azerbaijan include population-based studies conducted in Baku and other regions, as

well as clinical-epidemiological investigations led by Professor Sh. I. Magalov and colleagues, and studies conducted by the author in Mashtaga settlement.

The regional epidemiological studies in Azerbaijan covered a period from 1984 to 2021 and involved various population groups, including children and adults. Data sources included medical records, local health registries, and field surveys. The Mashtaga population-based study (2016–2019) assessed prevalence and incidence rates, including primary incidence, and analyzed distribution by age and sex.

Results

Global Epidemiology of Epilepsy

Epilepsy is among the most common neurological disorders worldwide. Global prevalence ranges from 4 to 10 per 1000 population, with higher rates reported in low- and middle-income countries. Incidence varies widely from 20 to 70 per 100,000 per year. The Global Burden of Disease (GBD) study estimates that epilepsy is a major cause of disability-adjusted life years (DALYs), especially in younger populations. In high-income countries, incidence peaks in early childhood and older age due to cerebrovascular disease, whereas in low-income regions, infectious etiologies and traumatic injuries contribute significantly to incidence. [1–3]

Regional Epidemiology in Azerbaijan

In Azerbaijan, multiple studies have reported prevalence and incidence of epilepsy. From 2000 onwards, prevalence estimates ranged from 3.8 to 8 per 1000 and incidence from 24.5 to 83 per 100,000. According to WHO estimates, more than 60,000 people in Azerbaijan live with epilepsy.

A study conducted in Baku in 1984 reported prevalence of 2.8 per 1000 in the city and 2.0 per 1000 in rural areas. Later studies focusing on children aged 0–14 years reported incidence of 36.7 per 100,000 and prevalence of 1.3 per 1000. The onset of epilepsy was most common between 7 and 11 years. These indicators varied across regions, with incidence ranging from 0 to 96.4 per 100,000, likely reflecting underreporting, diagnostic limitations, and social stigma. In some regions, zero incidence likely indicated concealment of the disease by parents and lack of accurate case registration. [4, 5, 6, 7]

The high prevalence and incidence in Azerbaijan may be associated with consanguineous marriages. However, misclassification and overdiagnosis may occur, including cases of febrile seizures and situational seizures. In adolescent populations, epilepsy forms were registered as follows: idiopathic generalized epilepsy (44%), localization-related epilepsy (34%), symptomatic partial epilepsy (17.4%), epileptic encephalopathies (2.2%), and cryptogenic generalized epilepsy (2.3%). The diagnostic value of various EEG methods was also evaluated in the country.

Population-based Study in Mashtaga Settlement (2016–2019)

A population-based epidemiological study conducted in the Mashtaga settlement of Baku (2016–2019) reported a prevalence of epilepsy of 4.2 per 1000 population. During the study period, overall incidence ranged from 413.3 to 421.1 per 100,000 population, and primary incidence varied from 4.4 to 6.4 per 100,000 population. The prevalence was significantly higher in males (4.9/1000) compared to females (3.4/1000). The highest prevalence in males was observed in the 15–19 year age group (14.8/1000), while in females it was highest in the 40–49 year age group (5.7/1000). Incidence rates increased from early childhood to adolescence and decreased in older adults, particularly in the 60–69 year age group. [14–24]

Studies Led by Prof. Sh. I. Magalov

Over the last 20 years, under the leadership of Professor Sh. I. Magalov (deceased 2020), a series of studies were conducted to address epilepsy-related problems in Azerbaijan. The research covered epidemiological, nosological, and clinical structure of epilepsy, epilepsy in women, and quality of life of patients. Approximately one million people from different ethnic groups were included in these studies. They evaluated the existing registry system, diagnostic quality, treatment, and social support for patients with epilepsy in the country.

Discussion

The epidemiological profile of epilepsy in Azerbaijan shows a substantial burden comparable to other low- and middle-income countries. Prevalence and incidence estimates vary significantly across regions, reflecting differences in healthcare access, diagnostic capacity, and social factors. The reported high prevalence may be partly explained by genetic factors, including consanguinity, which is more common in certain regions of Azerbaijan. However, underreporting and diagnostic limitations likely contribute to variations in incidence and prevalence.

The Mashtaga population-based study provides more detailed epidemiological data compared to earlier studies, demonstrating high incidence and prevalence rates, particularly among adolescents. The higher prevalence in males may be related to occupational and behavioral risk factors, as well as differences in healthcare-seeking behavior. The peak prevalence in males aged 15–19 years may reflect a combination of genetic predisposition and early exposure to risk factors such as head trauma and perinatal complications. The peak prevalence in females aged 40–49 years may be associated with hormonal changes and comorbidities that affect seizure threshold.

The regional data also highlight the role of stigma and lack of awareness in epilepsy management. Zero incidence in some regions likely reflects concealment of the disease and inadequate registration systems. Improving case detection and establishing reliable registries are crucial for accurate epidemiological assessment.

The findings underscore the importance of comprehensive epilepsy care, including access to antiepileptic drugs (AEDs), psychological support, and rehabilitation

services. In Azerbaijan, patients receive free medical care and AEDs, as well as disability benefits. However, patient associations, epilepsy centers, and support organizations are still lacking, which limits public awareness and social support for patients and their families. [17]

Conclusion

Epilepsy remains a significant public health problem in Azerbaijan. Regional data indicate a high prevalence and incidence, influenced by genetic, social, and healthcare factors. Strengthening epilepsy registries, improving diagnostic capacity, and enhancing public awareness are essential to reduce the burden of epilepsy. [9–13, 25] Continued research and collaboration with international epilepsy organizations are needed to improve patient outcomes and quality of life.

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PHARMACEUTICAL INNOVATIONS IN THE TREATMENT OF PERIODONTITIS, AGGRAVATED BY THE IATROGENIC FACTOR

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Abstract. *Traditional methods of treating periodontitis, which are based on disinfection of root canals with irritants, are not always effective. Given the complex anatomical structure, the impossibility of mechanical and drug treatment of “blind” areas, the methods of periodontitis treatment are constantly being improved. The team of authors proposed a method of treatment using a bacteriophage preparation, which makes it possible to stop the cascade of pathogenetic inflammatory processes and restore bone tissue in the periradicular focus.*

Keywords: *endodontics, bacteriophages, iatrogenic errors, root canal treatment.*

The lack of positive dynamics and restoration of bone tissue in the periradicular region in the treatment of apical periodontitis is often associated with errors made during endodontic treatment. Fragmented instruments, perforations, undetected channels, insufficient tightness, homogeneity and depth of obturation, or, conversely, removal of the filling material beyond the apex in infected channels, can serve as a prerequisite for the occurrence of refractory inflammatory processes and lead to tooth extraction.

The complex morphology of the root canal system and the ability of microorganisms to form polybacterial intra- and extraradicular biofilms that colonize the isthmuses, trunk, lateral channels, and root surface significantly complicate disinfection of the canal-root system. *Enterococcus faecalis* is considered to be the main etiological factor in the formation of persistent infections and unsuccessful root canal treatment. A study using polymerase chain reaction analysis showed that the detection rate of *Enterococcus faecalis* is 79.5%, with 67.5% of primary infections and 89.6% of secondary infections localized in the root canal. [1]

In addition, by forming biofilms, this pathogen demonstrates resistance to attacks by the host's immune system, various substances, including drugs such as calcium hydroxide, sodium hypochlorite, antibiotics and hormonal agents, reducing their therapeutic effect. Therefore, *Enterococcus faecalis* should be considered as the primary target for therapeutic strategies in the context of root canal infection treatment. [2]

Traditional mechanical treatment and irrigation of the root canal are insufficient for full disinfection, thereby preventing the desired results from being achieved. Currently, biological control methods based on bacteriophages are becoming increasingly popular, which makes them a strategically important link for stopping the cascade of pathogenetic inflammatory processes.

Phages are viruses that have a unique ability to penetrate bacterial biofilms and cause damage to them. It has been proven that the effectiveness of phage therapy surpasses that of conventional antibiotics, especially in cases of infections caused by multidrug-resistant biofilms. [3]

Phages exhibit specificity against certain bacterial species or even individual strains, which makes them an ideal therapeutic option for the selective, targeted elimination of pathogens. [4]

Phages destroy bacterial biofilms through a variety of complex mechanisms:

Phages multiply inside bacterial cells, which leads to their lysis and the subsequent release of the progeny of phages, which gradually destroy biofilms.

Some phages infect dormant cells, remaining in a latent state until these cells are activated, subsequently lysing them.

Phages encode enzymes such as endolysins and choline, which destroy bacterial cell walls, promoting the release of viral particles and the destruction of

biofilm structures. In addition, depolymerases produced by phages destroy the extracellular polymer matrix in biofilms, destabilizing it, thereby providing deeper penetration and more effective elimination. [5]

Phages disrupt bacterial communication systems such as quorum sensors, thereby interfering with regulatory processes critical to biofilm maintenance and stability. Phage therapy is a promising alternative to traditional methods for combating *Enterococcus faecalis*. The action of bacteriophage-based agents is aimed at eliminating “etiologically significant” pathogens without affecting eukaryotic cells. Bacteriophages have a very favorable safety profile and phage therapy is usually associated with a low risk of adverse reactions and effects.

In order to cure chronic forms of apical periodontitis of single-root and multi-root teeth, burdened by bone destruction and iatrogenic factor, the team of authors proposed a treatment method that allows teeth to be preserved with a probability of 0.999 negative clinical statistics.

The operation to implement the method is performed in stages:

1. Computed tomography of the tooth area to be treated is performed.
2. Anesthesia and isolation of the working field are performed.
3. Mineralized and non-mineralized dental deposits are removed from the tooth to be treated, and the filling material is removed.
4. Preparation of the carious cavity is performed.
5. The working length of the root canals is measured with the Dentaport ZX OTR J.Morita apexlocator, which is fixed on the instrument with a silicone stopper using the Dentsply endodontic ruler, the mechanical treatment of the root canals is performed to create a ledge at least 1 mm from the end of the working length of the canal to ISO size 25.
6. Medical treatment of the tooth canals is carried out by alternating washing with irrigation solutions of 7% maleic acid and 1% sodium hypochlorite with an endodontic needle with lateral holes at a distance of less than 2 mm. the working length of the root canals, each portion is activated with an endoactivator.
7. Perform the final irrigation with saline solution.
8. Remove excess fluid from the channels with a single injection of a sterile paper pin of 6% taper of 30 Meta Biomed size.
9. Phagodont is introduced into the channels with a disposable syringe with a plastic cannula
10. Adapt it in the channels with the Endoactivator Dentsply.
11. Remove excess material with paper pins of 6% taper of 30 Meta Biomed size.
12. A passive adhesive material based on OpalDam Refill Ultradent methacrylate resin is applied to the channel mouths.
13. Cure it with a SmartLite Focus Dentsply polymerization lamp.
14. A sterile Teflon tape is placed on the bottom of the tooth cavity.

15. Close the tooth cavity with Temp It Spident material. The next visit is scheduled in 3 days, after the time has expired, the Temp It Spident material is removed with boron.

16. The Teflon tape and the passive adhesive material based on OpalDam Refill methacrylate resin are removed with tweezers.

17. Irrigation treatment with saline solution is carried out.

18. The channels are dried with sterile paper pins of 6% taper of 30 Meta Biomed size.

19. Verification is performed by the Thermafil Verifier system with the selection of the appropriate size of the obturator.

20. Apply the AH Plus Dentsply sealer into the channels.

21. Thermafil Dentsply Maillefer thermafiles are heated in a ThermaPrep 2 Oven and preheated into the channel until it stops, thereby performing a 3-dimensional obturation of the channels with filling of all the undercuts.

22. An adhesive protocol is carried out.

23. Restore the integrity of the tooth with Ceram filling material.X SphereTEC one, sanded, polished.

The proposed method has been implemented in practice and is confirmed by a clinical example.

Patient A complained of pain when biting on the tooth 1.5. Anamnesis: about 5 years ago, the tooth was treated for complicated caries, after which pain periodically began to appear when biting on the tooth. Over time, the intensity and duration of pain increased. Periodically (when pain occurs when biting on a tooth), the patient took antimicrobial drugs.

There is no concomitant pathology. The allergic history is not burdened.

At the time of treatment, there are no changes during external examination, the face is symmetrical, the mouth opens freely, noiselessly and painlessly, the skin is of normal color, the lymph nodes are not palpable.

In the oral cavity: Hygiene index 1.6 (satisfactory), periodontal Index 0.6 (initial and mild degree of periodontal pathology). The bite is orthognathic, the oral mucosa has no visible pathology.

Objectively: 1.5 there is filling material on the chewing surface. The crown part is not changed in color. In area 1.5, the mucosa from the buccal surface of the marginal and alveolar gums is hyperemic, edematous, bleeds when probed, and is slightly painful on palpation. The tooth is not mobile, percussion is painful. On CBCT, the contents of the palatine canal are homogeneous, up to the apical opening, radiologically the apex is outlined, buccal канал свободен от пломбиривочного материала. Деструкция костной ткани в перирадикулярной области, деструкция кортикальной пластинки в области 1.5, с тенденцией к распространению в области медиального корня 1.6.

После обследования поставлен диагноз: К 04.5 хронический апикальный периодонтит 1.5, обострение.

Согласно предложенному способу, пациентке проведено эндодонтическое лечение с восстановлением анатомической и функциональной целостности зуба.

The presented reformats show the results of a patient's examination using cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) with restored bone tissue 12 months after treatment.

Thus, this method allows for effective treatment of chronic forms of apical periodontitis of single-root and multi-root teeth burdened with an iatrogenic factor. As a result of treatment, it is possible not only to relieve the symptoms of the disease, but also to potentiate the restoration of bone tissue in the periradicular region.

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EXOCRINE FUNCTION OF THE PANCREAS DURING LONG-TERM USE OF NONSTEROIDAL ANTI-INFLAMMATORY DRUGS (EXPERIMENTAL STUDY)

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Abstract: *Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are widely used to treat acute and chronic pain associated with various diseases and pathological conditions. However, they can cause serious gastrointestinal, cardiovascular, and renal complications. In this study, using a mouse model, we demonstrated that long-term use of NSAIDs at maximum therapeutic doses can lead to decreased exocrine pancreatic function and, consequently, possible exocrine pancreatic insufficiency. This pharmacological effect is more pronounced with nonselective NSAIDs.*

Key words: *nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), celecoxib, ibuprofen, exocrine pancreatic function, pancreatic elastase-1, C57BL/6 laboratory mice.*

Introduction. Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are a group of drugs with different chemical structures that share a common mechanism of pharmacological action: blockade of the cyclooxygenase (COX) enzyme, reduction of prostaglandin synthesis, and the ability to exert analgesic, anti-inflammatory, and antipyretic effects [1]. Therefore, NSAIDs are one of the main treatment options for acute and chronic pain in a wide range of diseases and pathological conditions.

NSAIDs are divided into selective (s-NSAIDs) and non-selective (n-NSAIDs). The latter, in therapeutic doses, block both isoforms of cyclooxygenase (COX-1 and COX-2), which can cause serious complications in the gastrointestinal tract (GIT), cardiovascular system, and kidneys [2]. According to Russian and foreign researchers, the most common complications include erosions of the

gastrointestinal mucosa, bleeding, and dyspepsia; development or destabilization of arterial hypertension, arrhythmia, thromboembolic complications; edema, acute renal failure, and others [3–6]. Therefore, the development of methods and techniques for monitoring such complications is currently considered an important medical and social task. At the same time, scientific and epidemiological studies aimed at studying the real risk of developing serious complications while taking NSAIDs are either insufficient, or they are contradictory and not always objective.

The primary objective of this study was to investigate the pharmacological effects of NSAIDs on the levels of one of the main pancreatic proteolytic enzymes, elastase-1, and to evaluate the exocrine function of this organ.

Pancreatic elastase-1 in mammals and humans (EC 3.4.21.36) is an endopeptidase that catalyzes the hydrolysis of dietary proteins, particularly connective tissue elastin, denatured hemoglobin, and others [7]. This process is essential for the complete digestion of meat, since, for example, elastin is not hydrolyzed by trypsin and chymotrypsin. Furthermore, elastase-1 works in conjunction with bile acids, which also improves nutrient absorption. Elastase-1 is synthesized by pancreatic acinar cells and excreted as a zymogen into the duodenum, where it is converted into active elastase-1 by trypsin [7, 8].

Quantitative analysis of elastase-1 is a sensitive and specific laboratory test for assessing pancreatic function, allowing for the diagnosis of exocrine pancreatic insufficiency [9]. Exocrine pancreatic insufficiency can be caused by numerous diseases, including acute and chronic pancreatitis, diabetes mellitus, autoimmune diseases, chronic inflammatory bowel disease, cystic fibrosis, and others [10]. Furthermore, this syndrome can be drug-induced, for example, by antibiotics, anti-tuberculosis drugs, cytostatics, and narcotic analgesics [11].

Dysfunction of the pancreas manifests itself as nausea, diarrhea, increased gas formation, bloating, which can cause pain, intolerance to certain types of food, weight loss due to impaired digestion and absorption of nutrients, etc. [10, 11]. Therefore, identifying exocrine pancreatic insufficiency and correcting it in the early stages allows us to avoid significant metabolic disorders in the body.

Methods. This study was conducted using male inbred C57BL/6 mice obtained from the Laboratory Animal Nursery of the Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry of the Russian Academy of Sciences (Pushchino, Moscow Region). The animals were maintained under standard vivarium conditions at Petrozavodsk State University. The principal investigator and the researcher share the position of international and Russian Expert Councils on Bioethics regarding the conduct of scientific experiments using laboratory animals. Animal care, collection of biomaterial, and study of parameters are carried out in accordance with international and Russian requirements established by regulatory documents governing the principles and standards of humane treatment of animals, the safe conduct of voluntary

biomedical research, sanitary and epidemiological control, and environmental protection. Prior to the experiment, consent was obtained from the Joint Ethics Committee of Petrozavodsk State University and the V.A. Baranov Republican Hospital. The total number of animals used in the experiment was 30, which is the minimum but sufficient to obtain statistically significant results. The mice were 10–12 weeks old and weighed 20–24 g.

The study included three groups of laboratory animals:

Group 1 (10 mice) — control animals not receiving NSAIDs;

Group 2 (10 mice) — animals receiving a c-NSAID (celecoxib, 150 µg once daily);

Group 3 (10 mice) — animals receiving an n-NSAID (ibuprofen, 500 µg twice daily).

NSAIDs were added daily to the feed to the required concentration. The concentration was calculated based on the maximum daily dose of the specific NSAID recommended for use in the mouse model. Animals were maintained in individual cages for 30 days. Quantitative analysis of elastase-1 in the biomaterial was performed on days 15 and 30 of the experiment. Elastase-1 was analyzed in feces by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) using specific antibodies according to the manufacturer's protocol (Santa Cruz Biotechnology, USA), and in pancreatic extracts, the enzyme was assessed by Western blotting (Abcam, UK).

Statistical processing of the results was performed using StatGraphics Plus 5.0 software. Results were evaluated using nonparametric statistics using the Mann-Whitney U-test ($p < 0.05$).

Fig. 1. Levels of pancreatic elastase-1 in the feces of male C57BL/6 mice receiving NSAIDs for 15 and 30 days of the experiment (ELISA data)

* differences are significant ($p < 0.05$)

Results and Discussion. The results of the study showed that on the 15th day of the experiment, no significant changes in the level of coprological elastase-1 were observed in the groups of animals receiving NSAIDs (Fig. 1). The results of Western blotting also did not show any differences between the control and experimental groups of mice (Fig. 2). However, on the 30th day of the study, a significant decrease in the level of elastase-1 was recorded in the group of animals receiving ibuprofen both in feces (Fig. 1) and in pancreatic extracts (Fig. 2). In the group of mice receiving celecoxib, a tendency towards a decrease in elastase-1 in feces was noted ($0.05 < p < 0.08$). Nevertheless, according to Western blotting, the level of the enzyme in the pancreas remained stable (Fig. 2). Perhaps, a longer study is required in the case of celecoxib. No changes in weight were recorded in the animal groups during the entire period of the experiment.

The obtained study results demonstrate the importance and significance of assessing pancreatic elastase-1 levels during long-term NSAID use, as quantitative analysis of this enzyme allows for the diagnosis of the presence or absence of exocrine pancreatic dysfunction. The mechanism of such dysfunction can occur at various levels and affect both the functioning of the pancreas as a whole and the synthesis of individual enzymes in acinar cells, intracellular transport and accumulation in zymogen granules, extrusion into the duodenum, enzyme activation processes after extrusion, etc. [10, 11].

Fig. 2. Elastase-1 content in pancreatic extracts from male C57BL/6 mice treated with NSAIDs for 15 and 30 days of the experiment (Western blot data)

C — control; CC — celecoxib; I — ibuprofen

Our study data suggest that potential impairments may be related specifically to the formation of elastase-1 in pancreatic acinar cells due to prolonged drug exposure, but a more comprehensive and detailed study is needed to provide a definitive answer.

Thus, the results of this experimental study demonstrate that prolonged use of NSAIDs (over a month) at maximum therapeutic doses can lead to a decrease

in pancreatic exocrine function and, consequently, possible exocrine pancreatic insufficiency. This pharmacological effect is more pronounced with n-NSAIDs. Therefore, when prescribing NSAIDs, it is recommended to additionally include enzyme replacement therapy in the treatment regimen, along with dietary intervention and the cessation of unhealthy habits. Unfortunately, there are currently no enzymes containing elastase-1 among those currently used for digestive health. Therefore, research into elastase-1 may be of interest not only to medical professionals but also to drug development companies.

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**THE MORBIDITY OF THE BODY AS A REFLECTION OF
DISTURBANCES IN THE KEY BALANCE UNDER THE
INFLUENCE OF IRRATIONAL FOOD BEHAVIOR, WHICH IS
A CONSEQUENCE OF BODY EXPOSURE TO
DIFFERENT NON-INFECTION DISEASES IN SOCIETY**

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Abstract. *Disruption of the adrenal glands (paired endocrine glands) leads to symptoms such as nausea, swelling of the face, rapid weight gain or sudden weight loss, loss of strength, and increases the production of the hormone cortisol in the blood, which destroys protein tissue and increases the level of glucose in the blood. Increased intake of foods rich in carbohydrates leads to metabolic disorders. Nutrition, in addition to ensuring the biological well-being of a person, is also an indicator of his social identity, emotional state and cultural affiliation. In modern times, technological and social changes, especially the transition of social media to the center of life, have radically changed people's eating behavior. Media influence is especially stronger among the younger generation, because under the influence of social media, they are more sensitive to both body image and food choices.*

Key words: *eating disorder, nicotine, stress, treatment*

Introduction. Alcohol and smoking abuse, including passive smoking, have a toxic effect on the liver [1,16,19]. Considering the fact that cholesterol is synthesized in the body in the liver, the main prerequisite for the accumulation of

excess cholesterol is an unbalanced diet, when excess amounts of fat enter the body [2–5,22,25]. Also, diabetes mellitus — high levels of glucose in the blood provokes the production of bad cholesterol. Frequent stressful situations lead to the consumption of nicotine, which, entering the bloodstream, irritates the adrenal glands, which in turn release the hormone adrenaline into the blood, which constricts blood vessels and increases blood pressure, causing persistent changes in the vascular walls [6–10,27,29]. Disruption of the adrenal glands (paired endocrine glands) leads to symptoms such as nausea, swelling of the face, rapid weight gain or sudden weight loss, loss of strength, and increases the production of the hormone cortisol in the blood, which destroys protein tissue and increases the level of glucose in the blood [11–16,31]. Increased intake of foods rich in carbohydrates leads to metabolic disorders. Cellular susceptibility to the most important hormone, insulin, which is responsible for the breakdown of glucose, decreases. With excess weight, the body is forced to intensively produce insulin, which leads to an excess of insulin in the blood, resulting in increased resistance of peripheral tissues to it [17–22,34,39,41]. Nutrition, in addition to ensuring the biological well-being of a person, is also an indicator of his social identity, emotional state and cultural affiliation. In modern times, technological and social changes, especially the transition of social media to the center of life, have radically changed people’s eating behavior. Media influence is especially stronger among the younger generation, because under the influence of social media, they are more sensitive to both body image and food choices [23–27]. People often try to compensate for negative emotions — feelings of stress, loneliness, tension or anxiety — with food. This situation is called “emotional eating”. time spent on social media increases impulsivity, while impulsivity weakens self-control over eating, resulting in emotional eating behavior in individuals. This mechanism works as a “stress-impulsivity-craving” chain and can be one of the main targets of psychological interventions [28,29–33]. Early detection of eating disorder can help to make the treatment more effective, prevent the chronicity of the disease and reduce the risk of complications [34–36]. Schools, universities, health care facilities, sports clubs, beauty salons, or other public places may conduct screening programs for the detection of eating disorders. Screening programs can be implemented through questionnaires, interviews, or physical examinations used to identify risk factors, symptoms, or behaviors associated with eating disorders [37]. Eating disorders should include treatment of eating disorders, psychological interventions, medical treatment, nutritional counseling, drug therapy, or other support services. Multidisciplinary treatment can help patients restore their physical and psychological health, normalize eating behaviors, create a positive attitude about body image, regulate their emotions, cope with stress, improve their social relationships, and improve their quality of

life [38–40]. People with eating disorders need ongoing support after treatment. Support groups, online forums, mentoring programs, phone lines, social media groups, or other support services can also provide support to patients after treatment. Ongoing support can help patients maintain treatment outcomes, prevent relapses, and improve quality of life. Food advertising has a significant influence on people's eating behavior [41]. Regulation of food advertising can help people make healthy eating choices. This can be done by banning unhealthy food advertising, increasing healthy food advertising, preventing misleading information in food advertising, limiting food advertising directed at children, or preventing negative body image messages in food advertising [42,43].

Purpose of work. The purpose of this study is to determine the structure of social and psychological factors that shape eating behaviors in Azerbaijan. Using the method of factor analysis, the research aims to evaluate the interrelationships of various factors (emotional state, social influence, perceived stress, impulsivity, body image) that influence eating behaviors.

Materials and methods. The purpose of this study is to determine the factors that shape eating behavior in Azerbaijan and to provide structuring of emotional, social and environmental factors affecting the eating behavior of individuals through factor analysis. The research model was built on the basis of previous international studies, but adapted to take into account local cultural and social characteristics. The main hypothesis of the study is that the factors affecting eating behavior are grouped in four main directions: — healthy eating behavior: balanced diet, use of fruits and vegetables, water intake, — harmful habits: fast-food consumption, sugary drinks, eating at night, — environmental influence: social media, advertisements, family and friend influence, — psychological and emotional factors: stress, emotional eating, self-punishment. 320 respondents participated in the study. The participants were in the age range of 18–65, from different socio-economic classes, 61% were women, 39% were men. Participants were randomly selected and their anonymity was fully protected. Consent was obtained from the respondents to use the data for scientific purposes. This methodological approach was implemented in accordance with accepted ethical principles in psychological and behavioral research (APA, 2020). The survey form consisted of 34 items and was assessed on a 5-point Likert scale (1 — completely disagree, 5 — completely agree). The Dutch Eating Behavior Questionnaire (DEBQ), an internationally validated questionnaire, was used to measure emotional, externalizing, and restrictive eating behaviors. The reliability of each section was checked with Cronbach's alpha coefficient and the overall result was $\alpha = 0.87$, which demonstrates high internal consistency. Collected data were analyzed using SPSS 25 and Python (NumPy, pandas, factor_analyzer libraries). Before starting the analysis, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's tests of

sphericity were performed to assess the consistency of the data. The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) method was used for factor extraction, and the Varimax method was used for rotation. Items with factor loadings above 0.50 were taken as the basis. 65.7% of the total variation was explained by four main factors. Additionally, a heatmap was developed and presented using Python for visual analysis of intervariable relationships. The map showed the intensity of factor loadings with color tones ranging from -1.0 to +1.0. Red areas indicate positive and blue areas indicate negative correlation. Thus, as a result of factor analysis, the structural model of social and psychological factors that shape eating behavior in Azerbaijan has been confirmed statistically and theoretically.

Results and discussion. The food environment has a significant impact on people's eating behavior. The food environment includes the physical, economic, social, and cultural factors that facilitate or complicate people's dietary choices. Limited access to healthy foods, expensive, unavailable, poor quality, or unhealthy foods being more accessible, cheaper, more attractive, and more advertised may cause people to choose unhealthy foods, not develop healthy eating habits, and increase the risk of eating disordered behaviors. The study will examine variables such as social media influence, emotional state, perceived stress, impulsivity, and body image and evaluate their interactions. This will create an important scientific basis for the protection of public health and psychological well-being, both theoretically and practically. The results showed that (Tab.1), the KMO coefficient was 0.84, which indicates that the data is fully compatible with the factor analysis ($KMO \geq 0.80$ is a high level of compatibility). During the analysis, the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) method was applied, and the rotation process was carried out with the Varimax method. The purpose of this method is to obtain more clear and interpretable loadings between the factors. applied and four main factors were identified. Together, these four factors explained 65.7% of the total variance, indicating that social and psychological factors play an important role in shaping eating behaviors, psychological factor (23.9%), healthy eating behavior (18.8%), unhealthy eating habits (12.5%), and the role of environmental and social influence (10.5%). Among all participants, 252 people (84%) reported at least one symptom of disordered eating behavior (Tab.2). The most common manifestations were a feeling of discomfort after eating and a conscious restriction of the diet. 48 participants (16%) had no signs of malnutrition. According to (Tab.3), 80% of participants exposed to social media reported altered eating preferences, versus 26% among those not influenced ($\chi^2=22.7$; $p<0.001$).

Table 1. Factor Explanation and Load

Factor	Factor Loading
Psychological Factors	0.70–0.83
Healthy Eating	0.74–0.81
Harmful Habits	0.72–0.83
Social Influence	0.71–0.80

Table 2. Prevalence of symptoms of disordered eating behavior (n = 320)

Symptom	Quantity (n)	% of participants
Feeling discomfort after eating	127	39,6
Conscious restriction of diet	95	29,7
Episodes of binge eating	32	10
Provoked vomiting	18	5,6
No symptoms	48	15

Table 3. Association Between Social Media Influence and Altered Eating Preferences

	Altered Eating Preferences	No Change in Preferences	Total
Influenced by Social Media	64 (48.2)	16 (31.8)	80
Not Influenced	5 (20.8)	15 (–0.8)	20
Total	69	31	100

Note: Expected values under the null hypothesis of independence are shown in parentheses

Conclusion. The four main factors identified in the factorial structure — psychological factors, social influence, healthy eating behavior and unhealthy eating habits — are consistent with the international literature and reveal new nuances relevant to the local social context. The results confirmed the relationship between emotional eating and stress. Individuals’ emotional states, especially stress and loneliness, have a direct impact on eating behavior. One of the important results of the study is that the social media factor has an impact on both psychological and behavioral levels. A large proportion of respondents (68%) reported that they follow food-related content on social media and that, these shares change their appetite and food choices. Research results show that social pressures related to body image are also an important factor in the formation of eating behaviors in Azerbaijan. It has been observed that propaganda about the body ideal in social media and social comparisons in the circle of friends cause dissatisfaction with their

appearance in individuals. Although the vast majority of respondents accepted the importance of healthy eating, it was observed that the trend towards fast food and sweet foods continued at the level of actual behavior. Although people know the benefits of healthy eating, daily stress and social influences prevent them from turning this knowledge into a practical habit. At the same time, some individuals try to balance this dissonance with compensatory strategies — exercise, mindful eating, and emotional regulation techniques. It is clearly observed that food has not only a biological but also a social function in Azerbaijani culture. The family table and communal eating rituals strengthen people’s emotional connections, but also create pressures of social norms. Therefore, social and emotional factors have both protective and risk-generating effects on eating behavior. For example, while family meals foster social bonding, at the same time, growing portion sizes and the social rule of “not eating alone” can lead to overeating. The results of this study have important implications for public health, education, and psychological intervention programs. Promoting body positivity and healthy eating habits on social media platforms, implementing emotional regulation and mindful eating training at the school and university level, as well as psychological education programs on stress management can play an important role in improving eating behaviors. Thus, the factor analysis shows that eating behaviors in Azerbaijan are formed on the basis of four main structural factors: psychological factors, healthy eating behavior, unhealthy eating habits and social influence. This structural model is consistent with international research and is shaped by local cultural factors (family, social norms, social media). At the same time, the results of the heat map analysis show that psychological factors and social influence mutually reinforce each other and act as one of the main mechanisms of emotional eating. A positive environment related to healthy nutrition and body image should be created in schools. This environment can help students develop healthy eating habits, resist body image pressures, increase self-esteem, maintain emotional health, develop social skills, and reduce the risk of eating disordered behaviors. Creating an environment can be done through cafeterias that offer healthy foods, posters that spread positive body image messages, body positivity events, or other initiatives.

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THE OCCURRENCE OF DENTURE STOMATITIS DURING THE ADAPTATION STAGE TO REMOVABLE DENTURES

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Abstract. *Denture stomatitis often occurs in patients using removable orthopedic prostheses and may present either as an acute or chronic condition (with periods of exacerbation and remission). Numerous reports in the literature indicate that mechanical, thermal, and toxic-allergic irritants can affect the oral mucosa, especially in cases of disruption of the microocenosis and immunological defense. The importance and relevance of conducting studies on the parameters of homeostasis and biocenosis of the oral cavity in denture stomatitis are indisputable. Removable plate dentures create a favorable environment for the accumulation of microflora and the emergence of microorganisms that are normally absent: Escherichia coli — from 10 to 63%, pathogenic Staphylococcus — from 10 to 22%, yeast-like fungi — from 10 to 34%, Enterococcus — up to 22%. Biofilm formation is a complex, multi-stage process that occurs without the necessity of creating special conditions for bacteria. For this, the presence of a dense and moist surface is sufficient, whether of organic or inorganic origin.*

Microorganisms such as D. pneumoniae, Streptococcus mills, Streptococcus salivarius, Streptococcus faecalis, Klebsiella, and Fusospirochetes have been identified in denture plaque. The most significant changes in microbial flora during the use of removable dentures are observed in species of Neisseria, Bacillus, Streptococcus, Leptotrix, Candida. by applying various physical, chemical, and biological methods. Denture stomatitis is an inflammatory process of the oral mucosa caused by the use of a dental prosthesis. It may have various etiologies: traumatic, toxic, allergic, or induced by physical factors. Depending on the presence of the pathological process, catarrhal (serous), erosive, ulcerative, ulceronecrotic, and hyperplastic forms of stomatitis are distinguished.

Keywords: *denture stomatitis, oral microflora, biofilm, removable dental prostheses.*

Studies conducted by researchers indicate that inadequate hygiene of removable dentures promotes the proliferation of opportunistic and pathogenic microorganisms on the oral mucosa, potentially leading to the development of various pathological changes both locally and systemically. Denture stomatitis often occurs in patients using removable orthopedic prostheses and may present either as an acute or chronic condition (with periods of exacerbation and remission). Clinical manifestations include erosive-ulcerative, ulceronecrotic, and hyperplastic forms. The causes of denture stomatitis in the dental arch may be local factors originating from the base of the removable denture, as well as from the material of which it is made [9].

The literature contains numerous reports indicating that mechanical, thermal, and toxico-allergic irritants can affect the oral mucosa, particularly when disturbances of the microbocenosis and immunological defense occur. Together, these factors determine the pathogenesis of the development of the pathology. The mucosal reaction to removable orthopedic dental prostheses may depend on the individual characteristics of the denture-bearing area. It is recommended to differentiate between true inflammation of the mucous membrane and the so-called 'psychological intolerance to the dental prosthesis,' or false inflammation. In false inflammation, subjective sensations of burning and paresthesia occur, whereas in true inflammation, catarrhal inflammation is observed, accompanied by erosions or pressure ulcers. These manifestations can lead to disorders of hemocirculation and trophic disturbances in the mucous membrane of the denture-bearing area and adjacent regions of the oral cavity. At the biochemical level, enhanced lipid peroxidation processes and altered enzyme activity in the oral fluid are observed within the oral tissues. Chronic inflammation and destructive changes in the tissues of the denture-bearing area have a detrimental effect on the organism as a whole. An insufficient level of oral hygiene disrupts homeostasis and biocenosis, activating conditionally pathogenic and pathogenic microflora, thereby increasing its pathological impact

on the severity and characteristics of the inflammatory process in the tissues of the denture-bearing area [2].

The importance and relevance of conducting studies on the parameters of homeostasis and biocenosis of the oral cavity in denture stomatitis are indisputable. Restoring the fundamental processes occurring in the oral cavity plays a key role in the successful adaptation to removable orthopedic constructions, their retention and stabilization, as well as in preventing the development of denture stomatitis. The oral cavity is an environment where complex ecosystems can develop. The installation of removable dental prostheses, following partial or complete tooth loss, can lead to alterations in the diversity of microbial communities. Biofilms on the surfaces of materials used for the fabrication of dental prostheses can significantly affect the mechanical and aesthetic properties of the material itself and cause local and systemic diseases in patients using removable dentures [5].

Removable plate dentures create a favorable environment for the accumulation of microflora and the emergence of microorganisms that are normally absent: *Escherichia coli* — from 10 to 63 %, pathogenic *Staphylococcus* — from 10 to 22 %, yeast-like fungi — from 10 to 34 %, *Enterococcus* — up to 22 %. The presence of removable orthopedic devices in the oral cavity often contributes to the development and persistence of dysbiosis, leading to pathological processes on the mucous membrane of the tongue, cheeks, and lips, manifested as erosions, hyperplasia, and hyperkeratosis. Disruption of the microbial balance in the oral cavity in favor of pathogenic microbiota species contributes to the development of inflammation of the oral mucosa. This may be facilitated by trauma to the mucous membrane resulting from insufficient fixation of the removable denture prosthesis. Some opportunistic pathogenic microorganisms residing in the oral cavity as biofilms possess pathogenic potential (including adhesive activity, colonization ability, and antibiotic resistance) and are protected from adverse environmental factors [3].

Dysbiosis of the microbiome, caused by significant alterations in its species and quantitative composition, leads to an increase in pathogenic microorganisms, the development of an inflammatory process following prosthetic treatment, and the subsequent formation of a chronic infection in the oral cavity. Particular attention should be given to studying the microbiological characteristics of the prosthesis surface, where colonization by the oral microbiome occurs at various stages of orthopedic rehabilitation. More than 700 species of microorganisms inhabit the oral cavity, including representatives of facultative and obligate microflora. These microorganisms exist as free-floating cells or form a bacterial biofilm, known as a microbial conglomerate. Each surface of the oral cavity possesses its own unique biofilm composition. Different species of microorganisms colonizing various surfaces utilize distinct receptors and adhesion molecules to form the biofilm. The process of biofilm formation can be divided into four phases. The initial layer that forms on

the tooth surface and leads to the development of dental plaque is the “acquired pellicle” or pellicle. This process begins just a few seconds after tooth brushing, when a thin layer forms on the tooth surface, followed by the initial attachment of the first colonizers of the biofilm. The primary colonizers are species of *Streptococcus* and *Actinomyces*, which are gram-positive facultative bacteria. Adhesin receptors located on the surface of primary colonizers interact with proline-rich proteins of the pellicle. This interaction leads to the formation of receptor structures known as ‘cryptitopes,’ which facilitate coaggregation. Over time, dental plaque accumulates on the surface of teeth (or removable dentures), leading to oxygen depletion in the surrounding environment, thereby promoting colonization by anaerobic bacteria. The connecting link between them is the species *Fusobacterium*, which plays a key role as both a primary and secondary colonizer in the development of periodontal diseases. The gradual transition of conditions from aerobic to anaerobic facilitates disease progression. Microorganisms in the microbial biofilm aggregate with the aid of a protective adhesive lipopolysaccharide matrix that they produce [8].

Microorganisms such as *D. pneumoniae*, *Streptococcus* mills, *Streptococcus salivarius*, *Streptococcus faecialis*, *Klebsiella*, and *Fusospirochetes* have been identified in denture plaque. The most significant changes in microbial flora during the use of removable dentures are observed in species of *Neisseria*, *Bacillus*, *Streptococcus*, *Leptotrix*, *Candida*. Studies demonstrate that biofilm cultures exhibit greater antibacterial resistance compared to planktonic cultures. This tendency is noted with respect to the body’s protective immune factors and other external aggression factors. Effective biofilm disruption strategies include preventing bacterial adhesion to surfaces, reducing polysaccharide production, and disrupting intercellular connections through various physical, chemical, and biological methods [1].

The fabrication of dental prostheses is performed using acrylic plastics in 72% of cases. These materials are favored due to their availability, low cost, aesthetic appearance, and straightforward manufacturing technology. They do not require specialized or expensive equipment and are easily repairable and relineable [7].

In the development of denture stomatitis, considerable attention is attributed to the chemical-toxic effects of acrylic plastics, particularly the residual monomer, the content of which can reach 1% or more. According to experts, up to 16.0 mg/l of monomer is leached from the base material samples within 24 hours. During the subsequent four days, its migration further increases by 11.0 mg/l, followed by a sharp decline. Analysis of the literature data supports the assertion that the monomer, as a component of polymethyl methacrylate, is a highly toxic substance and allergen. In some cases, it may cause allergic reactions; in others, toxic stomatitis. It is very difficult to differentiate these conditions in clinical practice. Allergic reactions manifesting as allergic stomatitis during denture usage belong to contact hypersensitivity reactions of the delayed type. Studies indicate that

allergic intolerance to denture materials increases annually. Currently, according to researchers, it reaches 40% [10].

The literature contains multiple reports of a high incidence of denture stomatitis. This underscores the importance of the issue of prosthesis material intolerance from a medico-social standpoint and the significance of developing modern methods for its prevention. To achieve this goal, further research is necessary, aimed at developing innovative approaches to predicting denture stomatitis, based on a profound understanding of its causes and mechanisms of development. Denture stomatitis is known to be an inflammatory process of the oral mucosa caused by the use of a dental prosthesis. They may have various etiologies: traumatic, toxic, allergic, or induced by physical factors [4].

The mechanical effect of the removable prosthetic design involves increased pressure on the tissues of the denture-bearing area. Even with a correctly designed denture, masticatory pressure can cause changes in the tissues of the denture-bearing area, leading to impaired blood circulation. During adaptation to partial removable dentures, patients may experience venous stasis in the microcirculatory vessels of the mucous membrane, which may progressively intensify. It should be noted that dental materials can release both unaltered components and their derivatives into the oral cavity, which may exert a direct toxic effect on the cells of the oral mucosa and gingiva [6].

Analysis of the literature data has shown that allergic reactions may be caused not only by allergens but also by other side effects. For example, trauma from a removable denture during mastication may lead to inflammation of the denture-bearing mucosa. This can increase the permeability of the vascular wall, disrupt redox processes, and induce acidosis. As a result of this process, substances from the oral cavity may penetrate the mucous membrane, lymph, and bloodstream, facilitating sensitization of the organism. Following prosthetic treatment, a shift in saliva pH toward increased acidity can cause corrosion of prosthetic structures, as well as the release of antigens into saliva and onto the mucous membrane [12].

Allergic reactions to denture materials may play a key role in the development of inflammation of the oral mucosa. These reactions may occur as independent factors contributing to denture stomatitis, as well as accompany other side effects of orthopedic treatment or be their consequence. Therefore, particular attention is currently given to allergic reactions to materials used in denture fabrication. It should be noted that among denture materials, acrylates are among the most undesirable with respect to the potential development of side effects, including allergic inflammatory reactions [10].

Despite this, acrylic resins remain in demand in prosthetic dentistry due to their availability, low cost, attractive appearance, advanced technologies, and ease of fabrication. They are widely used for the fabrication of removable prostheses and maintain leading positions in the market. However, the use of removable plate

dentures in the oral cavity negatively affects the overall resilience of the organism: during the development of inflammatory processes, there is a significant reduction in the body's adaptive capacity, as well as disruption of immune balance parameters. Patients may experience increased sensitivity to denture base acrylic resins; however, allergic reactions are rare, and most cases of denture stomatitis today have other etiologies [12].

Thus, analysis of the literature permits the conclusion that the tissues of the denture-bearing area respond to the impact of dental materials by developing diverse compensatory-adaptive reactions aimed at restoring and maintaining homeostasis. The issue of patient adaptation to removable plate dentures is a complex challenge that cannot always be completely resolved. Disturbances in the adaptation process to removable dentures frequently result in patients discontinuing their use and, consequently, a reduction in their quality of life. Therefore, further investigation into the specific effects of removable plate dentures on the oral mucosa is deemed important.

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RATIONAL THERAPY IN WOMEN WITH ANEMIC SYNDROME AND INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF THE PELVIC ORGANS

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Abstract. *Anemia is one of the most common hematological disorders, significantly reducing quality of life and aggravating the severity of concomitant diseases [1]. In women of reproductive age, anemic syndrome most commonly manifests as iron-deficiency anemia (IDA) during pregnancy, childbirth, and inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs. According to WHO estimates, more than 3.6 billion people worldwide suffer from IDA [2]. This condition is observed not only in obstetric and gynecological practice but also in therapeutic, oncological, hematological, anesthesiological, and other specialties, and always requires timely diagnosis and treatment.*

Keywords: *women, reproductive age, anemic syndrome, inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs.*

According to the authors Stuklov N. I. and Shikh E. V., IDA occurs in 50–60% of cases among women of reproductive age [3]. In clinical practice, anemia is diagnosed by obstetrician-gynecologists in patients with menstrual cycle disorders presenting as heavy menstruation lasting more than 8 days, blood loss exceeding 80 ml during a single day, cycle duration shorter than 24 days or longer than 38 days, abnormal uterine bleeding, malignant and benign neoplasms of the pelvic organs, endometrial hyperplasia, pregnancy, and inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs [4, 5]. Anemia

occurring within the context of inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs necessitates a detailed and proficient approach for its correction [6]; the development of anemia in these conditions may be associated with menstrual cycle disturbances such as menorrhagia or with immunosuppression due to inflammation [7].

A review of literature sources on Elibrary, PubMed, Cyberleninka, and abstracts of PhD and doctoral dissertations over the past 20 years reveals a limited body of work dedicated to the study of anemia in inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs. Authors Hayatova Z. B. [8], Vinogradova O. P. [9], and Selikhova M. S. [7] describe staged treatment approaches, where the first stage is anti-inflammatory therapy, followed by anti-anemic therapy.

The selection of anti-anemic agents for the treatment of IDA is extensive. These agents are predominantly represented by preparations for oral and parenteral administration. Modern iron-containing drugs include either salts of ferrous (divalent) iron or compounds of ferric (trivalent) iron [10]. Divalent formulations contain salts of ferrous (divalent) iron or compounds of ferric (trivalent) iron. Divalent iron is more commonly used in oral iron preparations than ferric iron [11]. Ferric iron is 3–4 times less bioavailable than divalent iron because it poorly dissolves in alkaline environments and must be converted to divalent iron for absorption in the body. Iron preparations may be presented in tablet form, as capsules, powders, chewable tablets, and liquid formulations. There are also iron-containing complex preparations, such as iron hydroxide in the form of a polymaltose complex. Additionally, there are combined agents containing complexes comprising iron or iron salts in combination with various vitamins, such as ascorbic or folic acid [12]. Currently, newer compounds are utilized: iron sucrosomes, ferric hydroxide adipate, iron chelate complexes with aminoxyates, and iron succinate with protein [13]. Russian researchers are developing a novel pharmaceutical formulation containing iron (II) sulfate, potassium-sodium iron hexacyanoferrate, potassium sulfate, and microcellulose [14]; further clinical trials on efficacy and safety are necessary for full implementation.

Parenteral formulations should be used exclusively in special cases when patients exhibit poor tolerance, treatment failure with oral iron preparations, or have contraindications such as impaired intestinal absorption in severe enteritis, extensive small intestine resection, or inability to take oral iron supplements [15]. Intramuscular iron preparations demonstrate extremely low efficacy and frequently result in the formation of persistent, painful infiltrates at the injection site. In some cases, infiltrates may form abscesses [10].

Anti-anemic agents are prescribed for an average duration of 1 to 3 months. Monitoring of the clinical blood test is conducted after 7–10 days of treatment, during which a reticulocyte crisis is observed, with reticulocytes increasing from 2–3% to 20–30% compared to the baseline peripheral blood analysis prior to initiation of iron therapy; after 1 month of therapy, hemoglobin rises by 10 g/L and

hematocrit by 3%, confirming the diagnosis of IDA. Iron preparations are continued even after normalization of the blood profile to overcome tissue sideropenia and replenish iron stores. The target hemoglobin level should be 120 g/L. and the ferritin level should be no lower than 40–50 µg/L. Depending on the severity of anemia, treatment may be extended beyond 3 months, monitored by normalization of free iron concentration (above 30 ng/mL) [16].

Thus, with timely diagnosis of IDA, rational therapy with iron preparations is prescribed; treatment continues until the target hemoglobin level is achieved, under the control of clinical blood analysis and replenishment of iron stores.

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**ON THE EXPEDIENCY AND POSSIBILITY OF USING A SET
OF MEDICAL AND BIOLOGICAL RESEARCH METHODS
TO DETERMINE THE LEVEL OF READINESS FOR TRAINING
AND COMPETITION LOADS OF VARIOUS TYPES AMONG
HIGHLY QUALIFIED ATHLETES IN TEAM SPORTS**

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Abstract. *This publication demonstrates the feasibility of incorporating, within the training process and competitions of highly qualified team sport athletes, an assessment of readiness for various training loads. This assessment includes informative morphometric and hemodynamic parameters of cardiac activity, indices of autonomic regulation of heart rhythm, parameters of internal organ function, and biochemical blood markers (glucose, lactate, mmol/L). According to the authors, this is essential for planning and effective management of the training process and competitions within the annual preparation cycle. The article presents the results of original studies conducted on highly qualified handball athletes.*

Keywords: *adaptation, myocardium, diastole, transmitral blood flow, remodeling, internal organs, physical load, athletes, biochemical parameters.*

Introduction

The organization of the daily training process in elite sports necessitates constant collaboration between the coaching staff and the medical-biological support team. The outcomes of both the training process and competitive activity rely on the effective interaction of these specialists. The primary objective

of this collaboration is to achieve high athletic performance while maximizing the preservation of athlete health and preventing overtraining syndrome, which is a factor contributing to health impairment and decreased athletic performance [1]. One of the pressing issues during the implementation of training and competitive loads remains the readiness of the athlete's organism to withstand them. The feasibility of achieving the objectives set by the coaching staff depends on this. In our view, to achieve planned sports results, it is essential to monitor the dynamics of athletes' conditions using objective medical and biological screening methods. Recognizing the importance of rapid assessment of athletes' functional states under modern conditions necessitates adequate hardware capabilities for determining morphometric and hemodynamic parameters of the athlete's cardiovascular system (CVS), alongside specific biochemical blood markers (glucose, blood lactate, mmol/L) that reflect readiness for various physical loads. Furthermore, it is essential to perform a comprehensive assessment of the condition of internal organs actively involved in the recovery processes during exposure to training and competitive loads. Metabolic, hormonal, and enzymatic processes during physical exertion depend on the condition of endocrine organs, regulation of which is mediated through the hypothalamic-pituitary system [7].

From a practical perspective, information provided by the medical-biological support service can facilitate not only the determination of the functional status and readiness of a particular athlete for training loads and competitions but also the identification of the optimal starting lineup, the tactical distribution of players across the field (court), and the timing of necessary substitutions during the game. This may contribute to sports performance.

Currently, the assessment of readiness for physical workloads includes indicators of the cardiovascular system (CVS), autonomic regulation of heart rhythm, parameters of internal organ function, and biochemical blood markers.

The state of the CVS under conditions of continuous loads is monitored using morphometric and hemodynamic parameters of the myocardium, with mandatory indexing to anthropometric data, specifically body surface area and body mass index, along with data on autonomic regulation and parameters of central circulation.

In the seasonal training cycle, adaptation of CVS parameters depends on multiple factors: the structure of the training process with predominant use of loads differing in focus, athletic experience, comorbidities (injuries, upper respiratory infections, gastrointestinal diseases), individual anthropometric characteristics, and the condition of internal organs (which can be assessed by ultrasound diagnostics using portable diagnostic systems). During the adaptation of athletes to training and competition loads within the framework of long-term preparation, the morphometric parameters of the heart and internal organs change over an extended period. In highly qualified athletes (masters of sport and above), with a long, harmoniously

structured training process and planned intervals for rest and recovery, the morphometric parameters of the heart and internal organs remain within physiological norms. This is evidenced by our research and studies conducted on large samples of athletes, including international studies, which have documented a small percentage of hypertrophic myocardial changes [6]. Therefore, when monitoring and analyzing cardiac parameters, it is necessary to consider those indicators that change over an extended period of the training process, with indexing to anthropometric data (for example, the left ventricular myocardial mass index, LVMI), as well as indicators dependent on the level of readiness for various types of loads during the training process (assessment of heart rate variability, left ventricular hemodynamic parameters) [6,10]. In the assessment of readiness for training and competitive loads, besides morphometric indicators of the heart indexed to anthropometric data, it is necessary, in our view, to consider parameters of pulse rate (HR) and biochemical readiness of the athlete for physical exertion, which are determined at rest [10,3]. According to data [5,10], bradycardia (HR at rest below 60 beats per minute) reflects the adaptive capacity of the heart to load and constitutes one of the components of the athlete's heart. It has been established that the lower the resting HR, the higher the level of adaptation to various physical loads and the degree of fitness during endurance-related efforts [10].

Furthermore, for monitoring purposes, it is essential to determine not only HR values and heart rate variability (HRV) indices but also hemodynamic parameters of cardiac blood flow, with simultaneous measurement of resting blood lactate and glucose levels [3]. The values of lactate and glucose (mmol/L) in the blood in this case are regarded as indicators of the baseline state and the efficiency of the body's recovery systems [3].

The investigation of both hemodynamic parameters of the heart and parameters reflecting the condition of internal organs, as integral components of the organism's unified response to physical exertion, remains relevant. This is essential for monitoring physiological parameters of homeostasis both during physical activity and at rest. This is also important for explaining the sequence of changes in the functioning of physiological systems of the body during physical exertion and recovery. According to L. A. Bokeria (2009), the isolated use of HRV in forecasting CVS condition has moderate significance, but when combined with additional methods (for example, considering the left ventricular ejection fraction), the examination exhibits a higher sensitivity range for assessing the CVS state [2].

Our research indicates that when comparing resting HR values of two handball teams (Premier League and Super League) during the competitive period, the advantage in heart rhythm economy was established in favor of the higher-qualified team [11]. The average resting HR values reflect a higher level of readiness of the top division team to withstand various types of loads.

The diastolic component holds particular significance as an indicator of readiness to tolerate loads of different modalities. Its importance lies in the increased duration of the interval between heartbeats [8]. The diastole phase of the cardiac cycle is a principal component influencing the force and frequency of cardiac contractions. The effectiveness of the subsequent systole is inherently determined by the diastolic parameters [8]. Therefore, despite the assessment of morphometric heart parameters conducted during the current monitoring of the athlete, special attention should be paid to resting HR and the state of diastolic function, which reflect readiness parameters for performing physical loads at the current stage of the training process; the evaluation of these parameters allows for adjustments in the dosing of physical loads. An important point should be noted. In assessing diastolic function, it is preferable to rely on data obtained through hemodynamic Doppler studies as part of the comprehensive echocardiographic evaluation of the heart, which provides a standardized dataset regarding the systolic and diastolic functions of the athlete's heart (assessment of LVM and LVMI with parameters of early and late diastole).

Assessment of the condition of internal organs and biochemical blood parameters (lactate, glucose, mmol/L) supplements information on the body's homeostasis parameters during the execution of intensive loads of various types within long-term training systems. Therefore, in our opinion, it is necessary to develop an algorithm for analyzing the condition of internal organs of highly qualified athletes, which can be applied at various stages of the training process. For this purpose, within the Super League team framework, it is necessary to establish a laboratory equipped to assess both morphological and functional parameters of the heart and internal organs. For these purposes, it is necessary to employ portable ultrasound systems, heart rate variability assessment devices (e.g., VNS-micro) with accompanying software, as well as portable blood lactate and blood glucose analyzers. Based on the analysis of research findings by E. A. Gavrilova (2019), O. A. Butova (2011), and our own studies, we propose an algorithm for evaluating the athlete's condition using the following parameters: assessment of anthropometric data (height, weight, BMI, body surface area); evaluation of heart rate and autonomic regulation; assessment of systolic and diastolic cardiac function indexed to anthropometric data; evaluation of internal organ parameters (particularly the sizes of the liver, spleen, kidneys, and thyroid gland); and assessment of resting blood glucose and lactate levels. This examination algorithm can be implemented taking into account the design of the training process, based on the analysis of load intensity. The algorithm for assessing an athlete's readiness for training and competition loads may involve the sequential resolution of tasks at various stages and during different periods of the annual training cycle:

1. Evaluate the anthropometric parameters of highly qualified athletes.

2. Assess pulse and autonomic regulation parameters of athletes at rest simultaneously with measurements of systolic and diastolic cardiac function.
3. Assess the parameters of athletes' internal organs (dimensions of the liver, pancreas, kidneys, and spleen).
4. Evaluate blood lactate and glucose levels (mmol/L) at rest.
5. Determine the significance of differences and identify correlational relationships between the obtained data.
6. Develop a set of theoretical and practical recommendations for adjusting the training process, load dosing regimen, nutrition, recovery, and both pharmacological and non-pharmacological correction of functional status to enhance sports performance.

In our view, the implementation of the proposed algorithm may have broad practical applicability. For example, it will facilitate the resolution of a range of tasks aimed at achieving high athletic performance both during the competitive season and in the long term. Having data on athlete condition will enable the construction of a balanced training process with an appropriate alternation of training loads of varying focus. Below, we present possible variants for the application of information on athlete condition throughout the annual training cycle.

Assessment of anthropometric indicators in evaluating physical condition is essential both for designing the training process according to the athlete's specific role and for selecting suitable nutrition and recovery interventions.

Evaluation of autonomic regulation parameters, alongside systolic and diastolic function indices, will specifically allow the use of approved pharmacological complexes combined with physiotherapeutic and reflexotherapy recovery methods after exertion, as well as enable the classification of athletes into groups considering their health status and training intensity throughout training cycles [4].

Determining the relationships between anthropometric data, autonomic regulation of rhythm, cardiac activity parameters (systolic and diastolic functions), and the condition of internal organs will enable a more comprehensive and balanced assessment of athletes' functional capacities at various stages of the training process (during different periods of the annual preparation cycle) and the prompt implementation of medical and biological correction with the prescription of recovery methods and means based on specific indications.

Compared to healthy male individuals who do not participate in sports, athletes exhibit a significant advantage in resting HR parameters, morphometric indices (LVM and LVMI, relative wall thickness of the left ventricle, RWT), and diastolic function parameters [11]. This ultimately accounts for differences in physical performance capacity under aerobic and anaerobic loads: the functional capabilities of the heart in highly qualified athletes are superior due to economization of the diastolic phase and a shift towards the creatine phosphokinase pathway for energy

provision at rest [3], with a minimal level of glycolytic energy metabolism. In our opinion, these indicators can be used both for the current assessment of an athlete's condition and for evaluating changes within the long-term preparation system of professional athletes, with mandatory correlation to physical development indicators and linkage to the stages of the long-term training process.

It should be noted that hemodynamic parameters of the left heart chambers during diastole at rest in highly qualified athletes differ significantly from those of individuals not engaged in sports [9]. From this perspective, the significance of the mechanism responsible for the duration of diastolic relaxation and the total duration of diastole becomes more evident. Prolonged temporal parameters encompassing early and late diastole (isovolumetric relaxation time, IVRT, plus ejection time, ET, into the left ventricle), under conditions of reduced heart rate with a tendency toward bradycardia, extend the duration of the diastolic phase and reduce the contribution of atrial contractions, thereby promoting a more economical cardiac function at rest. The aforementioned factors determine the economization of cardiac activity in athletes at rest, manifested as a significant reduction in HR in beats per minute compared to individuals not involved in sports [9]. In studies comparing qualification groups of athletes, as previously noted, resting HR in elite athletes is significantly lower than that of athletes competing in the premier league [11]. As HR is an indicator influenced by autonomic factors, we plan to further investigate the correlation between autonomic regulation parameters and cardiac hemodynamic parameters at various stages of the training process [10].

The prognostic significance for the training process of highly qualified athletes is conferred by resting HR indicators, the ratio of early to late diastolic blood flow velocities (E/A peak ratio) at rest, values of left ventricular myocardial mass and left ventricular myocardial mass index (LVM and LVMI), and systolic and diastolic blood pressure measures during recovery following aerobic and glycolytic load exercises. An E/A ratio greater than 2 units is a prognostic indicator of cardiac resilience to intensive aerobic and anaerobic glycolytic loads, observed in highly qualified athletes at a resting HR below 64 beats per minute, and correspondingly during bradycardia (HR less than 60). This reflects the presence of a 'Supernormal' variant of transmitral blood flow remodeling in athletes and serves as a marker of the reserve adaptive capacity in trained individuals, as confirmed by aerobic performance results in the Cooper test and anaerobic performance in the 300 m run test conducted in our previous studies [9].

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THE ROLE OF BURSONATAL IN MODULATING CUTANEOUS INFLAMMATION: AN ANALYTICAL REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: *Inflammatory processes of the skin underlie a wide range of dermatological and functional conditions, accompanied by impaired barrier function and slowed tissue repair. In the context of searching for agents that combine regulation of inflammation and support of regeneration, tissue preparations of biological origin are of interest. Bursonatal is a polypeptide complex obtained from the bursa of Fabricius of birds, containing biologically active components potentially capable of participating in the regulation of cellular and immune processes. The aim of the study is to conduct an analytical assessment of the mechanisms of skin inflammation and, based on data on the composition and biological properties of bursonatal, to formulate scientifically substantiated hypotheses of its possible anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory action in topical application. Methods of structured literature analysis and construction of a mechanistic model of interaction of the components of the complex with key links of the inflammatory response were used. The obtained results allow the assumption that bursonatal may contribute to the modulation of inflammation through an effect on cellular proliferation, cytokine balance, and restoration of the skin barrier function.*

Keywords: *bursonatal, tissue preparations, skin inflammation, immunomodulation, peptide complexes, skin regeneration.*

Skin is a highly specialized organ that performs not only the functions of a physicochemical barrier but also those of an integrated immunoregulatory system, ensuring the maintenance of tissue homeostasis at the “organism–external environment” interface. The stratum corneum and epidermal lipid lamellae form the primary barrier to the penetration of xenobiotics and microbial agents, whereas cellular elements of the epidermis and dermis (keratinocytes, Langerhans cells, dermal dendritic cells, macrophages, mast cells) implement mechanisms of innate and adaptive immune responses. Under physiological conditions, these systems function in a coordinated manner, maintaining a balance between tolerance to the resident microbiota and the rapid initiation of protective reactions in response to injury or infection.

Cutaneous inflammation is a common response to physical, chemical, and biological stimuli and is characterized by a multistage cascade of events: activation of keratinocytes and the endothelium, release of pro-inflammatory mediators and chemokines, recruitment of neutrophils and monocytes, and increased oxidative stress. In the early stages, a key role is played by signaling pathways associated with IL-1, IL-6, TNF- α , and other mediators, which lead to local vasodilation, increased vascular permeability, and the formation of a cellular infiltrate. Under physiological conditions, the inflammatory phase is limited in time and then transitions to a repair stage that includes keratinocyte proliferation and migration, fibroblast activation, extracellular matrix remodeling, and restoration of barrier properties. However, when inflammation is excessive or prolonged, a vicious cycle develops: barrier dysfunction increases transepidermal water loss, heightens sensitivity to irritants, facilitates colonization by opportunistic microorganisms, and, as a result, sustains chronic low-grade inflammation and slows epithelialization.

The practice of topical therapy for inflammatory skin lesions has traditionally relied on symptomatic suppression of the inflammatory reaction (including the use of corticosteroids and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory components) and on control of the microbial load (antiseptics/antibacterial agents). At the same time, long-term use of some anti-inflammatory agents is limited by the risk of adverse effects, and antimicrobial approaches do not always ensure restoration of the regenerative potential of tissues or normalization of barrier function. This determines the need to search for agents with a more “modulating” profile of action — agents capable of selectively adjusting the inflammatory response, accelerating the transition to the reparative phase, and supporting physiological restoration of the epidermis without marked suppression of protective mechanisms.

In this context, tissue bioregulatory complexes are of interest, as they contain a set of low- and medium-molecular-weight biologically active compounds that may influence cellular communication and provide metabolic support for regeneration. Bursonatal belongs to tissue-derived preparations obtained from the avian bursa

of Fabricius, a primary lymphoid organ functionally associated with the development of the B-cell arm of immunity. According to published data, preparations of this origin have a complex composition that includes amino acids, trace elements, and peptide fractions, which, in theory, may be linked to regulation of cellular proliferative activity and immune signaling. For topical application, key questions remain regarding the mechanistic interpretation of a possible effect: which parts of the inflammatory cascade may be responsive to the complex, how the transition from inflammation to repair may change in its dynamics, and what limitations the barrier properties of the skin impose on the realization of its biological potential.

The analysis of current concepts of cutaneous inflammation and data on tissue-derived preparations from the bursa of Fabricius made it possible to identify a central issue in topical therapy: in clinically relevant scenarios, the inflammatory response of the skin is rarely an “isolated” reaction to injury. More often, it is maintained by a self-sustaining loop in which barrier dysfunction, microbial stimuli, and epidermal stress responses reinforce one another. Within this loop, keratinocytes act not only as structural cells but also as key effector elements of innate immunity, capable of initiating and maintaining pro-inflammatory signaling via IL-1, IL-6, TNF- α , and chemokine mediators. Under favorable conditions, the inflammatory phase is limited in time and is followed by resolution of inflammation and repair, whereas when the barrier is compromised (increased TEWL, reduced lipid content, microdamage), stimulation by “danger” signals persists and shifts inflammation into a prolonged mode.

Based on a comparison between the mechanisms of the inflammatory cascade and the functionally significant groups of compounds described for bursonatal (the amino acid component, the trace-element profile, and peptide/oligopeptide fractions), an author-developed mechanistic model of “modulation rather than suppression” was formulated. In this model, the presumed effect of the complex is not reduced to blocking inflammatory mediators; instead, it consists in accelerating the shift from the pro-inflammatory phase to the reparative phase while preserving the baseline protective response. The model includes three interrelated levels of action that correspond to the logic presented in the Introduction.

The first level is epidermal–barrier. In conditions where barrier failure is a critical factor in the chronicity of inflammation, the greatest effect is expected from interventions capable of stabilizing epidermal homeostasis: supporting the metabolic competence of keratinocytes, optimizing their proliferation and differentiation, and thereby restoring the integrity of the stratum corneum. Within this logic, the amino acid component of bursonatal is interpreted as a metabolic and structural basis for protein synthesis and tissue repair, whereas trace elements are viewed as cofactor support for enzyme systems involved in repair. Importantly, the proposed “barrier effect” is considered not as mechanical occlusion, but as a biologically mediated

acceleration of normalization of epidermal structure, which in theory should reduce TEWL and decrease sensitivity to repeated stimulation by irritants.

The second level is cellular–reparative. Skin repair requires coordinated activity of keratinocytes (epithelialization) and fibroblasts (synthesis and remodeling of the extracellular matrix). Publications on preparations derived from the bursa of Fabricius discuss indications of effects on the proliferative potential of cells, which allows a hypothesis to be proposed regarding a possible strengthening of the “reparative arm” of the inflammatory response. Within the model, bursonatal is considered as a factor that may facilitate switching the tissue response from a “defense/damage” mode to a “recovery” mode, shortening the duration of epidermal defects and thereby disrupting the self-sustaining inflammatory loop.

The third level is immunoregulatory. Cutaneous inflammation is determined not only by the absolute levels of pro-inflammatory mediators, but also by their relationship to signals that initiate the resolution of inflammation and reparative processes. In this connection, a hypothesis was formulated that regulatory peptide fractions of bursonatal may affect the balance between pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory signals, shifting response dynamics toward resolution of inflammation. Importantly, this refers not to direct “anti-inflammatory” suppression, but to modulation of the response profile: reducing the likelihood of prolonged inflammation while simultaneously strengthening parameters of repair.

To increase the testability of the model, a set of predicted observable effects (operationalization of the hypotheses) and corresponding biomarkers was proposed. As barrier endpoints, it is appropriate to assess TEWL and indices of stratum corneum hydration; as markers of inflammatory activity, levels of IL-1/IL-6/TNF- α and chemokines in the local environment (exudate/washes), as well as indicators of cellular stress; as reparative outcomes, the rate of epithelialization, parameters of cell migration/proliferation in *in vitro* models, and the dynamics of matrix remodeling in tissue systems. Thus, an original result of the present study is the developed conceptual map of bursonatal “nodes of action” within the inflammatory process of the skin and the proposed scheme of measurable effects, enabling a transition from descriptive reasoning to experimentally testable assumptions.

The proposed model directly follows from the key thesis of the Introduction: the skin functions as an immunoregulatory system, and inflammation within it is not only a pathological phenomenon but also a physiological mechanism of protection and restoration. Consequently, promising topical agents should not simply suppress the inflammatory phase, but should adjust its dynamics so that the protective response does not become chronic and repair occurs in a timely and complete manner. It is within this logic that the potential role of bursonatal is considered — as a complex capable of supporting tissue homeostasis through a combination of metabolic support, regulatory signals, and an indirect effect on barrier competence.

In practice, the problem of topical therapy often lies in the fact that suppression of inflammatory symptoms does not eliminate the primary driver — barrier dysfunction. When elevated TEWL and microdamage persist, penetration of irritants and microbial factors continues to increase, maintaining a “trigger” mode in keratinocytes. Under these conditions, even an effective symptomatic anti-inflammatory agent may produce only a short-term effect, because after discontinuation the barrier remains functionally weak and the inflammatory cascade is easily reactivated. Therefore, the hypothesis that bursonatal acts as a factor promoting restoration of epidermal homeostasis and accelerating repair is of fundamental importance: it proposes a different direction — not “suppression of the response,” but “shifting the system out of a self-sustaining inflammatory state.”

The immunological specificity of the preparation’s origin from the bursa of Fabricius strengthens the rationale for the immunoregulatory hypothesis. In theoretical terms, this makes it possible to assume the presence in the complex of fractions capable of contributing to fine regulation of cellular responses (including signaling interactions critical for shifting inflammation toward resolution). However, this is precisely where a key methodological challenge arises: modulation of inflammation is dose-dependent and context-dependent. For the skin as an organ in constant contact with antigens and microbiota, excessive immune stimulation is as undesirable as excessive suppression. Accordingly, the promise of bursonatal is determined not by maximizing any single effect, but by shaping a balanced activity profile that manifests as accelerated repair and reduced tendency toward prolonged inflammation without loss of baseline protective reactivity.

A separate barrier-related biopharmaceutic limitation should be considered: large molecules and peptide fractions have low ability to penetrate through an intact stratum corneum. However, the conditions discussed in this work (superficial damage, irritation, maceration, chronic barrier insufficiency) are often accompanied by partial disruption of barrier integrity and changes in the lipid organization of the stratum corneum, which in theory increases the accessibility of active fractions in the superficial layers of the epidermis. This means that the most reasonable therapeutic niche for topical bursonatal is associated with areas of functionally impaired barrier, where local bioavailability may be higher and the effect more pronounced. At the same time, this circumstance increases requirements for safety and standardization: variability in the composition of biological preparations and differences in barrier status among patients may lead to different response intensity.

From an evidence perspective, the proposed model should be viewed as a framework for designing experiments. The most convincing test of the hypothesis will be a combination of three lines of data: (1) confirmation of a reparative effect in keratinocyte/fibroblast models (proliferation, migration, differentiation markers), (2) assessment of the cytokine profile and signs of a shift toward resolution of

inflammation, and (3) measurement of restoration of barrier function (TEWL, hydration, stratum corneum parameters). The combination of barrier, cellular, and immune endpoints will make it possible to distinguish a “symptomatic” effect from a “modulating” one and to confirm that the proposed influence on inflammation is realized through disruption of the self-sustaining loop of “barrier insufficiency–inflammation–repeated stimulation.”

A limitation of the present study is the absence of original experimental data and reliance on interpretation of published information on tissue-derived preparations and the components of the complex. At the same time, the value of this work lies in moving the discussion of bursonatal from a general description of “biological activity” to specific mechanistic scenarios and measurable predictions. In practical terms, this provides a basis for rational planning of further research — from standardization of the fractional composition and safety assessment to development of biomarker protocols to demonstrate a modulating effect in inflammatory skin conditions.

Cutaneous inflammation is a regulated process that depends on the balance between pro-inflammatory and reparative mechanisms. Bursonatal, as a tissue-derived polypeptide complex, contains biologically active components that may participate in cellular regulation. A hypothesis has been formulated that its action occurs by accelerating the transition from inflammation to the tissue-repair phase. Promising directions include studies of the preparation’s effects on cellular proliferation and the cytokine profile.

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**LYOPHILISED DRY EXTRACT OF ARTEMISIA GYPSACEA:
PREPARATION, CHEMICAL COMPOSITION
AND MEDICINAL VALUE**

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Abstract. *Artemisia gypsacea* is an endemic medicinal plant of Turkmenistan known for its rich content of bioactive terpenoids and sesquiterpene lactones. Traditional extraction methods often lead to the degradation of these heat-sensitive compounds. **Methods:** This study developed a specialized technology for obtaining a high-quality dry extract using lyophilization (vacuum-freezing). The process involved primary freezing at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ followed by a controlled 48-hour sublimation cycle reaching a final temperature of $+20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The chemical profile was analyzed via Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) without additional derivatization. **Results:** The lyophilized extract exhibited a highly porous cellular structure, ensuring rapid dissolution and enhanced bioavailability. The yield of the obtained dry extract was 14.3% based on the dry weight of the raw material. GC-MS analysis identified 9 primary bioactive constituents, including Propyl propionate, α -Pinene, 1,4-Cineole, Limonene, Trifluoroacetyl- α -terpineol, 2-Carene, Tetradecane, 2-Decyn-1-ol, 2-Butyl-5-methyl-3-(2-methylprop-2-enyl) cyclohexanone with a higher preservation rate of volatile components. These compounds provide the extract with significant antiseptic, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory

properties. Conclusion: Lyophilization is a superior technology for producing stable, high-concentration medicinal raw materials from *Artemisia gypsacea*, offering strategic advantages for the pharmaceutical industry.

Keywords: *Artemisia gypsacea*, Lyophilization, Dry Extract, 14.3% Yield, GC–MS Analysis, Terpenoids, Bioavailability, Turkmenistan Flora.

Among the medicinal plants found in the rich flora of Turkmenistan, the genus *Artemisia* is distinguished by its unique bioactive substances. Our ancestors used wormwood in their centuries-old medical practice to treat various infectious and cold diseases, as noted in the multi-volume scientific encyclopedic book “Medicinal Plants of Turkmenistan” by the National Leader of the Turkmen people, Hero Arkadag [1]. Modern pharmacy combines this historical heritage with the achievements of new technologies, opening up a wide range of opportunities for obtaining highly effective medicinal products of plant origin.

Importance of the work. Valuable compounds such as terpenoids and sesquiterpene lactones contained in wormwood (*Artemisia gypsacea*) can lose their properties at high temperatures. Therefore, the lyophilization (vacuum-freezing) method of solidifying plant extracts at low temperatures (from $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) ensures the high preservation of volatile components such as eucalyptol and spathulenol [3; 8]. Lyophilized dry extract due to its cellular structure has a high solubility in water, which increases the bioavailability of the drug.

Purpose of the work. To develop a technology for obtaining high-quality dry extract from *Artemisia gypsacea* by lyophilization, to determine the volatile compounds in its composition and to study the pharmaceutical value of the obtained product.

Objectives. To select a suitable extraction method from the above-ground part of *Artemisia gypsacea*. To determine the technological parameters of converting the liquid extract into a dry form by lyophilization, to determine the physicochemical properties of the obtained dry extract, as well as its chemical composition (terpenoids and sesquiterpene lactones) using the modern analytical method GC–MS, and to substantiate its pharmaceutical value.

Materials and methods. The above-ground raw materials for the study of wormwood were collected from the Levishgen Valley, located south of the village of Gurykhovdan in the Central Kopetdag, at geographical coordinates $37.753637\text{ }^{\circ}\text{N}$, $58.628960\text{ }^{\circ}\text{E}$, on June 19, 2022 [2]. The collected raw materials were dried and rolled for two weeks in accordance with the drying conditions for medicinal plant raw materials containing essential oils, and then sieved using sieves with a pore size of 2 mm, and raw material samples with a size range of 0.5–2.0 mm were selected. Then, to prepare the extract from the selected small raw material samples of a certain size, purified water was selected as the solvent, and an aqueous extract was prepared by remacerating in a ratio of 1:10 in a water bath at a temperature

of 60–65 °C for 2 hours. Our prepared aqueous extract was filtered from the raw material samples using a four-layer filter and, to convert it into a thick extract, was placed in a special flask of a vacuum evaporator and evaporated at a temperature of 40°C. After the thick extract was formed, it was placed in a wide-mouthed glass jar and placed at a temperature of –80 °C for 24 hours, and then solidified by freezing. Our completely frozen solid extract was placed in a lyophilizer and lyophilized by raising the temperature to +20 °C for 48 hours according to a specially designed method. The yield of the lyophilized dry extract was determined to be 14.3% relative to the dry weight of the initial plant material.

The yield of lyophilized dry extract of wormwood was expressed as a percentage by calculation of the dry weight of wormwood raw material.

Physical properties of lyophilized dry extract of wormwood: light brownish yellow fine powder, the powder is initially loose or non-sticky, after some time it becomes slightly sticky, has a characteristic weak or almost no odor, the taste is bitter and slightly bitter (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Lyophilised dry extract of *Artemisia gypsacea*.

Biologically active compounds in the dry extract of wormwood obtained by lyophilization were determined by GS-MS analysis and identified using the NIST program database. GS-MS analysis was carried out without using additional derivatization methods to identify volatile terpenoid compounds and sesquiterpenoids in the extract. This allowed us to preserve the natural phytochemical composition of the plant and accurately identify the original form of its volatile compounds (Figure 2).

Thus, the natural phytochemical components of the plant were analyzed without modification. In future studies, it is planned to use the derivatization method to identify heavier molecular (polar) compounds in the extract.

Results and pharmaceutical significance.

Lyophilized dry extract of wormwood offers several strategic advantages for the modern pharmaceutical industry:

Stability and high concentration of substances: bioactive substances in the extract obtained by the lyophilization method, mainly volatile terpenoids and

unstable sesquiterpene lactones, are stably preserved as microencapsulated in the powder. This allows extending the shelf life of the drug by 3–4 times compared to conventional liquid extracts [3].

Figure 2. Chromatogram of GS-MS analysis of lyophilized dry extract of wormwood without derivatization.

Lyophilized dry powder is a ready-made raw material for “pre-formulation”. It does not require additional thermal processing in the pharmaceutical industry for the preparation of dosage forms such as granules, granules (capsules). This saves energy consumption in production and reduces the risk of dispersion of substances.

The powder structure of the dry extract obtained by this method is highly porous, and it dissolves quickly when it comes into contact with a liquid. From a pharmaceutical point of view, this property ensures rapid absorption of the drug in the gastrointestinal tract and the onset of its therapeutic effect in a short time [5; 10].

The dry extract is lighter and less bulky than the liquid form of the drug. This simplifies the transportation (logistics) of the medicinal product and creates great advantages for its export to the international pharmaceutical market.

The identified substances in the composition of the lyophilized dry extract and their medicinal value.

The combination of the 9 main bioactive components (including Propyl propionate, α -Pinene, 1,4-Cineole, Limonene, Trifluoroacetyl- α -terpineol, 2-Carene, Tetradecane, 2-Decyn-1-ol, 2-Butyl-5-methyl-3-(2-methylprop-2-enyl) cyclohexanone) identified in the lyophilized extract of *Artemisia gypsacea* provides its versatility as a medicinal agent:

Antiseptic and antibacterial effect: The presence of α -Pinene, 1,4-cineole, and camphene exhibits high activity against pathogenic microorganisms. It is noted that these substances are stable in the lyophilized powder, increasing the therapeutic effect in infectious diseases of the respiratory tract and gastrointestinal tract [4; 7; 8].

Antioxidant and immunomodulator: Limonene and 2-decyn-1-ol (alkyne alcohol) are noted to strengthen the body's defense system by resisting cell oxidation and neutralizing free radicals [9].

Antipyretic and analgesic effects: The specific derivative Trifluoroacetyl- α -terpineol, identified via GC-MS, and the detected ketone compounds demonstrate a targeted impact on the foci of inflammation within tissues. According to scientific reviews, α -terpineol and its derivatives act as potent anti-nociceptive agents by inhibiting the production of inflammatory mediators such as prostaglandins (PGE2) and suppressing the NF- κ B signaling pathway. This dual action on both peripheral pain receptors and central nervous system pathways effectively relieves pain and reduces febrile responses, providing a scientifically substantiated antipyretic effect [5, 6].

Summary. As a result of scientific research, it was found that the lyophilization (vacuum-freezing) method is a suitable technology for preserving the phytochemical composition and medicinal properties of the endemic medicinal plant of Turkmenistan, wormwood. Studies have shown that the lyophilization process allows for the sufficient preservation of volatile terpenoids and heat-labile sesquiterpene lactones in the plant. The medicinal properties of 9 main bioactive compounds, such as α -pinene, 1,4-cineole and limonene, identified by GS-MS analysis, scientifically substantiate the fact that this extract has a strong antiseptic, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effect. From a technological point of view, the cellular (porous) structure of the lyophilized dry extract ensures its rapid solubility in water and bioavailability of medicinal substances, which indicates its great importance in the preparation of "fast-acting" drugs in modern pharmaceuticals.

Thus, it can be noted that the lyophilized dry extract of wormwood, with its high chemical stability, physicochemical properties, and rich phytochemical composition, is a scientifically and practically promising medicinal raw material for the preparation of new, highly effective medicinal products based on the latest achievements of science and technology in the pharmaceutical industry. It will be of particular importance in the scientific use of the gene pool of the country's plant world and the preparation of modern medicinal products.

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PRODUCTION AND STANDARDIZATION OF DRY EXTRACT FROM MARIANUM SEEDS

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Annotation. *The scientific article describes the production and standardization of a dry extract from milk thistle seeds. According to scientific data, milk thistle seeds contain 40 different medicinal and nutritional substances. Milk thistle seeds contain up to 30% oil, the main part of which is linoleic acid — 54%, oleic acid — 36% and palmitic acid — 8%. The main active ingredient of milk thistle seeds is flavolignan compounds or a silymarin complex.*

Keywords: *marsh marigold, flavolignan, dry extract, standardization, spectrophotometry, high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC).*

Introduction. The medicinal plant milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*) was used by ancient healers as a tonic for liver diseases, capable of alleviating congestion in the liver and spleen, and as an effective remedy for jaundice. In Turkmen folk medicine, milk thistle seeds were used to treat pain caused by gallstones, jaundice, disorders of the liver and biliary tract, spleen, hemorrhoids, and constipation, as well as a strengthening and tonic agent for the body. Milk thistle belongs to the genus of the same name within the Asteraceae family. Scientific data indicates that there are two species of this medicinal plant worldwide, with one species found in Turkmenistan [1; 6; 12].

According to scientific data, milk thistle seeds contain 40 different medicinal and nutritional substances. The seeds contain up to 30% oil, primarily composed of linoleic acid — 54%, oleic acid — 36%, and palmitic acid — 8%. The main

active component of milk thistle seeds is considered to be flavolignan compounds, also known as the silymarin complex. This compound includes silybin A and B, silychristin, isosilychristin, isosilybin A and B, dehydrosilybin, silydianin, and the flavonoid taxifolin. The primary components are the diastereoisomers silybin A and B, which account for 50–70 % of the flavolignans, followed by silychristin, silydianin, and isosilybin [5; 8; 9].

The safety and high therapeutic effect of milk thistle as a phytopreparation for the treatment of liver diseases have been scientifically confirmed by scientists of the World Health Organization. In 1970, the silymarin flavonolignan complex from milk thistle was officially recognized in the medical system as a medicinal product with hepatoprotective properties [9].

When using milk thistle seeds for medicinal purposes, according to the European and American Pharmacopoeias, a standard of 1.5–2 % silymarin in the dry weight of mature fruits is considered normal. However, extensive scientific data indicates that the amount of silymarin in seeds can vary depending on the plant's genotype and cultivation conditions. According to some scientific data, its content ranges from 0.62 to 6%. According to the European Pharmacopoeia, the standard content of flavonolignan compounds in dry milk thistle extract, obtained by various methods, is considered to be 35–65 % [7; 10].

In our previous studies of the phytochemical composition of milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*) growing in Turkmenistan, its seeds showed a moisture content of 4.9%, total ash of 5.5%, ash insoluble in 10% hydrochloric acid of 3.8%, flavolignan content of 2.9%, and seed oil of 20.12%. Additionally, light brown and yellowish-brown dry extracts were obtained by Soxhlet extraction [2].

The purpose of research is to obtain a dry extract from milk thistle seeds (*Silybum marianum*) grown in Turkmenistan and to standardize the resulting dry extract.

Materials and Methods. For this study, milk thistle seeds collected in the Nyare valley of Magtymguly etrap on July 25, 2024, were used.

Total ash of dry milk thistle seed extract [10].

3.0 g of dry extract were placed into empty crucibles. The dry extract was then incinerated to ash in a muffle furnace for 20 minutes, first at 100 °C and subsequently at 500 °C. Afterward, the crucibles containing the ash were transferred to a desiccator and cooled to room temperature. The crucibles with the ash were weighed on an analytical balance, and the mass was calculated using a formula:

$$x = \frac{m_1 * 100 * 100}{m_2 * (100 - W)},$$

where, m_1 – ash weight, g;
 m_2 – mass of the sample, g;
 W – sample humidity.

Ash of *Silybum marianum* Dry Extract, Insoluble in 10% Hydrochloric Acid [10]. To the residue inside the crucible after igniting the dry extract, 15 ml

of 10% hydrochloric acid solution was added. The crucible was covered with a watch glass and heated on a water bath for 10 minutes. The watch glass was rinsed, 5 ml of hot water was added to the crucible, and the mixture was filtered through ashless filter paper. The filter with the precipitate was washed with hot water until there was a negative reaction for chlorides in the running water. It was then transferred to the same crucible, dried, ignited, heated, and weighed. The amount of ash insoluble in 10% hydrochloric acid solution in absolutely dry raw material was calculated as a percentage using the formula.

$$x = \frac{(m_1 - m) * 100 * 100}{m_2 * (100 - W)};$$

where: m^1 – ash weight, g;
 m – filter weight, g;
 m^2 – weight of raw materials, g;
 W – humidity of raw materials, %

The pH value of the dry extract [10]. To determine the pH value of a dry extract, standard solutions with different pH values (pH 1.65, 3.56, 4.01, 6.86, 9.18, 12.43) were prepared, and a pH meter was calibrated. 1.0 g of the dry extract was dissolved in 50 ml of distilled water, and the pH value was determined.

Solubility test of dry milk thistle extract. The solubility test of dry milk thistle extract was conducted according to the pharmacopoeial monograph method. [3].

Table 1. Definition of Solubility for Pharmaceutical Substances and Excipients

Term	Approximate volume of solvent (ml) required to dissolve 1.0 g of the substance	Dry extract of milk thistle (<i>Silybum marianum</i>) (Water solubility)	Dry extract of milk thistle (<i>Silybum marianum</i>) (Solubility in 96% alcohol)
Very easily dissolves	To 1		
Easily dissolves	From 1 to 10		
Soluble	From 10 to 30		Soluble
Moderately soluble	From 30 to 100	Moderately soluble	
Slightly soluble	From 100 to 1000		
Dissolves very little	From 1000 to 10 000		
Almost insoluble	More than 10 000		

Phytochemical Analysis of Dry Milk Thistle (*Silybum marianum*) Seed Extract [8; 10]. For the phytochemical analysis, extracts of dry milk thistle seeds were prepared at a 1:10 ratio using water, 80% ethanol, and petroleum ether.

Carbohydrate Analysis. Benedict's Test. Take 1.0 mL of the extract, filtered through paper, and add 1.0 mL of Benedict's reagent. Heat the mixture in a boiling water bath. The formation of a red precipitate indicates the presence of sugars in the dry extract.

Protein and Free Amino Acid Analysis. *Biuret Test.* To 2.0 ml of extract, diluted copper sulfate solution is added drop by drop. The formation of a red or pink hue indicates the presence of peptides with at least two peptide bonds.

Flavonoid Analysis. *Alkaline Reagent Test.* Add 3-4 drops of 2% sodium hydroxide solution to 2.0 ml of the extract. The formation of a bright yellow color in the solution, and its decolorization after adding 2-3 drops of diluted hydrochloric acid and shaking, indicates the presence of flavonoids.

Aluminum Chloride Test. To 1.0 ml of extract, filtered through a paper filter, add 2-3 drops of 5% aluminum chloride solution. If the extract contains flavonoids with two hydroxyl groups at the C3 and C5 positions, a lemon-yellow color will form.

Wilson's Test. To 2 ml of the extract, add 1-2 drops of boric acid solution and 1 drop of oxalic acid solution. If the plant extract contains 3- and 5-hydroxyflavones and 3- and 5-hydroxyflavonols, a light yellow color with a yellowish-green tint will form.

Tannin Test. *Ferric Chloride Test.* To 5.0 ml of the extract, add 2-3 drops of a 10% ferric chloride solution. A change in the solution's color to dark green indicates the presence of phenolic compounds.

Potassium Dichromate Analysis. Add 3-5 drops of a 5% potassium dichromate solution to 3.0 ml of the extract. If tannins are present, the solution darkens or a yellow-brown precipitate forms.

Saponin Test. **Froth Test.** Add 5.0 ml of purified water to 0.1 g of extract and shake vigorously. The formation of persistent froth indicates the presence of saponins.

Alkaloid Test. *Wagner's Reaction.* Dissolve the dry extract in dilute hydrochloric acid and filter. Use the filtered solution for the alkaloid test. To 1.0 ml of the plant extract, add 1.0 ml of Wagner's reagent. The formation of a reddish-brown precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

Glycoside Test. *Keller-Kiliani Reaction.* To 1.0 ml of the extract, add 0.5 ml of 0.1 N acetic acid, 2-3 drops of 2% ferric chloride solution, and then 5.0 ml of 98% sulfuric acid. The formation of two phases, i.e., reddish-brown and blue-green, indicates the presence of glycosides.

Steroid Test. *Libermann-Burchard Reaction.* Dissolve the dry extract in 2.0 ml of chloroform, add 10 drops of acetic anhydride, 5 drops of concentrated sulfuric acid, and mix. A color change from red to blue-green indicates the presence of steroids.

Cyanide Test. Place 0.05 g of dry milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*) extract into a test tube, pour 10 ml of 96% alcohol over it, and shake. Add 0.25 g of zinc powder and 1.0 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid and mix. The formation of a burgundy color indicates a positive result.

Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) Procedure. For the analysis, silymarin and a lyophilized extract of milk thistle were used. Each was dissolved in 10 mL of 60% ethanol solution at a concentration of 0.020 g. The ethanol extract of milk

thistle was then diluted 1:1 with 60% ethanol. As standard substances, 0.002 g of rutin was dissolved in 10 mL of methanol, and 0.005 g of quercetin was dissolved in 10 mL of methanol. The samples were applied to silica gel thin-layer plates. 10 μ L each of silymarin and the standard solutions were spotted, along with 30 μ L of the extract solution. The mobile phase consisted of anhydrous formic acid, acetone, and dichloromethane in a volumetric ratio of 8.5:16.5:75.

After air drying, the silica gel plates with the spotted samples were sprayed with the reagent – vanillin-sulfuric acid. This reagent was prepared by dissolving 1.0 g of vanillin in 2 mL of sulfuric acid and subsequently mixing it with 100 mL of 95% ethanol. The silica gel plates with the reagent were heated in an oven at 105-110 °C for 5 minutes. They were then examined under ultraviolet (UV) light at wavelengths of 254 nm and 365 nm [10].

Determination of Flavonolignans in Dry Extract [4]. To determine the quantity of flavonolignans, calculated as silybin, 0.02 g of precisely weighed dry extract was placed into a 25 mL volumetric flask and brought to the mark with distilled water (Solution A). Then, 5.0 mL of Solution A was transferred to another 25 mL volumetric flask and brought to the mark with 96% ethyl alcohol (Solution B). The optical density of Solution B was measured using a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 289 nm in a 1.0 cm quartz cuvette. 96% ethyl alcohol was used as the reference solution. The optical density of the standard alcoholic solution of silybin was also determined at a wavelength of 289 nm.

Preparation of Standard Silybin Solution. 20 mg of standard silybin was placed into a 100 mL volumetric flask, then 80 mL of 96% alcohol was added, and the mixture was heated in a water bath at 70°C-80°C. After cooling, the solution was brought to the mark with 96% ethanol (Standard Solution A). 1.0 mL of Standard Solution A was placed into a 25 mL volumetric flask, brought to the mark with 96% ethanol, and mixed by shaking (Standard Solution B).

The quantity of flavonolignans (X) in the dry extract of milk thistle was calculated as a percentage (%) in terms of silybin using the following formula:

$$X = \frac{D * m_0 * 100 * 25 * 25}{D_0 * m * 100 * 25 * 5};$$

where D — Optical density of the test solution;

D₀ — optical density of a standard solution of silybin;

m — dry extract mass, g;

m₀ — mass of silybin standard solution, g.

Ultraviolet spectrophotometric analysis of milk thistle dry extract was compared with the standard silybin spectrum from the Photochem CAD 3.0 database and the standard silybin's absorbance in the ultraviolet range. The characteristic wavelength for flavonolignan compounds was 288±2 nm, and this absorbance was also observed in the milk thistle dry extract at a wavelength of 288 nm.

Figure 2. From left to right: silybin spectrum (288 nm) presented in the Photochem CAD 3.0 database, silybin standard (288 nm), and UV spectra of a dry extract prepared from milk thistle seeds (288 nm).

The content of flavonolignans in a dry extract of milk thistle seeds was determined by direct spectrophotometry using an ultraviolet spectrophotometer (Agilent Cary 60, UV-Vis) at a wavelength of 288 nm, which is characteristic of silybin, and calculated as silybin. The metrological characteristics of the obtained results for flavonolignan content are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Metrological characteristic of the content of flavonolignans in dry extract of milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*).

No	Sample mass, g	Optical density (D)	X, %	Metrological characteristics
1	0.0210	2.408	39.13	Arithmetic mean: $\bar{X} = 40.12$ Standard Deviation: $S \approx 1.163$ Standard Error (SE): 0.368 Confidence Limit: lower – 39.29 Confidence Limit: upper – 40.96
2	0.0220	2.436	37.79	
3	0.0201	2.403	40.80	
4	0.0198	2.398	41.33	
5	0.0211	2.409	38.96	
6	0.0202	2.403	40.60	
7	0.0205	2.408	40.08	
8	0.0203	2.407	40.46	
9	0.0202	2.406	40.65	
10	0.0197	2.395	41.49	

Chromatographic Study. For the chromatographic investigation of flavonolignan compounds in dry milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*) seed extract, a high-performance liquid chromatograph (HPLC) (Agilent Technologies, 1260 Infinity HPLC system) equipped with a diode array detector (DAD) was used. Data acquisition, chromatogram processing, and absorption spectra analysis were performed using Chemstation software (Agilent Chemstation for LC 3D). A C-18 column (Zorbax Eclipse Plus C-18, rapid resolution 4.6x100 mm, 3.5 μm) served as the stationary phase. The mobile phase consisted of a mixture of 85% phosphoric acid:methanol:distilled

water in a volume ratio of 0.5:46:64, operated in isocratic mode. The flow rate of the mobile phase was 0.8 mL/min, the column temperature was 25°C, the injection volume was 50 μ L, and the detection wavelength was 288 nm. The duration of the analysis was 35 minutes. For the study, 5.0 mg of standard silymarin and dry milk thistle seed extract were dissolved in 50 mL of the solvent prepared as the mobile phase. The solutions were then filtered through a 0.45 μ m filter (Chromafil PET 45/25), and 50 μ L of each was injected into the chromatograph column [11].

Figure 3. Liquid Chromatographic Analysis of Standard Silymarin and Dry Milk Thistle Seed Extract

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The results of the phytochemical quantitative analysis of the dry extract from milk thistle seeds are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Results of Phytochemical Quantitative Analysis

Raw material	Humidity, %	Total ash content, %	Insoluble ash in 10% hydrochloric acid, %	Common flavonolignans, %
Milk thistle seeds	3.98	1.8	0.42	40.12

High-quality phytochemical analysis of dry milk thistle seed extract was performed by preparing extracts with water, 96% ethanol, and petroleum ether. The obtained results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Phytochemical Analysis of Milk Thistle Seeds

№	Phytochemical composition	Extractants		
		Water	Ethanol, 96%	Petroleum ether
1	Carbohydrates			
	Benedict's Test	+	+	-
2	Proteins and amino acids			

№	Phytochemical composition	Extractants		
		Water	Ethanol, 96%	Petroleum ether
	Biuret Test	-	+	+
3	Flavonoids			
	Alkaline Reagent Test	+	+	-
	Aluminum Chloride Test	+	+	-
	Wilson's Test	+	+	-
4	Flavonolignans			
	Cyanide Test	+	+	-
5	Tannins			
	Ferric Chloride Test	+	+	+
	Potassium Dichromate Analysis	+	+	-
6	Saponins			
	Froth Test	+	-	+
7	Alkaloids			
	Wagner's Reaction	-	+	-
8	Glycosides			
	Keller-Kiliani Reaction	+	+	-
9	Steroids			
	Libermann-Burchard Reaction	+	+	-

Thin-Layer Chromatography (TLC). In this method, flavonolignans form a yellowish-green fluorescent band, appearing in the same band as the silybin standard. Below this, a pink fluorescent band characteristic of taxifolin is formed.

Determination of Flavonolignan Content in Dry Extract. According to the European Pharmacopoeia, the standard content of flavonolignans in dry milk thistle extract is 30-65%. In our studies, the average flavonolignan content was 40.12%. High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) analysis of the dry milk thistle extract was conducted by comparing it with a silybin standard. A total of 18 substance peaks were detected during the analysis. The obtained results and information regarding the detected substances are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Substances identified in the analysis of standard silymarin and dry milk thistle seed extract by High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)

№	Silymarin standard	Milk thistle dry extract	Identified substances
	Rt, minute	Rt, minute	Name
1	1.278	1.205	-
2	-	1.444	-
3	-	1.563	-

№	Silymarin standard	Milk thistle dry extract	Identified substances
	Rt, minute	Rt, minute	Name
4	1.847	1.870	-
5	-	2.090	-
6	-	2.402	Taxifolin
7	-	2.608	-
8	3.727	3.747	-
9	3.963	4.025	-
10	4.300	4.290	Isosilicrystine
11	-	4.676	-
12	5.672	5.697	-
13	5.900	5.930	-
14	6.826	6.859	-
15	7.812	7.845	-
16	8.851	8.769	-
17	21.060	21.038	Silibin
18	25.242	25.202	Isosilibin

The standardization indicators for dry milk thistle extract were determined through the conducted research. These indicators are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Standardization indicators of dry milk thistle extract

Indicators	Standard *	Dry milk thistle extract
Description	A homogeneous, light yellowish-brown amorphous powder with a characteristic odor and a bitter taste.	+
Solubility	Soluble in alcohol, moderately soluble in water.	+
Establishment	Cyanide test	+
The weight that is lost during drying.	< 4.0%	3.98
pH	4.5-6.5	4.74
Total ash content	< 2.0%	1.8
Insoluble powder 10%-HCl	< 0.5%	< 0.42%
The content of flavolignans	30-65%*	40.12
*[7]		

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